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Describing and assessing the value of the existing and
potential Blue Economy in the North-East Tobago Man and
the Biosphere Reserve

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Abstract

In many parts of the world, humans are underachieving to sustainably use the oceans' potential for economic development and benefitting local communities, while threats to their ecosystems are steadily increasing. The concept of the Blue Economy aims to address this situation, as it embodies the dual need for inclusive economic development and marine health, seen as compatible dimensions. By promoting sustainable and equitable economic growth through ocean-related industries, the Blue Economy presents an excellent opportunity for Small Island Developing States (SIDS). In a rural region of the smaller of the twin islands of Trinidad and Tobago, a Caribbean SIDS, lies the North-East Tobago Man and the Biosphere Reserve (NETMABR). The significance of its coastal and marine environment as a driver of economic development has largely been overlooked by policy makers. There is no formal (comprehensive) knowledge about the current state and value of the Blue Economy, nor its potential in the NETMABR. Therefore, the thesis aims to fill these knowledge gaps. Participant observations, semi-structured and key-informant interviews conducted between October 2023 and February 2024 enabled this main objective to be achieved. The status quo of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR is described, and for the first time its value is assessed in detail. This is estimated to be between 41'685'727 TTD year⁻¹ and 48'688'153 TTD year⁻¹, equivalent to the range of 6'144'477 USD year⁻¹ – 7'176'635 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024. Contributing are tourism, artisanal fisheries, and shipbuilding and repair, which are the only presently existing Blue Economy activities. Moreover, the study finds that the Blue Economy holds vast potential in north-east Tobago, both in terms of improving the established sectors and developing new ones. A number of promising opportunities are proposed and discussed, while respecting local communities, and appropriate to the Biosphere Reserve. Crucial management measures for artisanal fisheries and tourism are recommended, along with practices to increase compliance. Some of the proposed changes could be introduced within the context of the North-East Tobago Marine Protected Area, planned to be part of the NETMABR in the future. This dissertation provides stakeholders and policy makers with a valuable baseline to understand the current local state of the Blue Economy and to plan areas for intervention and development.

Keywords: Blue Economy, Small Island Developing States (SIDS), Caribbean, small-scale artisanal fisheries, tourism, value assessment

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1| Introduction

1.1| The Blue Economy

Oceans cover about 71% of the Earth's surface and, among countless things, provide us with essential food, livelihoods, and ecosystem services. Keeping them and their resources healthy is very important for human and planetary health, as well as for the intrinsic value that marine life has in and of itself. However, the oceans have for too long been considered a limitless source of free resources and are now under severe threat, both from direct human activities such as overfishing, pollution, and destruction of coastal habitats and landscapes, and from the pressures of anthropogenic climate change like ocean warming and acidification. Due to the degradation of marine environments and all the significant changes the oceans are facing, they are currently underachieving their true capability in terms of economic development for many nations and regions (UNDP, 2018; Phang et al., 2023). This implies that the oceans still have enormous potential for economic growth, especially for coastal and island developing countries, provided that such growth is pursued in a sustainable manner. In fact, ocean- and coastal-based economic activities have the potential to boost local economies around the world, and if they are to be sustainable they will have to go beyond purely extractive and exploitative practices and incorporate conservation and marine spatial planning (McKinley et al., 2019).

It is exactly in this context that the concept of the Blue Economy comes into play. The term is quite recent and originated from the book "The Blue Economy: 10 years, 100 innovations, 100 million jobs" written by Gunter Pauli and published in 2010 (Pauli, 2010). Since then, it began to assume more and more importance worldwide, to the extent that it emerged and was discussed as a concept during the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development held in Rio de Janeiro in 2012, hereinafter referred to as Rio+20. A main theme of the conference was the advancement of the Green Economy, but many coastal and island developing countries questioned the concept and its applicability to them, demanding a Blue Economy approach to be addressed. These actors acknowledged that the oceans will play an essential role in the future of humankind and requested that the Blue Economy aligns more closely with their contexts (United Nations, 2014). In particular, it was the Pacific Island countries that pushed for the use of the Blue Economy terminology, while other Small Island Developing States (SIDS), such as those in the Caribbean, showed reservations towards it at Rio+20 (Dornan et al., 2018). In fact, in the lead up to the conference, Caribbean SIDS claimed that the expression 'Blue Economy' was unnecessary, and warned against "too many colour economies" (as quoted in Silver et al., 2015, p. 7). This opposition did not instantly recede and other expressions, such as 'sustainable ocean-based economy', were initially preferred (Hassanali, 2020). However, such resistance has not persisted to date, and the initial terminology is now commonly

used globally. Furthermore, since Rio+20, the concept of the Blue Economy has become extremely important, and it currently permeates every discussion related to the sustainable development of coastal and marine ecosystems. So much that it is reflected in Goal 14 (*Life below water*) of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which has set a call to “conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development” (United Nations, 2015a). The 17 SDGs are at the heart of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted in 2015 by all United Nations (UN) Member States, are based on sustainability, and are an urgent global call to action to end poverty and inequality, protect the planet, and ensure that by 2030 all people enjoy health, justice and prosperity (World Health Organisation, 2024). The SDGs are integrated and emphasise the interconnected environmental, social and economic aspects of development (Sachs, 2012). Since action in one area can affect outcomes in others, the transition to a Blue Economy will not only contribute to the achievement of SDG 14, but also have an important impact on the attainment of many others of the 17 SDGs (e.g., Goal 1: *No poverty*, Goal 2: *Zero hunger*, Goal 7: *Affordable and clean energy*, Goal 12: *Responsible consumption and production*, and Goal 13: *Climate action*).

Notwithstanding its immense relevance, the Blue Economy has no common agreed definition. On the contrary, a multitude of definitions exist for the concept, as it has been adopted by (and often adapted to the context of) many organisations and countries all over the world. This entails that there is a lack of consensus on what Blue Economy means on the ground (Wenhai et al., 2019), and such issue has surrounded the discussion of the term since its dawn. In fact, as noted by Silver et al. (2015), the term was used in many different ways even at Rio+20. According to the widespread definition given by the World Bank, “the Blue Economy is sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods and jobs, and ocean ecosystem health” (World Bank, 2017). At its core lies the decoupling of socio-economic development from environmental degradation, which shows how the concept emerged from the recognition of the ongoing deterioration of the oceans and associated resources, and the consequent need to integrate conservation and sustainability in their management (Smith-Godfrey, 2016; World Bank and UNDESA, 2017). In the Blue Economy it is recognised that economic activities depend on the status of the underlying ecological systems and thus have to be in balance with the long-term capacity of coastal and marine ecosystems (Patil, 2016), as well as with the communities depending on these. In the optimal vision of the Blue Economy framed by these definitions, all the activities that are part of it can be continued indefinitely (Pauly, 2018) and lead to improved social justice and human welfare. Being also linked to efficient resource use and minimisation of carbon emissions, the Blue Economy is meant to be a true holistic concept (Smith-Godfrey, 2016).

Despite the fact that according to various interpretations it is ideally based on a true underpinning of sustainability and equity, many coastal and island countries are adopting the opportunity of the Blue Economy without taking proper account of the risks and trade-offs associated with its development,

which is testified by many examples of habitat destruction, community displacement, and loss of fishing grounds around the world (Harper and Wabnitz, 2023). So, with time, Blue Economy discourses have leaned more towards a 'business as usual' (Cisneros-Montemayor, 2019). To reaffirm the need for a Blue Economy inclusive of social and ecological dimensions alongside the economic one, the balancing of which is a key component (UNDP, 2018), the conversation is shifting towards a 'sustainable Blue Economy' (Harper and Wabnitz, 2023). Therefore, nowadays to mean a Blue Economy based on meeting the needs of the present population without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own, and even more broadly based on the harmony among operations, supporting system and communities (Smith-Godfrey, 2016), we expressly talk about sustainable Blue Economy. And it is precisely this type of Blue Economy that is considered in this work (even if not always explicitly specified).

Many activities are part of the Blue Economy since it encompasses numerous industries and sectors.

Table 1. Components of a Blue Economy. Adapted from Smith-Godfrey (2016), World Bank (2016), and World Bank and UNDESA (2017)

Type of activity	Ocean service	Industry - Sector	Driver of growth
<i>Harvest of living resources</i>	Seafood	Fisheries Fisheries-related activities (e.g. processing, net and gear making, ice production and supply, boat construction and maintenance...)	Food security and demand for protein
	Marine biotechnology	Aquaculture Pharmaceuticals, chemicals...	Healthcare, medical, cosmetic and manufacturing industry demands
<i>Extraction of non-living resources and generation of new resources</i>	Minerals	Seabed mining	Demand for minerals
	Energy	Oil and gas	Demand for energy
		Renewables	Demand for alternative energy
Fresh water	Desalination	Demand for fresh water	
<i>Commerce and trade in and around the oceans</i>	Transport and trade	Shipbuilding and repair Shipping Port infrastructure and services	Growth in seaborne trade; international regulations
		Tourism and recreation	Eco-marine tourism Coastal development aimed at tourism
<i>Response to ocean health challenges</i>	Ocean monitoring and surveillance	Technology and R&D	R&D in ocean technologies
	Carbon sequestration	Blue Carbon	Climate mitigation
	Coastal protection	Habitat protection and restoration	Resilient growth
	Waste disposal	Assimilation of nutrients and wastes	Wastewater management
	Existence of biodiversity	Protection of species and habitats	Conservation

It has to be mentioned that just as no consensus seems to be reached on its clear definition, there are also differing opinions on what should be considered part of the Blue Economy. If the concept as previously explained is to be strictly followed, it should comprise only those sectors that are ecologically and socially sustainable. So, from this point of view, the oil and gas and seabed mining industries, unsustainable by their very nature since they are based on the exploitation of non-renewable resources (not to mention the rising concerns about irreversible damage to deep-sea habitats caused by seabed mining), should not be included within the Blue Economy. Proponents of this approach (e.g., Cisneros-Montemayor, 2019) argue that these industries can and must reduce their negative impacts, but their inclusion in the Blue Economy would undermine the framework. Other authors and entities consider oil and gas and seabed mining industries as important components of the Blue Economy (e.g., Hassanali, 2020; Patil, 2016).

1.2| The Blue Economy and Small Island Developing States

The Blue Economy represents a huge opportunity for the development of SIDS, and this has even been acknowledged in target 14.7 of SDG 14, centred on the need to “increase the economic benefits to Small Island Developing States and least developed countries from the sustainable use of marine resources, including through sustainable management of fisheries, aquaculture and tourism” by 2030 (United Nations, 2015b).

Small Island Developing States form a group of 39 countries recognised by the UN (United Nations, 2024). Ocean and coastal areas are an integral feature of them, not only because the related ecosystems often harbour highly valuable resources, but also because their Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) are generally many times larger than their land masses. Hence, in SIDS, people strongly rely on marine resources for food security, livelihoods, and economic development. In some cases there are few alternatives, as for example very small land areas limit agricultural possibilities. It is therefore understandable why ocean health is extremely important to SIDS (Techera and Appadoo, 2020), and why the Blue Economy approach is an excellent opportunity for them. In fact, it can help foster economic resilience and diversification, generate income and employment while managing marine resources sustainably. However, it has to be mentioned that financial, technological, institutional and technical capacity constraints of many SIDS can pose a significant barrier to their growth and Blue Economy development (Harper and Wabnitz, 2023), as well as the fact that they are the forefront of climate change. More generally, SIDS are considered to be structurally weak (Bakshi, 2019) and to face serious difficulties mainly from an environmental and socioeconomic point of view. This is demonstrated by a shared set of unique features and sustainable developmental challenges recognised by many authors (e.g., Hay et al., 2001; Turvey, 2007; Wong, 2011; Sha, 2019), which not only identify SIDS as a definite group but also highlight

their overall vulnerability (Bakshi, 2019). Despite the common traits, there are indeed many strong differences among them (for instance due to their geographical positions, culture, politics and social component), which is why SIDS should not be examined as a homogeneous group. This is especially important in a Blue Economy context, as there is no single model suitable for all countries and the scope of the Blue Economy approach in each of them varies according to the sector (UNDP, 2023).

1.3| Blue Economy prospects of Tobago

Tobago is the smaller of the two islands that constitute the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago, located at the southernmost end of the Caribbean archipelagic chain, 40km north-east of Venezuela (see Fig. 1). Although the country has many of the typical characteristics of SIDS, its context regarding the development of a Blue Economy is fairly different compared to its neighbours (UNESCO-IOC and IMA, 2021). The income level of Trinidad and Tobago is classified as high (World Bank, 2023), mainly due to its richness in terms of fossil fuels. In fact, the oil and gas sector is a major constituent of the economy and the primary contributor to GDP, typically accounting for about 40% of it (Ogeer, 2020). The industry is such a powerful player in the country's economy that it largely determines how the ocean is managed and has dominated the development discourse for decades (UNESCO-IOC and IMA, 2021). For this reason, along with the desire to strengthen other sectors (such as shipping), developing a sustainable Blue Economy has never really been considered a priority. Although the country has formulated overarching themes and goals in the direction of a Blue Economy development and policy objectives, and respective strategies to achieve them – noticeably in the Vision 2030 National Development Strategy of Trinidad and Tobago (Government of the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago, 2016) and in the draft National Integrated Coastal Zone Management Policy Framework (ICZM Inter-ministerial Committee, 2019) – evidence shows that virtually no strong and coordinated real action has been taken. Furthermore, the latter document, by which Trinidad and Tobago appears to be conscious of the social and environmental obligations in a Blue Economy development, was first submitted in 2014 but was never adopted because it was not regarded as urgent. Because of the elapsed time it was revised and resubmitted in 2019 (Hassanali, 2020), and was approved by the Cabinet only in August 2023 (Ministry of Planning and Development, 2024). Nevertheless, Trinidad and Tobago has been identified by the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) as a key country in which to explore new paths for growth within the Blue Economy (Phang et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Location map of Trinidad and Tobago. Source: <https://www.mapsland.com/>

In that regard, focussing on the smaller of the twin islands, the Blue Economy holds a great promise for Tobago, and particularly for its north-eastern region, given the special context in which it is situated. Much less affected by human impact and consequently less spoilt than the south-western region, north-east Tobago was declared a Biosphere Reserve by the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere Programme in 2020 (UNESCO, 2020). A Biosphere Reserve is an area comprising terrestrial, coastal, and marine ecosystems that demonstrates a balanced relationship between humans and the biosphere and promotes “solutions reconciling the conservation of biodiversity with its sustainable use” (UNESCO, 2024a). The North-East Tobago Man and the Biosphere Reserve (NETMABR), as it is officially called, crosses numerous ecosystems with many habitat types representative of the region, and is home to International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List, endemic, and Evolutionarily Distinct and Globally Endangered (EDGE) species (ERIC, 2019). In addition, it encompasses the oldest legally protected tropical forest reserve in the world, three Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs), and a large proposed Marine Protected Area (MPA), which was demonstrated to be of high ecological value (ERIC, 2019). The design process of the North-East Tobago MPA started in 2013 (Wothke et al., 2013), but is currently stalled and has not been further followed-up since 2019, when the establishment of this MPA was proposed again in the nomination form of the Biosphere Reserve. In fact, of the 834.88 km² of the NETMABR, 80.5% represents a planned MPA as a Marine Buffer Zone (ERIC, 2019; see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Zonation of the North-East Tobago Man and the Biosphere Reserve (prepared by ERIC)

There are 14 villages within the NETMABR area. Seven on the windward side of the island: Speyside, Delaford, Louis D'Or, Betsy's Hope, Roxborough, Argyle, and Belle Garden; and seven on the leeward coast: Moriah, Castara, Parlatuvier, Bloody Bay, L'Anse Fourmi, Hermitage, and Charlotteville. They are all small with 1000 or less residents, with the only exception of Roxborough (~2000) which also has some government facilities (ERIC, 2019).

Figure 3. Communities of the North-East Tobago Man and the Biosphere Reserve (prepared by ERIC)

Human interventions, albeit present, are relatively limited due to the low population density, the remoteness of the area, and the absence of large infrastructure and major economic interests. All of that implies enormous potential for the development of the Blue Economy, which is currently underdeveloped. In fact, of the several industries and sectors included in the general model as seen in Table 1, only three occur in the NETMABR: namely, fisheries, marine and coastal tourism, and shipbuilding and repair (the latter to a much lesser extent). Vast potential seems to exist both to improve these sectors and to develop new ones. Presently, a fully comprehensive description and overview of the Blue Economy and its potential is missing in the Biosphere Reserve and in Tobago in general. To the best of the author's knowledge, two publications on the topic of a sustainable Blue Economy with a nationwide focus have been produced (i.e., UNESCO-IOC and IMA, 2021; Commonwealth Secretariat, 2023), but as such, they are very general and do not contain much specific information on north-east Tobago. The only document dealing with its Blue Economy is the respective Component of the 10-years management plan for the NETMABR (ERIC, 2022a), as the management plan for the proposed MPA did not elaborate on that topic. So, the next step for the NETMABR is to possibly confirm the high economic value that the marine area has (alongside its ecological significance) and that could materialise through the development of a sustainable Blue Economy. This is perfectly aligned with the general scope of Biosphere Reserves, as they are also "learning areas for sustainable development" (UNESCO, 2024a). Moreover, a clear and strong demonstration of the reality of that remarkable opportunity, as well as of the need of a management approach inclusive of the social and ecological dimensions, could provide two decisive justifications for the establishment of the North-East Tobago MPA years after it was first proposed.

Since an understanding and awareness of the importance of the Blue Economy could lead to a transition to sustainable development and push for the establishment of the North-East Tobago MPA, this thesis attempts to provide a detailed view on the existing and potential Blue Economy in north-east Tobago. To do this it was necessary to look at its current status and value in the Biosphere Reserve and at the potential it could have; and since nothing or very little is documented in such regards, this innovative work aimed to close these knowledge gaps. Although the Blue Economy is now a prominent concept at the global scale, assessments of its value in a given area are remarkably scarce. And this is even more the case if the focus is on SIDS, for which a sustainable Blue Economy is so important. The body of literature on the Blue Economy has expanded considerably, mainly relating to definition, objectives, and its contribution to sustainable development (Martinez-Vazquez et al., 2021), but as yet there have been few efforts directed at investigating its progression in SIDS. They are rarely considered in their own terms and their perspectives are often overlooked in the academic literature, which is essentially a paradox since the concept of the Blue Economy was promoted by SIDS themselves. Knowledge of the Blue Economy related to them therefore remains inadequate, leaving scope and calling for more SIDS-specific research (Pouponneau, 2023).

1.4| Objectives of the thesis

The first overarching objective of this dissertation is to describe the existing Blue Economy sectors in the NETMABR and to assess their value; the second is to evaluate the potential of the Blue Economy in the same area. More specifically, the fieldwork aimed to estimate and find out together with local communities what potential sustainable Blue Economy activities could have for them. Consequently, the study revolved around the following research questions:

RQ1: What is the state of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR?

RQ2: What is the current value of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR?

RQ3: What is the potential of a sustainable Blue Economy in the NETMABR?

To address these questions, a methodology based on participant observations, literature research, semi-structured and key-informant interviews was developed (described in more detail in the next chapter). In relation to the first objective, by looking at how the marine and coastal environment is utilised and talking to people directly involved in its use, it has been possible to depict in an informed way the status quo of the Blue Economy and make an estimate of its worth. As for the second objective, by combining a literature research focused on best practice examples with on-site interviews, which allowed to investigate the point of views, perceptions, expectations and hopes of local communities, it has been possible to evaluate opportunities that respect and are in agreement with local efforts, while at the same time being promising and appropriate for the Biosphere Reserve context in north-east Tobago. In this way, the study aimed to identify solutions that could be implemented to develop and improve the Blue Economy with a view to sustainability and inclusivity. Attention was also paid to the regenerative dimension of such solutions. Indeed, in the context of this rapidly changing world in which the oceans face constant challenges and threats, sustainability may no longer be sufficient. What is needed is regeneration. A regenerative Blue Economy does not simply maintain the status quo, but goes beyond the typical goal of bringing about economic growth by using marine resources sustainably and preserving associated ecosystems, aiming to actively revitalise them (le Gouvello and Simard, 2024). By respecting those principles, all the considered and explored opportunities point towards an inclusive and sustainable economic growth, thus intended to benefit and improve livelihoods while fully respecting the environment. In addition to what has been mentioned earlier, this would also contribute to the protection of coastal and marine environments, as well as to the conservation of Tobago's marine biodiversity and the essential ecosystem services depending on it. While unique in some characteristics, Tobago shares a multitude of features and challenges with other Caribbean SIDS, mainly in the environmental, socio-economic and governmental spheres (e.g., exposure to climate change risks, disempowerment, high dependence on governmental support) (ERIC, 2019). Therefore, if the identified solutions were to be implemented and prove successful, the island could become a sustainable (and ideally

regenerative) Blue Economy role model for the whole region, with ample opportunities to share its experiences and lessons learnt with the wider Caribbean.

Since at present the two main established Blue Economy sectors in north-east Tobago are fisheries and tourism, unavoidably they were the primary focus of research. However, since potential exists for other sectors as well (such as aquaculture, marine bioprospecting and biotechnology, and marine-based renewable energy), their investigation was also part of the objectives of this thesis. It is envisaged that its results will be shared with the Tobago Biosphere Management Alliance (TOBIMA), the multi-sectoral Civil Society Organisation (CSO) that will implement the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere Programme in Tobago, with other interested CSOs, the Environmental Research Institute Charlotteville (ERIC), and the Division of Food Security, Natural Resources, the Environment and Sustainable Development. The latter is one of the nine Divisions of the Tobago House of Assembly (THA), the government body responsible for the island of Tobago within the unitary state of Trinidad and Tobago. Sharing research results with them will ensure a two-way knowledge exchange process. In fact, the core part of this study was based on the willingness of residents to share knowledge, perceptions and ideas, hence the results will also go back to the island and its communities. The intent is to present a Master's thesis that not only provides an account of the current state of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR, but also contains insights to make meaningful changes in the context of north-east Tobago, i.e. changes local stakeholders are able and willing to integrate in their respective livelihoods. The ideal outcome of the dissertation would be its use to create opportunities that directly benefit people.

2| Methods

2.1| Data collection

Participant observations, semi-structured and key-informant interviews were employed. Data were collected over a 20 weeks period between October 2023 and February 2024. Of the 14 villages in the North-East Tobago Man and the Biosphere Reserve, 13 were considered in the research: Moriah was excluded because it is located relatively too far inland and therefore was deemed not relevant for a Blue Economy analysis. In addition, no data was collected from people who lived or worked in Hermitage and L'Anse Fourmi, since the former is a very small settlement (~30 residents) where hardly any coastal activities take place, and the latter is mainly dedicated to agriculture (ERIC, 2019 and own observations).

A total of 106 people from different groups of stakeholders were interviewed: fisherfolk ($n = 46$), boat builders ($n = 4$), tourism operators ($n = 45$) including tour and dive operators ($n = 16$), lifeguards ($n = 12$) and accommodation providers ($n = 17$); and representatives from relevant CSOs and government divisions, agencies and institutes ($n = 11$, specifically referred to as key informants). All interviews and conversations were held in English, the official language of the country as part of the English-speaking Caribbean. Initially, people were a little suspicious of the researcher as a foreign student moving around villages and non-tourist areas, but in the course of the fieldwork they became much more familiar with his presence.

2.1.1| Sampling

The first step of the sampling strategy consisted in identifying some initial key stakeholders with the help of the on-site partner: the ERIC, a Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) working towards sustainability for the people and ecosystems of north-east Tobago. Its Executive Director acted as a gatekeeper and provided assistance in getting in touch with those potential respondents, who were selected purposively. They had already collaborated with the ERIC and therefore a relationship of trust had already been established, which was crucial to receive agreement and willingness to participate in the study.

For all other interviewees at the village level, a combination of convenience and snowball sampling was used. Convenience sampling often required going nearby the fishing facilities (or fish markets, premises where fisherfolk generally bring in the fish when they return from sea, clean and sell it) and tourist sites to identify and create opportunities to talk to people potentially relevant to the research. The villages of the NETMABR were visited repeatedly during fieldwork. While at the village level

purposive, convenience, and snowball sampling were used, at the island level people with a governmental or institutional role were only purposively selected.

Interviewees may not represent the opinions of everyone in the Biosphere Reserve due to the fact that a non-probability sampling was used. In addition, it has to be mentioned that snowball sampling risks capturing only specific point of views because of inherent path dependencies (Tracy, 2013). However, due to time limitations and little prior knowledge of the study site, it was deemed that these were still the best approaches to employ. Efforts were made to maximise the number of interviews that could be managed given the amount of time and resources available. To the author's knowledge, all boat builders and dive operators in the NETMABR were interviewed. With the exception of three people, the same applies to tour guides, while interviews with fisherfolk were conducted until saturation was reached (i.e., until no new themes or information emerged) (Glaser and Strauss, 1967).

2.1.2| Participant observations and non-verbal data

The participant observation phase represented the first step of fieldwork, covering the first month of research. This approach allows to learn about what people do, know, and use by attentively observing and interacting with them in natural settings (Spradley, 1980). As participant observation involves collecting information in a certain social context by taking on a role within it (Cropley, 2022), this phase required travelling regularly to the 13 villages under analysis, where mainly fish markets and 'limes' (a word commonly used in Tobago meaning informal gatherings) were actively attended. To avoid ethical concerns, the role of the researcher was made known whenever new people were met, so that everyone would always know from the start who I was, why I was in Tobago, and what the goals of my work were. The data collected through participant observations was documented in written fieldnotes (a research diary).

Simply by being present in the field, the researcher had also access to a vast amount of non-verbal data related to both fisheries (e.g., number and use of boats, fish price, whether fisherfolk maintain the cooling chain and what are their daily activities) and tourism (e.g., frequency of diving activities, how many boats with tourists on board leave the beach). Moreover, villages where there is more activity (and where therefore there was much to investigate) and those where virtually no Blue Economy-related business takes place were identified.

In addition to what has just been mentioned, there are other reasons why the observation phase was essential. It allowed to establish contacts that were very useful later in the study and gave the possibility to dive into the local settings and circumstances, consequently enabling a better understanding of the social and societal context of north-east Tobago. By providing precious time to familiarise with the study's context, this phase presented the opportunity to start developing appropriate interview guidelines using the acquired insights. At the same time, it avoided having to rush interviews without a deep awareness of the social component. Instead, it opened up the

possibility for a short intermediate step during which interview guidelines were completed and piloted (see next section). Finally, the observation phase was critical to achieving the objectives of the thesis. On one hand it helped to understand and make an informed description of the state of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR, and on the other it enabled to start probing the potential it might have in the area.

2.1.3| Interviews

The main instruments of primary data collection were semi-structured and key-informant interviews, which were conducted for 15 weeks. Since in the Biosphere Reserve there are only three established Blue Economy sectors (i.e., fisheries, shipbuilding, and tourism), respondents were limited to fisherfolk, boat builders, tourism operators, and representatives from CSOs and government divisions, agencies, and institutes relevant to those domains. Opportunities to talk to people who make other uses of the marine environment or are involved in different economic activities were sought in the course of the research, but did not materialise precisely because of the absence of such people.

Semi-structured interviews were preferred to structured interviews because they offer the prospect of flexibility, and to unstructured interviews because the investigation had a fairly clear focus, so through the former it was possible to address more specific issues (Bryman, 2012). Combining the two strengths, following a script to a certain extent and having some structure helped to ensure that all the main topics were consistently covered across the sample, while flexibility allowed for an exploratory analysis on a case-by-case basis. To make all this possible, interview guidelines were developed (see Appendix, section 6.1). Even if the general topics had already been determined so that the research questions of the study could be answered, the guidelines were finalised only during fieldwork, more precisely at the end of the observation phase. At this stage, a short step was planned to complete the guidelines with the experience and increased familiarity gained with the local context up to that point. Thus, it was possible to ultimately produce guidelines for achieving project goals that were appropriate and meaningful to the local settings and circumstances, which would have been impossible if they had been developed prior to fieldwork. Finalising the interview guidelines also implied to conduct a field-test of the questions and topics to be covered (Bryman, 2012). For this reason, five pilot interviews (three with fisherfolk and two with tourism operators) were carried out. These exploratory interviews were very useful to reveal shortcomings in the content and structure of the guidelines, which were then modified accordingly. The main corrections following the field-tests were made regarding the use of a more contextually pertinent wording, removal of certain questions, and change of questions that produced identical or very similar answers. Moreover, pilot interviews were used to check the potential sensitivity of certain topics and the interview flow, and also to gain some general experience in interviewing people (Bryman, 2012).

Both semi-structured and key-informant interviews were conducted individually by the author alone and lasted between 30 and 75 minutes. They were not recorded, as it was strongly recommended not to do so due to possible inappropriateness to the local context. Many people would have felt uncomfortable, which would have added to the already suspicious attitude towards (foreign) researchers. To remedy the non-recording, meticulous note-taking was carried out during the interviews, which often took place outdoor. One interview had to be conducted by telephone due to schedule constraints and three online due to location issues (two key-informants and an accommodation provider were not based in Tobago).

Following the study's objectives outlined above, the aim of the interviews was twofold: obtain information to describe and assess the value of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR, and determine the potential that a sustainable Blue Economy might have for local communities in the same area. Therefore, stakeholder interview guidelines generally included closed and open-ended questions that firstly enquired about the general aspects of a certain profession and then focussed on possible livelihood constraints, challenges and opportunities. At the end of the interview, people were asked the questions that were likely to be most sensitive, as they related to their earnings (e.g., catch, number of tourists taken on a tour, occupancy rate). The situation was slightly different with regard to key informants, since some of those questions were not relevant to them. Key-informant interviews were strongly geared to benefit from stakeholders' specific knowledge and expertise, but at the same time were conceived to address as many common themes as possible (i.e., similar interview guides were adopted).

With regard to rules and rules of thumb on how to design and formulate interview guidelines and questions, the recommendations of Bryman (2012) and Tracy (2013) were followed as closely as possible. Bryman (2012) was also the main reference author for strategies on how to approach and deal with prospective respondents, but the advices of Cropley (2022) proved useful as well. Lastly, the guidance of Tracy (2013) and Kvale (1996) on how best to conduct interviews was heeded, the latter mainly regarding the criteria to be adopted in order to be a successful interviewer.

2.2| Data analysis

At first, interview data was rewritten and gathered into a Microsoft Word document, where it has been preliminarily explored to get a sense of the information and to highlight some of the key ideas. Subsequently, data was analysed through open and axial coding (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). Also Charmaz (2006) was followed in the sense that in the beginning coding was very detailed, as many codes were generated to encapsulate all the information (i.e., initial coding). They evolved through an iterative process over the course of the analysis, which was conducted using Microsoft Excel (see Appendix, section 6.2, for the codes used). The choice of the two programs was driven by the fact

that according to some authors (e.g., Stanley and Temple, 1995), the majority of coding and retrieval functions that are likely to be needed when analysing qualitative data are achievable with Microsoft Word and Excel. Following Bryman (2012), repetition was considered an important criterion for establishing that a certain pattern within the data could be considered a theme. In addition, the frequency of recurrence of these has determined the prominence given to some themes over others. Some of the information that is reported later in the thesis, typically when describing the status quo of certain matters or the background against which the findings are set, was provided by key informants. Additional data in the form of fieldwork notes, mainly coming from participant observations and informal conversations, allowed to complement and triangulate information obtained through interviews. Also non-verbal data were combined with interviews and provided opportunities for further contextualisation (Flick, 2018).

2.3| Rationale for the sectors considered in the Blue Economy assessment

Identifying the Blue Economy can be a challenge, as it is divided into a number of sectors and there are some discrepancies regarding the economic activities that are considered part of it in the scientific literature. Therefore, Ebarvia (2016) suggested that defining the industries to include is the first step to a Blue Economy assessment. As it has already been highlighted, in this context the situation in the NETMABR is rather simple to understand: fisheries, tourism and, to a far lesser extent, shipbuilding and repair are the only existing Blue Economy activities (the oil and gas sector falls outside its boundaries), and no industry can reasonably be considered emerging. Consequently, only those sectors were considered when estimating the current value of the Blue Economy. In order to fully justify what has been done, some clarifications still need to be made.

Boat repairing was not taken into account. This business usually takes place in almost every village, where many people are able to do some minor repairing, often directly on the beach. Mainly due to its widespread and informal nature (e.g., people only work or accept jobs when they have time), it would not have been possible to evaluate the scale of that subsector within the scope of this research.

The catering sector was not included in the assessment either. On one hand it is indeed an essential component of tourism-related revenues and thus ideally it should have been considered, but on the other hand assessing this sector from a Blue Economy perspective is very challenging. First of all, it has to be said that in north-east Tobago there are three catering options, namely street food stands, eateries, and restaurants, and none of these has exclusively fish or shellfish on the menu. Quite the contrary, actually. Most street food stands do not sell seafood at all, while others may have it available occasionally (e.g., fish soup and saltfish accra, which are saltfish fritters very popular in

Trinidad and Tobago, on Sundays). Eateries generally have very few fish or shellfish dishes on the menu, as they mainly serve meat and 'provision' (a term referring to roots and tubers), while in restaurants it is more variable. At this point it can be said that street food stalls do not depend on marine resources at all, or do so to a very limited extent, and that eateries and restaurants do not depend much on them either. Therefore, it stands to reason that the money derived from seafood is a limited portion of the total. Moreover, it has to be understood that in the context of the catering sector local people are to be considered part of the Blue Economy only if they consume food from the sea, while all the tourists that go out for a meal fall within it because their presence in Tobago is linked to a 'Blue' type of tourism (see also next paragraph). This means that it would have been necessary to differentiate between the money earned from tourists and from local customers who consumed sea-related products (i.e., Blue Economy), and the remainder. Considering the difficulty in overcoming this challenge with the time and resources available for the study, it was decided to exclude the catering sector from the investigation.

Furthermore, the accommodation sector was considered for the assessment even if initially there were similar concerns to those just mentioned. In fact, it is in principle very difficult to distinguish between Blue Economy clients and people visiting Tobago mainly because of its terrestrial features (most notably the Tobago Main Ridge Forest Reserve, which is the oldest legally protected tropical forest reserve in the world) or cultural events. However, interviews with accommodation providers revealed that nearly all tourists undertake marine activities as part of their stay or as their only focus. So, albeit a bit of a simplification, every guest was considered a Blue Economy guest, and under this assumption the hospitality sector has been included in the analysis. After all, it is a core part of tourism, and if it had been left out one of the main sources of revenue in that regard would have been ignored.

2.4| Ethical considerations

The study dealt with a potentially sensitive topic, i.e., income. This was vital to assess the value of the Blue Economy, but at the same time it implied having to be careful and aware of the intercultural context. This was one of the reasons why pilot interviews were conducted and why guidelines were only finalised during fieldwork: having learned more about the local situation it was possible to develop appropriate and sensitive questions. Moreover, advice was sought from ERIC and interview guidelines were reviewed by the gatekeeper, who advised on their appropriateness.

Research was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards detailed in the Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice by the German Research Foundation (DFG, 2022) and following the recommendations of Bryman (2012). In particular, there were no potential risks or costs to participants involved in the research, neither physical nor psychological. There was no prospect

of any harm to respondents in terms of disclosure dangers either. In fact, confidentiality has been guaranteed: actual names are not used, and any other information that can lead to the identification of participants is not included in the dissertation. In addition to the prevention of identification and the related control of information gained from them or about them, another procedure that was established for the care and protection of respondents was related to the location of the interview. The setting was adapted to local conditions and participants' requests, and if necessary a quiet, appropriate place that ensured privacy was selected. If despite all these precautions participants were still concerned about what they said being disclosed, they were invited to speak freely about it or to contact the scientist. The same applied to any questions about the project. Furthermore, interviewees' availability was always asked and followed.

All information in the last paragraph, along with a brief description of the study, was contained in an Informed Consent Form. It was also designed to inform about the entities the results would be shared with, give adequate time to contemplate whether to take part in the research and explain that this choice was entirely voluntary and the possibility to withdraw from it at any time. However, due to the high illiteracy rate in north-east Tobago, the Informed Consent Form could not be administered to participants in paper version. Instead, its content was summarised in a speech that was used to seek prior informed consent orally from all respondents.

In addition, this project has been considered by an Institutional Ethics Committee at the Leibniz Centre for Marine Tropical Research (ZMT) before it started and has been given a favourable review.

2.5| Limitations

A number of methodological limitations exist that affected the execution of this thesis and should be borne in mind when looking at the study design and interpreting the results.

The first major limitation was the ubiquitous data deficiency for north-east Tobago regarding all components of the Blue Economy (ERIC, 2022b). Statistics and figures are generally not available to date, and if they are they cover the entire island or the entire nation of Trinidad and Tobago. For instance, there is no disaggregated data on the number of registered fisherfolk living in the villages belonging to the NETMABR, no data on the number of accommodation properties in the territory, just as there is no count of tourists accessing the Biosphere Reserve. Data is also a problem considering the island of Tobago as a whole. There is no information on the diving sector, and seaport data is not systematically collected: when people travel from Trinidad to Tobago by ferry their destination is not recorded. Even the occupancy rate presented later on in the thesis is not official but based on a preliminary analysis, and was communicated to the author only through personal acquaintances. Catch data was available, as the Department of Marine Resources and Fisheries (DMRF) of the THA and the University of Trinidad and Tobago (UTT) are carrying out data

collection. However, despite the author's repeated efforts to gain access to these collections, there was ultimately no collaboration in sharing them. The same applies to information on the average spending of visitors and the number of visitor arrivals in Tobago (broken down into domestic and international), which were potentially available from the Tobago Tourism Agency Limited (TTAL), the destination management organisation of Tobago.

The fact that north-east Tobago is a data-deficient environment influences how research can be conducted and the results that can be achieved. To begin with, the present work had to start practically from scratch without being able to rely on earlier work of others, which is why the methodology of this study was developed as described earlier in the chapter. Then, it was impossible to conduct some analyses that would have been relevant for the purposes of the dissertation, like investigating how many jobs and businesses there are in the different Blue Economy sectors and comparing these numbers with the total available or present in the region. This would have allowed, for example, to determine whether the share of Blue Economy-related jobs is high or low and, in the latter case, the figure could have supported the fact that there is a lot of room for growth. More generally, these kind of analyses would have permitted a fuller description of the Blue Economy.

Another noteworthy limitation is linked to the very nature of the Blue Economy. This topic is so vast that the time available for the dissertation has made it imperative to restrict the discussion of the potential, both in terms of number of opportunities and level of detail (in some cases the discussion is based on a non-exhaustive list of references). Furthermore, although the extent of marine and coastal activities in north-east Tobago is not so great, quantifying its value is still very complicated. This is due to some factors that have to be taken into consideration. First of all, economic activities have indirect as well as direct effects, and the former are very difficult to assess. To give a simple example, hotels buy supplies for meals and housekeeping (Katila, 2019), and if this happens to accommodate Blue Economy guests (as assumed above) then those purchases are part of the Blue Economy too. Secondly, besides a thorough understanding of the social and economic constructs of a certain area, measuring the Blue Economy also requires knowledge about the ecological resources that could contribute to it (UNECA, 2021). Indeed, the Blue Economy includes not only industries but also a number of ecosystem services (e.g., World Bank, 2016; World Bank and UNDESA, 2017), which could not be evaluated in the scope of this study. Some of them are not accounted for even in many estimates found in the literature because they are not traded on the market (e.g., coastal protection, waste disposal, existence of biodiversity, spiritual values associated with the ocean) (Patil, 2016). Going further, important caveats are related to the difficulty of considering the interactions between ecosystem services when valuing them (Kwiatkowski and Zaucha, 2023). An assessment of the Blue Economy without an account of the (indirect) impacts of economic activities and of ecosystem services, inclusive of the relationships between them and of non-commercial benefits, will never be fully accurate.

In conclusion, it must be mentioned that many choices regarding how to calculate the value of the Blue Economy had to be made, which will be explained and motivated together with the presentation of the various economic sectors for greater clarity and completeness. The author has made these decisions in order to address the objectives of the thesis as best as possible with the resources and time available for it. However, due to all the reasons presented in this section, a complete quantification of the Blue Economy in north-east Tobago was not (yet) feasible, and the values given in this study are to be understood as approximations. One of the main efforts of the research was to make reasonable and valid assumptions, such as the one explained earlier in relation to the accommodation sector. Although by their own intrinsic nature they cannot be exact, considering the data-deficient scenario and the complexity inherent in the Blue Economy, making assumptions was of crucial importance because otherwise it would not have been possible to achieve results and give recommendations to inform decisions towards the development of sustainable and regenerative Blue Economy activities.

3| Results and Discussion

3.1| Fisheries sector

3.1.1| Overview

Fishing is traditionally very important in north-east Tobago, not only as a livelihood but also as a way of life. Many fishermen (this form is used because all fishers interviewed were male) reported to have started fishing at a very early age with family members and that generally this activity is reduced or abandoned only when they get old. They conveyed a strong passion for fishing, accompanied by anecdotal accounts of fishing gear carried in backpacks instead of books and of how school was sometimes skipped to go to sea. As denoted by the fact that all respondents were male, in Tobago almost exclusively men occupy fishing roles. To the best of the author's knowledge, at the moment no women fish regularly in the study area; yet, a few own boats and hire fishermen to work on these. Fishing starting from north-east Tobago is exclusively small-scale. For the vast majority it is artisanal, consisting of operations that catch fish intended for human consumption and whose primary purpose is to sell that catch, which is done locally or, in some few cases, within the national territory. In north-east Tobago not enough fish is caught for export, as fisherfolk do not have the capacity to satisfy their personal need (a small portion of the catch is always kept for household consumption), local demand (on Tobago) and also to export. Subsistence fishing is very rare, while recreational fishing is more associated with tourism. No explicit fishing restrictions exist to date in Tobago (Draft Fisheries Management Bill; THA, 2023a), with the exception of the ban on hunting sea turtles. Some people mentioned gear restrictions, in particular the prohibition of using 'white nets' and excessively small mesh size nets and pots. However, the researcher could not find confirmation of this information in the most recent Draft Fisheries Management Bill (THA, 2023a). In any case, if actually existing, to date such restrictions are not enforced.

The number of fisherfolk was difficult to assess because in each village there are people who go fishing regularly and others who only go to sea if the catch is abundant at a certain time. That information could have been derived from the landings data of the DMRF and UTT, but not having had access to it an independent estimate was produced. At the time of the study there were approximately between 87 and 107 active fishers in north-east Tobago, distributed as follows: between 20 and 30 in Charlotteville, ~6 in Speyside, ~10 in Delaford, ~10 in Roxborough, ~11 in Belle Garden, between 10 and 15 in Castara, and between 20 and 25 in Parlatuvier. People living in Bloody Bay fish from Parlatuvier, people living in Louis d'Or fish either from Delaford or Roxborough,

and people living in Betsy's Hope and Argyle fish from Roxborough. In fact, all the villages mentioned in the count have a jetty, a fishing facility, or both, while the others do not.

All fisherfolk use pirogues, typically in the 22 ft. – 28 ft. range. Boat ownership was widespread (85% of participants), with only 7 people constantly going fishing with someone else or borrowing a boat from friends or relatives. Fewer than 40% of boat owners (15 out of 39) were willing to lend it, even though they would get a portion of the other person's catch. All respondents owned fishing gear, generally of various types because fishers can change fishing methods depending on the season, as some target species are migratory. Information on fishing techniques is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Usage (including season), description (adapted from Flower, 2011) and target species of the most common fishing techniques in north-east Tobago

Technique	Num. of interviewees	Description	Main target species	Season of usage
Trolling	40 (87%)	Generally four to six lines towed from bamboo outriggers. Some lines are weighted to sink, while others run on the surface. Artificial bait or pieces of little tunny (<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>) are placed on each hook, one per line	Blackfin and yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus atlanticus</i> and <i>Thunnus albacares</i>), little tunny (<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>), common dolphinfish (or mahi-mahi, <i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>), wahoo (<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>), king mackerel (or kingfish, <i>Scomberomorus cavalla</i>)	Approximately from November to May. Tobagonian fisherfolks consider this to be the main fishing season
Banking	37 (80%)	Bottom line fishing done on ocean banks offshore, typically underwater hills. A weighted line with 10-50 baited hooks is held by hand and lifted when fish bite. Several lines can also be attached to buoys and checked periodically (this technique is sometimes called "vertical")	Snappers (locally called "red fish", <i>Lutjanus</i> spp.) and groupers (<i>Epinephelus</i> spp.)	Mainly from June to September, but since target species are always present it can be used throughout the year. This is often done by older fisherfolks, who suffer the boat bouncing while trolling (back pain)
Live bait (a-la-vie)	29 (63%)	Line fishing in which live bait (Clupeidae) is placed on the hooks. Live bait is also periodically thrown into the water to attract target species. Bait fish is caught through beach seine fishing or cast nets	All of the above and additional species (e.g. <i>Seriola</i> sp.). People reported that live bait is used to catch every type of fish	All year round
Pots	11 (24%)	This is a passive fishing method: pots are set on the bottom and attract target species inside them, which are then prevented from escaping. Pots are hauled by hand, generally on a daily basis or every other day	Snappers (locally called "red fish", <i>Lutjanus</i> spp.) and lobsters	All year round

The total number of people does not equal the number of fishermen interviewed ($n = 46$), and correspondingly the percentages do not add up to 100%, because the vast majority of participants (38 out of 46) regularly employed two or more fishing methods. Table 2 shows the most popular

ones, but there are more. Jigging, seine fishing, drifting for flying fish and gill- and drift netting were all done by a minimum of two to a maximum of five interviewed fishers, albeit some only occasionally. A few people fished also at night using light to attract small fish which, in turn, together with the bait thrown into the water, attract larger fish.

Two thirds of the study participants (31 out of 46) reported fishing frequently around Fish Aggregating Devices (FADs), which they own, set and anchor to the seabed (anchored FADs) themselves, and are able to find again by recording the coordinates on a GPS. In this regard, the use of some sort of technological device while fishing was common: 70% of fishermen owned a GPS (everyone who owned at least one electronic instrument had a GPS), essential to locate the fishing ground and for the return trip when land is not in sight, 26% a fish finder, and 22% a radio for communication. Here too, values do not sum up to 100% because more than half of the people who used technological devices for fishing actually employed two or three of them. Most of the respondents who did not use FADs said they fish at a maximum distance of 5 miles off the coast, a distance within which there are popular fishing grounds, namely Little Tobago and St. Giles Islet Complex. Of the 16 people fishing in the 1 – 5 miles range (or closer), 15 started their operations from Charlotteville or Speyside. This is not surprising, as they are extremely near to the above-mentioned fishing grounds (St. Giles Islet Complex and Little Tobago, respectively; see Fig. 3), which are therefore usually frequented by the fisherfolk of those villages. The 1 – 5 miles' range is the most common range of distances from the shore that interviewees went to (35% of them), followed by 5 – 10, 10 – 20 and 20 – 30 (all three 15%), 30 – 40 (11%), and 40 – 60 miles (9%).

3.1.2| Fishing in a context of perceived declining catches

When queried as to whether fish catches changed since they had started fishing, all fishermen agreed that they were lower than in the past (the perception of time varied among fishermen, so it was not possible to define a precise timeline). Most people (34 out of 46) used the same few words to describe the situation, saying that the catches “declined” or “decreased” and frequently also adding “a lot”, “drastically”, or “dramatically”. Some estimated that their current catch is a third (or even less) of what they used to get, while others mentioned the need to go further than before to catch fish. Several respondents ($n = 15$) had also noticed a size decline. This fact, along with the decline in catches, was echoed by a key informant with extensive experience in the fishing industry. An old fisherman stressed the seriousness of the problem:

“Things get harder and harder every day. [...] I have no hopes. Every year the situation is getting worse and worse.” [Interviewee 13]

Unlike what used to happen in the past according to the accounts of some key informants, during fieldwork no stories were heard about extraordinarily large catches that fishermen had made some

time before, but rather complaints about too frequently returning from sea empty-handed or “having to put hands in the pockets to pay back gas”. In this regard, when asked what they considered to be a bad catch, the two most common answers were “nothing” (i.e., no fish) and a certain amount of pounds (including 0) followed by the specification that a bad catch occurs when the earnings from it are not sufficient to repay the fuel that has been consumed. This implies that the day not only does not end in profit, but indeed in loss. Sixty-three percent (63%) of respondents reported that such bad catches occur “very [or “quite”] frequently” or “very [or “fairly”] often”. Noteworthy is that none of them said bad catches are uncommon, let alone that they never happen. Quite the opposite, when asked how often they happened to get a good catch (in general, the higher the usual catch of a fisherman the higher what he deemed to be a good catch), only eight interviewees answered “sometimes” (which was quantified by two of them as 1/5 or 1/4 of the times). All the others used expressions such as “quite [or “very”] rarely” and “hardly ever happens”. The answers of two fishermen to that question are quite illustrative:

“It hasn’t happened for some years. I can’t remember the last time I had a good catch.”
[Interviewee 20]

“Almost once in a blue moon.” [Interviewee 11]

These results, coupled with the fact that the proud accounts of large catches that key informants reported to be the norm in the past have been replaced by those about the unfruitfulness of fishing, paint a rather negative picture. In addition, although it was not possible to compare the perceptions of changing catches to up-to-date trends in landings data, perception surveys can act as a good indicator of fish stock status (Leenhardt et al., 2016). In this light, the fact that 46 fishermen unanimously concurred to have seen a decline in catches over time takes on great significance and suggests a depletion of some (if not all) fish stocks in north-east Tobago. Yet, the majority of participants (39 out of 46) believed that fish is still very abundant in the ocean and that the decrease they are experiencing is therefore a purely local issue.

Ninety-one percent (91%) of interviewees (42 out of 46) cited the operations of the oil and gas companies as a cause of the catch drop, referring to both marine drilling and seismic explorations. These activities were held responsible for scaring off the fish and creating a hostile environment, which resulted in driving the fish stocks further away from the island. Some people even thought that the surveys kill the fish. In addition, oil rigs were accused of acting as FADs and attracting fish far from the coast, an effect to which the lights of these infrastructures would also contribute. One fisherman believed that the oil and gas extracting industry is the sole cause of the problems the sector is facing:

“They [the oil and gas companies] destroyed the fisheries of Trinidad and Tobago.”
[Interviewee 23]

The second main theme that emerged from interviews in that regard is the overfishing by foreign fishing vessels, mainly from Venezuela and Barbados, which 35% of study participants (16 out of 46) considered a major cause of the catch decline. More than a third of respondents denounced this intrusion into the territorial waters of Trinidad and Tobago, often referring to them as “our waters” and pointing out that foreigners go there “without any rights”. Their boats have a much larger capacity than local pirogues, which allows them to fish a lot and for long periods of time, since there is virtually no control. Two interviewees who go far offshore (40-60 miles) also reported that Barbadians and Venezuelans cut the FADs that might get caught on their gear. One participant remarked how easy it is for intruders to act undisturbed, especially at night:

“At night when no one from Tobago is out fishing they [the foreign fishing boats] have all the time to do whatever they want.” [Interviewee 25]

Data from interviews reveals that the inappropriate location of FADs was considered to be the third main reason why less fish is caught compared to the past. According to 30% of interviewees, fishers are setting FADs excessively far from the coast, causing them to attract and keep fish too remote from the island. Not coincidentally, 10 of the 14 fishermen who identified FADs as responsible for the catch decline fish in the 1-5 miles range, and 13 of them within 10 miles. They complained about the serious problem posed by not reaching great distances at sea, which they are prevented from doing mainly because of age or because their boat’s engine is not powerful enough.

Some people ($n = 8$) recognised that climate change might play a role in the decrease of the catches and lead to variability in the seasons shown in Table 2, and a few ($n = 3$) stated that there must be a link between this decrease and the fact that there are more boats operating than in the past. They were convinced that the rise of local boats led to a partition of fish among more fishers, but did not believe that it had led to an absolute decline in the populations. In other words, even after the increase in the number of boats the amount of fish remained the same and simply started to be shared among more people (i.e., no reference to overfishing).

So far, with the exception of FADs, whose inclusion in the perceived causes for the decline in fish catches in north-east Tobago is new to this research, these results largely reflect the themes identified by Flower (2011). However, their recurrence strongly differs in two cases: oil and gas companies were held responsible for the catch decline by only a third of Flower’s respondents (compared to 91% in this study), while almost 50% of them mentioned the local increase in boats as a cause, without linking it to overfishing (compared to just 3 people in this study, i.e., less than 7%). Perhaps, this can be explained by the fact that the two studies have been conducted more than 12 years apart, and that Flower’s sample was less than half the size of the one used here, besides being limited to only two villages. Another new theme has emerged with this dissertation, and it assumes considerable importance having been mentioned by many people ($n = 17$). This theme encompasses all the problems related to bad fishing practices, from overfishing and size reduction

to the use of fish pots, beach seines, and cast nets. Starting with overfishing, some participants (7 out of 46) admitted that it can have a part to play as the number of boats increased a lot over time and fishermen have never set a limit on the amount of fish to catch, thus preventing populations from recovering (which is different from the above-mentioned argumentation of perceived smaller catches due to splitting of fish among more fishermen). Two of them made clear references to sustainability, although without making this word explicit:

“They [most of the other fishermen] don’t think about tomorrow.” [Interviewee 29]

“Fishermen think just about catching as much fish as they can and don’t have a future perspective.” [Interviewee 16]

In a similar number of interviews ($n = 9$), local fishermen were deemed responsible for the size reduction of fish, as they catch excessively small individuals (both with active and passive techniques) and do not allow them enough time to grow. Several of the people who talked about overfishing and size reduction as a result of local operations (in a few cases the same person talked about both aspects) stated to have understood this only on the basis of observation and experience. Fish pots, in addition to being accused of having an overly small mesh size and thus contributing to the size reduction, have also been related to ghost fishing. In fact, if the rope attaching a pot to the surface buoy is cut, for instance by the passage of a boat, the derelict fishing gear will remain on the bottom for a long time and continue to fish. Finally, beach seines and cast nets have been blamed for depleting reef fish. One respondent explained the harmfulness of the former by relating it in particular to the deployment time:

“If every single time that fish come in the bay to breed they are killed in massive amounts they can’t reproduce.” [Interviewee 23]

3.1.3| Conflicts between fisherfolk and oil and gas companies

Results from interviews suggest that nearly all fisherfolk in north-east Tobago currently consider the oil and gas companies responsible for the catch decline, mainly because their activities chase the fish away. To provide some context, certain fishing grounds are close to areas earmarked for hydrocarbon extraction, relying on the region’s offshore natural resources.

Figure 4. Map of oil and gas fields across Trinidad and Tobago (prepared by the Geological Society of Trinidad and Tobago). Retrieved from: <https://newsday.co.tt/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/14562147.jpg>

In addition to offshore gas drilling, seismic explorations for oil and gas are still being conducted at different areas around the island. When this happens, some fishing grounds are closed off for a certain period of time. According to some stakeholders and key informants, it occurred that companies even anticipated that for some time after the survey fisherfolk would not have been able to catch much fish in the affected areas. For this reason, although not required by law, Tobagonian fisherfolk were compensated monetarily at least once. This was also despite Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) having been made and submitted for evaluation to the Department of the Environment, which determined that they did not reveal anything that was going to create significant permanent negative environmental externalities (though the existence of a huge conflict of interests must be borne in mind). It is possible that compensations were paid on other occasions as well, but only in specific areas that were judged to be more at risk of being directly affected; yet this aspect had to remain a speculation. Other times, instead of payments, oil and gas companies gave GPS devices to fishers and organised training courses for their use, or contributed to local social or environmental projects. At the time of this study, a new Shell exploration was in the planning stages. During its course, the fishing ground nearby the selected area will be closed for around 140 days, denying fisherfolk access to it. To address the problem, the company is examining two types of solutions reflecting what has already been done in the past: assist local communities in social projects or provide monetary compensations. According to a key informant, affairs are likely to be managed differently should the latter be the case. First of all, Shell will be assisted by the Department of Marine Resources and Fisheries to distribute the money equitably, in order to avoid some issues (mentioned informally by some interviewees) that occurred previously when it was given through the All Tobago Fisherfolk Association (ATFA). Secondly, the amount will be calculated based on the

number of closure days and on the average catch of individual fishermen, which should be available as a result of DMRF and UTT's data collection. At the same time, this will allow only those fishermen who are actually active on a regular basis to be eligible for compensations. Finally, since the concerned fishing ground is located very far from the coast of Tobago, only the (few) people who reach such distance and can prove it (e.g., GPS and gas station receipts) will be compensated.

The topic of the oil and gas industry is very delicate. More than 40% of interviewees explicitly said that compensations are needed and that companies must pay them. Some respondents were even against any other form of assistance, as only the people involved in fishing have their livelihood put at risk. According to them, since the other villagers are not affected, money should not be invested in community projects. Many questions arise at this point, for example: are fisherfolk really affected by the operations of the oil and gas companies? And if so, in what ways?

Fishermen's assertions that the platforms and their lights attract fish to move far offshore find confirmation in the scientific literature. Artificial night light can attract and concentrate prey species characterised by positive phototaxis and therefore enhance foraging possibilities (e.g., for visually hunting predators) (Keenan et al., 2007). In addition, the fish aggregating effects of oil rigs are well recognised and have been documented in various parts of the world, mainly the Gulf of Mexico, California, and the North Sea (Fabi et al., 2004; Love and Schroeder, 2004; Love et al., 2005; Ibanez-Erquiaga et al., 2024). Many studies have focused on demersal species, more closely associated with oil and gas platforms that can function ecologically as artificial reefs (Ibanez-Erquiaga et al., 2024), while there has been limited research on highly migratory species (Snodgrass et al., 2020), which are also commercially very important in Tobago. Snodgrass et al. (2020) note that the spatial and temporal overlap of migratory species with offshore platforms and their spatial proximity are lower than for essentially structure-associated species. Nevertheless, the authors suggest that closeness to and food web connections with rigs can affect the life history, for instance inducing changes in the migratory behaviour or reproduction. Provided that effects on fish biology are difficult to determine, while such potential impacts at the population level of highly migratory species are thought to be unlikely, they could be locally or regionally significant. The scale of stock-level events might instead be greater for demersal stocks found only in a certain area (Snodgrass et al., 2020). Given the lack of knowledge on such topics in the context of Tobago, these aspects should be explored through dedicated local studies.

Concerning now the fact that fishermen were certain that the oil and gas companies were a (if not *the*) cause of decreasing catches, situations of this kind are not new to the academic literature. A very similar scenario of small-scale fishers arguing that increasing seismological studies were "killing fish and driving them away" is reported from the Mexican Gulf of Mexico by Quist (2019, p. 8). Here, unlike in Tobago, the claims of declining fish catches were supported by landings data, but similarly, there was scientific indeterminacy on the causes of populations' depletion. Although potentially harmful effects on the environment are reported (e.g., as reviewed by Andrews et al., 2021), data on

the impact of the oil and gas extracting industry on fish catches is rarer and often contradictory (excluding oil spill events, on which many studies focus to assess the repercussions on fish populations and the environment in general). While in some cases a reduced catch rate following seismic surveys has been demonstrated (Skalski et al., 1992; Engås et al., 1996), in others little evidence of consistent catch rate change induced by a seismic survey was found (Bruce et al., 2018). The literature showed no effects even on the distribution or abundance of fish (Pickett et al., 1994; Peña et al., 2013). The findings of Pickett et al. (1994), Peña (2013), and Bruce et al. (2018) suggest that clear and strong negative impacts due to the activities of oil and gas companies do not occur, but this does not preclude the possibility that they are one of the causes of diminished catches in north-east Tobago. Investigating such relationship is certainly an important direction for future research. Until recently, this would have been difficult due to the lack of a baseline and accurate landings data in general, making it difficult to understand how (and if) Tobagonian fishers are affected by marine drilling and seismic explorations. Recently, data collection by DMRF has improved and the UTT-led project has added to it. The fishermen's attitude towards data collection also bodes well: during informal conversations, 10 people revealed to be willing to collect data. One of them explained the importance of catch recording as a way to understand whether fish stocks are declining or not, showing the similarity to a vegetable garden:

“If you don't replant everything gets depleted when you start eating it.” [Interviewee 1]

Therefore, DMRF's efforts could be coordinated with fishermen's willingness to collect data in a participatory monitoring program once the UTT project is concluded. Future data, following the completion of new surveys, could be compared with that preceding the explorations and shed light on the situation. If it will not reveal statistically significant differences, the causes of (perceived) declining catches would have to be sought elsewhere, hopefully contributing to ending the dispute between fisherfolk and oil and gas companies. Beyond that, an improved catch monitoring would allow information to be obtained regarding the status of fish populations and thus inform management. In the meantime, what could be done in relation to the hydrocarbon industry is to adopt a preventive approach. For instance, conducting seismic surveys outside spawning periods is highly recommended (Carroll et al., 2017).

3.1.4| Addressing other perceived causes of catch decline: foreign fishing vessels and Fish Aggregating Devices

The causes of catch decrease are difficult to assess in highly migratory species such as some of the most important target species in north-east Tobago (i.e., tunas, common dolphinfish, wahoo and king mackerel). Among them, interviewees identified overextraction of marine resources by Venezuelan and Barbadian vessels fishing off Tobago, which are in fact recognised to enter the

waters of Trinidad and Tobago pretty often (Flower, 2011). As for the Barbadians, the primary reason for their incursions is well known: access to flying fish stocks. The flying fish is a cultural symbol and a traditional food in Barbados (it is part of the national dish), but once abundant around the island, it has migrated south towards Tobago. Given the great value Barbadian fisherfolk attach to flying fish, they feel to have the right to catch it wherever it might go and venture very far, including Tobago's waters (Blake and Campbell, 2007). Here, they are believed to fish also for other species. Although a maritime boundary between the two nations was established in 2006, the situation is still unresolved as there seems to have been no further developments since the account provided by Nyman (2012). Unregulated and illegal fishing by foreign fishing boats and the severe consequences it can have on local small-scale fishers have also been documented elsewhere, for example in Sri Lanka, North Korea, and West African countries (Daniels et al., 2016; Dodangodage, 2017; Park et al., 2020). This is a problem that local fisherfolk alone cannot cope with and that made some Tobagonians feel unarmed:

“This [the overfishing by foreigners] leaves Tobagonians stranded. And we have no saying in that.” [Interviewee 1]

They then blamed the coast guard for not acting and urged the government to control and protect their waters. Among others, this solution was advocated by a fisherman who added that harsher penalties should be put in place for foreign vessels caught fishing in the EEZ of Trinidad and Tobago. He explained that when they are surprised the catch is confiscated and the boat is forced to leave, but since these measures are not particularly serious they do not act as a deterrent against reoccurrence. Law enforcement, more severe punishments (e.g., higher fines) and patrols at sea are recommended to tackle the situation. However, there are costs associated with that and what is more, Trinidad and Tobago has never shown commitment to address the situation. In fact, in 2016 the country received a yellow card from the European Union (EU) mainly because of a “lack of monitoring and control of fishing activities, and of inadequate penalties to prevent illegal fishing operators” (EJF et al., 2023; p. 1). Following this formal warning, the efforts to combat Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing are to date still insufficient and there has been a lack of progress in addressing the shortcomings identified when the country was firstly recognised as a non-cooperating country (European Commission, 2023). For these reasons, in September 2023 the EU issued a red card to Trinidad and Tobago. The most severe consequence of a red card is that a nation's fishery products are banned from being imported into the EU (IUUwatch, 2016). The ban itself is a non-existent problem for Tobagonian artisanal fisherfolk since they sell the catch locally and are therefore not hampered by the seafood export restrictions, but the reasons behind it confirm that there are indeed problems with IUU fishing in the EEZ of the country. It is reasonable to suppose that in a context of a perceived decline in catches, foreign, more industrialised fishing fleets play a

role. These boats fish more efficiently than local pirogues and have much more storage space, which allows them to stay at sea for longer.

The impact of fishing in north-east Tobago is not limited to the local effort also for other reasons. Longliners and trawlers come regularly from Trinidad (Flower, 2011), and some key informants reported that Grenadian vessels occasionally go specifically to the area to get bait fish, and so do fishers from other parts of Tobago, who are also reported to fish in the north-eastern region. Once again, however, the availability of data is deemed indispensable for assessing the impact of external fishing and informing management to secure the livelihood of small-scale fishers. Provided that there is willingness and capacity to intervene by the government.

FADs make pelagic fish more easily available to small-scale fishers by leveraging the tendency of some species to aggregate around floating objects. Unlike in some other tropical areas, where FADs for artisanal fishing are located near the coast at a maximum distance of a few miles (e.g., Bell et al., 2015 & 2018; Eighani et al., 2019; Mills et al., 2019), in north-east Tobago fishermen (both owners and non-owners of FADs) reported that they are mainly positioned further offshore. This is probably the result of a process that has progressively encouraged FAD deployment further and further out at sea to avoid detection by other fisherfolk, which is a known phenomenon in the Caribbean (Guyader et al., 2017). Data from interviews reveals that the extreme distance at which FADs are now usually set is considered one of the main causes of decreased catches, as some pelagic species are concentrated tens of miles from the shore. This has led to the discontent of fishermen who cannot go that far but, to the author's knowledge, not to heated conflicts in the communities. Conflicts over FAD use are common in the Caribbean, yet more related to competition over fishing territories: the fisher that builds and deploys a FAD does not want others to have access to and benefit from it, and thus claims exclusivity of the area where the FAD has been placed (Alvard et al., 2015; Guyader et al., 2018; Saduski et al., 2018). This is not the case in Tobago, although it is clearly difficult, if not impossible, to control FADs and keep other fishers away from them. Interviewees proved to be aware of this, which is ultimately the reason why FADs are being placed increasingly farther out to sea, precisely to avoid undesired access. The blaming of artisanal FADs for the decrease in catches due to the fact that they are located too far from the coast (mainly by those fishers who cannot reach such distances) seems to have no precedent in the scholarly literature. For this reason, the only solutions that can be suggested are in fact those suggested by the fishermen themselves. Several people proposed to make an agreement among fishers to deploy FADs closer to shore, and some of them even to have the DMRF introduce official regulations in this regard (i.e., setting a mandatory maximum placement distance), so as to re-attract pelagic fish nearer to Tobago's shores. Nearshore FADs have shown success in increasing catch rates in a variety of locations around the globe (e.g., Albert et al., 2014; Sharp et al., 2014; Mbaru et al., 2018; Tilley et al., 2019). Two respondents considered having nearshore FADs as so important that they recommended asking those oil and gas companies willing to help local communities to place

professionally made FADs close to the coast instead of giving compensations. They felt this would be much more profitable for Tobagonian fishermen, as it would have a more lasting impact than a direct payment.

Bringing FADs closer to shore would ensure that the benefits of their use are more equally distributed. However, it is very likely that those who rely on offshore FADs for their advantage over other fishers will be reluctant to renounce. Interdisciplinary research that sheds light on and integrates the ecological (FADs aggregation capacity given their current density and spatial distribution) and social (attitudes to find agreement or compromises) dimensions of the situation is suggested to find feasible solutions.

3.1.5| Value assessment of the fisheries sector

To estimate the economic value of the fishing sector in north-east Tobago, the annual net income of fisherfolk was calculated. To do so, the number of weekly fishing days (which equals the number of fishing trips) was multiplied by the self-reported usual catch per fishing trip and the fish price. Since the result would provide the gross income, running costs (fuel and ice) were subtracted from it. Then, to make the calculation annual, both parts of the formula were multiplied by 52, which is the usual number of weeks in a year:

$$I = d \cdot 52 \cdot c \cdot p - d \cdot 52 \cdot (f + i)$$

However, at this point, an important consideration has to be made. Fishermen reported to reduce their fishing activity on average by 1/3 outside the main fishing season (30 weeks) because there is less fish around the island. In order to take into account the difference in fishing effort between the two periods of the year, this was examined as consisting of 30 + 22 weeks, and a correction coefficient was introduced for the latter season. Therefore, the original formula was broken down into two similar components. The first one is identical to the original formula, the only difference being that the multiplication factor used to make the annual calculation is no longer 52, but 30. This is the approximate number of weeks between the 1st of November and 31st of May, which is considered the main fishing season by fishers in north-east Tobago (see Table 2). In the second component, a correction factor of 2/3 was added to consider that people usually fish less off season (22 weeks of the year). Finally, it is multiplied by 22, which is the approximate number of weeks between the 1st of June and 31st of October. To summarise, the following formula was used to calculate the annual net income of individual fisherfolk:

$$I = (d \cdot 30 \cdot c \cdot p - d \cdot 30 \cdot (f + i)) + (2/3 \cdot d \cdot 22 \cdot c \cdot p - 2/3 \cdot d \cdot 22 \cdot (f + i))$$

where:

- *I* is a fisher's net income, expressed in Trinidad and Tobago dollars (TTD) per year

- d is the number of fishing days per week
- 30 is the approximate number of weeks in the main fishing season. The number of fishing days per week (d) refers specifically to this period
- c is the self-reported usual catch per fishing trip, expressed in pounds
- p is the fish price in TTD per pound
- f is the fuel expenditure for a usual fishing trip, expressed in TTD
- i is the ice expenditure for a usual fishing trip, expressed in TTD
- $2/3$ is the correction factor
- 22 is the approximate number of weeks outside the main fishing season

It is necessary to make a couple of remarks on the values that could be substituted for the parameters that make up the formula in the calculations. Starting with c , some fishermen used a range to report their usual catch, which is why a first decision to be made was whether to consider the lower value, the higher value, or an average. Regarding p , it has to be mentioned that in addition to retailing directly to consumers at 25 TTD per pound, fisherfolk can sell their catch (or part of it) to fishmongers, locally simply known as 'vendors'. They buy wholesale at a lower price (generally 22 TTD per pound) and resell the fish in other parts of the island. On the one hand, it is less convenient for fishers to sell to fishmongers, but on the other hand they do not have to deal with the fish and have the opportunity of selling it even if the catch is very abundant or if the village market has already been saturated at a certain point in time. In the first case, it would be very difficult to sell everything retail, while the second situation implies that the fish has to be moved elsewhere to be sold. So, the question is whether to consider 22, 25 TTD per pound, or the average as the fish price to be used in the calculation. To conclude the computation, after the annual net income has been calculated for all individual fishermen, the values have to be added together to obtain the total annual net income of interviewees. This sum then has to be related to the total number of fishers in the NETMABR. Information on the number of weekly fishing days, usual catch, and fuel and ice expenditures was obtained for 44 people (see Appendix, section 6.3), while between 87 and 107 active fishers were estimated to be present in north-east Tobago at the time of the research. So, the last decision to be made was whether to make the proportion between 44 people and 87, 107, or the average. To account for all the possibilities regarding the self-reported usual catch, fish price, and number of fisherfolk, three different scenarios have been devised. They are presented below.

Scenario 1: minimum and maximum range

This scenario shows a range where the first term was calculated using all minimum values (lower catch when a range was given, 22 TTD per pound as fish price, 87 total fishers) and the second using all maximum values (higher catch when a range was given, 25 TTD per pound as fish price, 107 total fishers). Under this first scenario, the value of the fisheries sector in north-east Tobago is

estimated between 4'908'725 TTD year⁻¹ and 16'604'925 TTD year⁻¹. This is equivalent to the range 723'546 USD year⁻¹ – 2'447'566 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024.

Scenario 2: average

Here, all average figures were used for the calculation: average between the two catch values when a range was given, 23.5 TTD per pound as fish price, 97 total fishers. The rationale for this choice is that it is not possible to define with certainty which of the two extreme values to take in each case. The estimate is 10'067'369 TTD year⁻¹ (1'483'930 USD year⁻¹).

At this point, to compensate for possible errors in the choices that have been made and to provide figures that can be used more confidently in future management plans, a rough order of magnitude (ROM) estimate is introduced. The ROM is used in project management, and according to the Project Management Body of Knowledge guide (PMBOK guide, 2013) has a variance of -25% to 75%. Its formula is twofold and results in an upper boundary and lower boundary range:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Upper boundary} &= \text{estimate} \cdot 1.75 \\ \text{Lower boundary} &= \text{estimate} \cdot 0.75 \end{aligned}$$

Under the second scenario, the value of the fisheries sector in north-east Tobago is estimated between 7'550'527 TTD year⁻¹ and 17'617'896 TTD year⁻¹. This is equivalent to the range 1'112'948 USD year⁻¹ – 2'596'878 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024.

Scenario 3: corrected average

This scenario is very similar to the previous one. The only difference is that the lowest catch value has been used for the computation instead of the average when a range was given by respondents. This is because the literature shows that it is possible that fisherfolk overestimate their catch (Pollock et al., 1994; Hutchings and Lambert, 2002; O'Donnell et al., 2012; de Melo Alves Damasio et al., 2015).

After the first estimate was obtained (7'002'426 TTD year⁻¹; 1'032'158 USD year⁻¹), ROM was applied again. Hence, under this third scenario, the value of the fisheries sector in north-east Tobago is estimated between 5'251'820 TTD year⁻¹ and 12'254'246 TTD year⁻¹. This is equivalent to the range 774'119 USD year⁻¹ – 1'806'277 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024.

Whichever scenario is used to make the calculations, it is noteworthy that some fishermen (always a minimum of 7 and a maximum of 12, out of 44) constantly make a loss according to the figures they reported during the interviews. They spend more on fuel and ice than they earn from the sale of fish, hence the expression "having to put hands in the pockets to pay back gas" used by some respondents. After all, while catches are most likely declining, those operational expenses (maintenance was not considered) are very high. To show this, the gross income of interviewees per

fishing trip can be compared to the amount they usually spend on fuel and ice. Using the parameters of the third scenario (23.5 TTD per pound as fish price, lower catch when a range was given), respondents' gross income averages 183 USD trip⁻¹, of which 124 USD trip⁻¹ are running costs (more than two thirds of the total gross income).

This study did not have access to an accurate record of fishers' catches, as there was no collaboration on sharing landings data by the bodies collecting it on a regular basis. Since data collected through interviews is often used to assess people's income in data-poor fisheries (e.g., Barnes-Mauthe et al., 2013; Fröcklin et al., 2014; Wamukota et al., 2014; Vieira et al., 2017; Purcell et al., 2018), this method was also applied here. Thus, the estimates are based on data obtained during semi-structured interviews in response to specific questions aimed precisely at assessing the economic value of the fisheries sector in north-east Tobago (see Appendix, section 6.1.1). However, a calculation made in this way carries a number of inaccuracies. To start with, the number of weekly fishing days strongly depends on sea conditions and on the quantity of fish being caught in a certain moment: in rough seas most people do not go fishing, and if the catches are low they reduce the frequency. It is therefore very likely that a person's annual fishing days are fewer than those extrapolated from weekly averages, even if a correction factor was introduced. Then, there is uncertainty in the annual value estimate, which is extrapolated from average fishing trip estimates. This reporting time period was chosen to try to avoid recall bias; however, it does not remove all possible sources of error (Aylesworth and Kuo, 2018). For instance, this type of data might be dependent on the time of the year in which the study is carried out (Purcell et al., 2018). Semi-structured interviews were conducted during the main fishing season in Tobago, which implies that the values reported by fisherfolk refer to the usual catch during this period and that it is possible that they catch lower amounts of fish in the remaining five months. Moreover, during semi-structured interviews, fishermen provided the amount of fish they most commonly caught, which does not take into account particularly positive or negative fishing trips. However, while 'good catches' were reported to occur very rarely, 'bad catches' were reported much more frequently. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that they do not equalise each other. Finally, not all the catch is actually sold after a fishing trip, as a small part of it is generally kept for household consumption and in some cases donated to relatives and/or close friends. For all these reasons, the total annual net income of fisherfolk calculated in the different scenarios might be an overestimate, not least since none of them took into account boat and engine maintenance costs.

Nevertheless, the fact that the main target species vary throughout the year does not really undermine the accuracy of the assessment. In fact, the vast majority of fish species are sold at the same price. Additionally, the retail price set by fishers is very stable and increases only occasionally if the fuel price rises significantly. The situation is slightly different for fishmongers, who exert a stronger control over the market. They can decrease the price they buy at from fisherfolk if the

catches are abundant in a certain moment, but this happens less than in the past because of the overall declining catches.

Apart from the assumptions made in the three scenarios and the general uncertainties, the estimates provided do not reflect the value of the entire fisheries sector in north-east Tobago because they do not take into account fish vendors and seafood processing. The business of fishmongers (and their mark-up on fish sales) was not taken into account for two reasons. First of all, they also move the fish outside the geographical limits of the study area, which made it very difficult to track their movements given the time and resources available for the research. Secondly, their purchases from fishers are very variable, as they depend on potential commissions (i.e., someone orders a certain quantity of fish) and on the time of the year. In fact, while vendors actively look for fish during the main fishing season, off season (or in general when the catches are low) fisherfolk call them if needed. So, combining everything, any attempt to estimate the earnings of fish vendors would have been based on mere conjectures, and not reasonable assumptions. The value added by seafood processing was not taken into account either; the rationale for this decision is that it is negligible compared to the revenues from the direct sale of fish.

3.1.6| Multifaceted potential to improve the fisheries sector in north-east Tobago

A multitude of possibilities exist to improve small-scale fisheries. Among them, only those that dovetail with the concept of sustainable Blue Economy, and are therefore promising for advancing the sector in a sustainable manner, have been considered. Moreover, the focus is mainly on opportunities that have a connection to the local setting, in the sense that they build on something that already exists, projects in the pipeline, or ideas and initiatives of fishing communities. The aim is to seek opportunities that fit the Biosphere Reserve and local social contexts, and therefore have a concrete chance of being implemented meaningfully and successfully, possibly leading to the development of artisanal fisheries in north-east Tobago in a sustainable and equitable way. Some strategies to improve the sector have already been outlined in sections 3.1.3 and 3.1.4 (e.g., establishing a participatory catch monitoring program, addressing the possible overfishing by foreign fishing vessels), and more are discussed in the following.

As evidenced in the previous section, fishing operational costs are very high. In particular, fuel expenses alone use up about 61% of the gross income earned by fishers on average. Thus, it is no coincidence that more than a quarter of study participants (12 out of 46) referred to the excessive cost of fuel during interviews and that this topic came up in countless informal conversations. The fact that in north-east Tobago people fish exclusively alone, or at most with one other person on the boat, does not help to share the expenditure. According to some, the substantial fuel costs prevent many people from fishing as they used to, i.e. going to sea frequently even outside the main fishing season and even if the catches at a certain time are low, and travelling great distances by boat. They

have now decreased the mileage, which was reported to be problematic because longer searches are necessary to find fish, and have to really ponder when to go fishing. Therefore, the considerable fuel costs explain why there are a lot of locals only going fishing if they see the people who go to sea more frequently bringing back satisfying catches. An interviewee referred to the latter as "hardcore fishers" and to the former as "opportunistic fishers".

Added to all of that, the investments required to buy a boat and an engine were considered too high. In total, 44% of interviewees mentioned that the costs associated with fishing are too much and/or that some form of government assistance is needed in this regard. When asked about their ideas on how to improve the fishing sector in Tobago, some fishermen hoped that people would start to invest more in the profession (e.g., by upgrading their boats) so that it could be seen as a real business model and career opportunity. However, they also admitted that it is very difficult for people to do this given the current prices. Combined with the catch decline, fuel, boat and engine costs make it very difficult to make a living from fishing, which some started to consider an unprofitable activity. This seems to explain why young people no longer enter the fisheries, as a respondent highlighted:

“That’s why you don’t see young fishermen. They don’t have interest in the business anymore.” [Interviewee 4]

Very young fishers were never observed, and interviewees had been fishing for a living on average for 33 years. None of them had been fishing for less than 10 years, and only about 20% ($n = 9$) had been fishing for 20 years or less. Everyone else had at least 25 years of experience, up to a maximum of 50. Thus, in general, there were not many young people dedicated to this profession. To cope with the expensiveness of boats and engines, fishermen felt they need government support, especially through subsidies or tax breaks. However, such measures have already been put in place by the government of Trinidad and Tobago. Registered vessel owners (valid Fisherman’s Certificate and Certificate of Registry for vessel) can have subsidies when buying fishing vessels and VAT (and duty) exemption on (imported) engines (Ministry of Agriculture, Land & Fisheries, 2024). Evidently, the information does not circulate enough among fisherfolk in north-east Tobago, and the reasons for this limited information flow need to be better understood. A similar problem exists in relation to the above-mentioned registration as vessel owner: fishermen complained about the bureaucratic procedures being very complicated and not straightforward because they are not clearly explained. Addressing this lack of transparency and communication between the government and the fishing communities is very important, also with a view to reducing discontent with the former.

The central government put in place a system to help fishers with fuel costs as well. By submitting a set of forms with original bills on a quarterly basis, registered vessel owners are eligible for a rebate on gasoline, diesel and oil used during fishing. However, according to stakeholders and key informants, this program never came into operation in Tobago, which is why many fishermen were unhappy and showed hope of seeing it implemented in the future. The island is not the only place

where people protest against the high costs of fishing (e.g., Ben-Yami, 2008; Tanner et al., 2014). One solution that has been found in other parts of the world is exactly fuel subsidies, which are common in the small-scale fishing sector (e.g., de Melo Alves Damasio, 2016; Islam et al., 2016; Owusu, 2021). In terms of overall economic value, however, the vast majority of global fisheries subsidies still go to the large-scale and industrial fishing sector (Schuhbauer et al., 2020), which means that in some countries it receives amounts disproportionate to landings and employment rate compared to small-scale fisheries (Schuhbauer et al., 2019). For this reason, Schuhbauer et al. (2019) recommend a redistribution of subsidies, which could also apply well to Trinidad and Tobago should there be such an imbalance. How to direct the subsidies is an additionally important issue. While subsidies for fuel (but also engines and boats) directly help fisherfolk from an economic point of view and thus benefit their business in the immediate future, they also lead to more fishing effort and can therefore increase overfishing in the absence of management, ultimately adversely affecting the fishers' livelihoods. In this regard, government fuel subsidies reduce or completely nullify the sustainability value that higher fuel prices could have by decreasing harvest, given that fuel is a significant contributor to fishing costs (Sumaila, 2008). Another argument against that type of subsidies is related to the CO₂ emissions associated with fuel use. First of all, in general terms, the fishing sector needs to lower its carbon footprint (Suuronen et al., 2012), which is the opposite of what would most likely happen in the presence of a fuel subsidy system. Secondly, in north-east Tobago the carbon footprint of the artisanal fishing sector is already quite large. In fact, fishers' fuel consumption is very high as evidenced by the sums spent in gasoline, mainly because a great proportion of them make daily trips to distant fishing grounds with small boats and inefficient outboard motors. Small-scale fisheries can be significant emitters of greenhouse gasses, even compared to some large-scale fisheries per ton of seafood landed, which is why fisheries policy or reforms to their management should consider regulations to reduce carbon emissions (Purcell et al., 2018). All of these aspects suggest that fuel subsidies are far from being the best option to support small-scale fisheries (and the fishing sector in general) and that other support opportunities should be sought. One such opportunity to lower fuel costs and consumption is related to the importance of letting fish stocks recover to a healthy state and keeping them close to Tobago, so that fisherfolk no longer have to travel far offshore. Thus, the possibility of bringing FADs closer to shore becomes even more relevant, as attracting pelagic species nearer to the coast would result in a win-win situation in this context: fishers spend less in fuel, while CO₂ emissions are reduced. Additionally, in this way even poorer fisherfolk who do not have enough money to buy powerful engines would benefit, since at the moment they are forced to fish closer to their villages in less productive waters, due to the high costs of fishing and the lack of investment capacity. To make all of that possible, a feasible solution is the implementation of a long-term nearshore-FAD program, which could best be realised by studying how to position the devices in a way that maximises their attracting capacity and by improving the technology of their design. Nearshore-FAD programs have been put in place for instance in the

Pacific Region and in the Indian Ocean, and some of their lessons that should be heeded relate to sustainability (Beverly et al., 2012; Albert et al., 2015 & 2016). In fact, these programs have to be approached in such a way that they do not lead to further overexploitation of fish populations (Bell et al., 2015), as this would jeopardise the livelihoods of local communities instead of benefitting them.

Another measure to reduce the carbon footprint and fuel costs is the modernisation of the artisanal fishing fleet. During fieldwork, information on 49 boats have been obtained (higher than the number of fishermen because some people owned more than one boat), and more than 70% ($n = 35$) are powered by 2-stroke outboard engines that run on gasoline and oil mixed by hand. They are characterised by high fuel consumption and by having negative environmental impacts that go beyond CO₂ emissions, for instance due to the release of a portion of the unburnt fuel into the water. To reduce all of that, a potential solution is to switch to hybrid (gasoline and LPG) electronic fuel-injected 4-stroke engines. A technology that converts standard electronic fuel-injected 4-stroke engines to dual fuel usage has already been successfully applied in other countries (e.g., Spain, Colombia, and Nigeria) and complies with EU and UN regulations. Approaching funding agencies to finance a replacement of 2-stroke engines with 4-stroke hybrid engines is a possibility that the ERIC has been pursuing. Before doing so, however, it is necessary to conduct a pilot project that tests the acceptance and capacity of the system to meet fisherfolk's performance demands and expectations (e.g., in terms of speed and fuel consumption). A proposal to fund this pilot project, which consists of purchasing a fishing pirogue and a 4-stroke engine, installing the conversion kit, and allowing Tobagonian fishers to test drive it, was submitted by ERIC but after a long wait the potential funder withdrew in early 2024. Since then, this project with enormous beneficial potential for the artisanal fishing sector in Tobago is on hold. A government intervention on this initiative (as well as on projects of this kind) would be an excellent way to redirect fisheries subsidies, in line with the valuable recommendations of Schuhbauer et al. (2020). Should the test phase be successful and funding for an island-wide transition be obtained, Tobago could become a role model for the Caribbean region, having significantly reduced the operational costs and environmental impacts (e.g., greenhouse gasses emissions and liquid pollution) associated with boat engines used in artisanal fisheries.

Finally, another way to lower operational costs is linked to the presence of ice machines in the fishing facilities, which should provide ice to fisherfolk at a favourable price. With the exception of Castara's fishing facility, the most recently built, all the others in north-east Tobago (located in Charlotteville, Delaford, Roxborough, and Belle Garden) have ice machines that have been broken for a long time. Responses to a specific question in semi-structured interviews revealed that most people (33 out of 46) believed this to be a major problem and the facilities' main deficiency. In the absence of a functioning ice-making machine, fisherfolk are forced to buy it from minimarkets, which charge between 50% and 100% more than fishing facilities, where the price is controlled by the THA. Having working ice machines is a strong potential to reduce running costs and is relatively easy to achieve,

as it would only be a matter of repairing. By saving fishers a considerable amount of money on an almost daily basis, this intervention would probably decrease their dissatisfaction with fishing facilities and, consequently, with the local government. In fact, 30 fishermen blamed it for never taking care of the maintenance of these premises, some of which are now in a dilapidated state. In this regard, it is also highly recommended to consult with fisherfolk before any future renovation or construction of new fishing facilities. Many of them complained that this has never happened in the past, adding that most of the problems the buildings have at the design level (e.g., not enough storage space for all fishers, air conditioning in the wet room, absence of an open area at the front to display the fish) could have been easily avoided by consulting stakeholders.

Another great potential for improving the fisheries sector in north-east Tobago is to strengthen fisherfolk associations. At the time of fieldwork, these existed in eight villages (Charlotteville, Speyside, Delaford, Roxborough, Belle Garden, Castara, Parlatuvier, and Bloody Bay), and 70% of respondents (32 out of 46) were part of one of them. However, half were reported to be not active or not fully active. This theme emerged during interviews, with several study participants expressing dissatisfaction with the association they were part of, raising collaboration and management issues. Additionally, (vice) presidents of fisherfolk associations revealed that many people tend to be very reluctant to show up in meetings. The lack of organisation in the fishing communities was perceived as a big problem affecting the sector. (Vice) Presidents explained the ambitions of their organisations mainly in terms of representing fisherfolk and giving them a voice, supporting them in bureaucratic procedures, helping their families in case of death, approaching the government for assistance (easier and more effective as a group rather than as individuals), and ultimately promoting general cooperation among members. The latter is precisely the hope that was expressed by stakeholders during interviews.

The importance of organisations and collective action in small-scale fisheries has been extensively analysed on a global level by the FAO (2013), which then further emphasised their value through the inclusion of the concepts in the voluntary guidelines for securing sustainable small-scale fisheries (FAO, 2015). In addition to what was reported by (vice) presidents of Tobagonian fishing organisations, which was found to be in line with their benefits according to the literature, associations and cooperatives play a crucial role in community development and well-being for a multitude of reasons (FAO 2012; Kalikoski et al., 2019). They contribute to achieving long-term benefits and addressing livelihood insecurities, for example by creating gender-balanced employment opportunities, facilitating access to funds and microcredit schemes, making fishing operations more sustainable, allowing cost-saving bulk purchases of engines and fishing gear, increasing fishers' price-negotiating power, and opening up new markets (FAO 2012; Méndez-Medina et al., 2015; Rivera et al., 2017; Kalikoski 2019). In this last regard, a concrete possibility for associations or cooperatives of artisanal fisherfolk in north-east Tobago is to organise the transport and sale of the fish they catch in Trinidad, thereby bypassing Trinidadian fishmongers. The latter go

to Tobago occasionally throughout the year, but intensify their visits during Lent when there is a fish consumption peak in the country. If fisherfolk associations took over this business, their members could obtain much better prices for the fish, since it is generally paid better in Trinidad. Furthermore, it has been shown that the development of national long-term FAD programs can be successful if done in collaboration with fishing associations, to which maintenance and replacement of FADs could be delegated (Albert et al., 2016). This knowledge could be applied to a project with the characteristics previously described, and that in Tobago would likely be island-wide. Finally, fishing associations can provide for information exchange and training (Kalikoski et al., 2019) and membership has been positively correlated also with participation in training activities external to them, as information reaches fisherfolk more easily (Ifabiyi et al., 2023). Another way interviewees identified to improve the fishing sector is precisely through training of fishers. At the moment, worldwide, most efforts seem to be directed towards improving post-harvest seafood processing methods (e.g., MacKeracher et al., 2019; Cramer and Kittinger, 2021; Purcell et al., 2021), given the potential to increase fisherfolk's income. Instead, study participants mainly referred to training in fishing methods to enhance their skills and knowledge. This could be a way to introduce new fishing techniques and/or modern fishing gears, a desire that has also been expressed by fishers elsewhere (e.g., in Nigeria; Asa and Inyang, 2016).

Although capacity building in best-practice methods for post-harvest processing has not been mentioned by respondents, it has potential for livelihood development, too. Therefore, both types of training programs are recommended as a further excellent opportunity to redistribute and direct the fisheries subsidies widely discussed above. Indeed, going beyond primary production in the fishing sector enables to add value to the fish catch and increase the income of artisanal fishers. Popular higher-value products in Tobago are fish ham, salt and smoked fish, which are made locally and not on a large commercial scale (even though salt fish can also be imported). The Caribbean type of fish smoking is very different from what European consumers are commonly used to: the fish is cooked for a long time and dried completely, so that it can be preserved for extended periods. A project aimed at introducing a Caribbean – European fusion smoking is being launched by ERIC during the drafting of this dissertation. Atlantic bonito (*Sarda sarda*) and Albacore (*Thunnus alalunga*) will be processed in smoking kilns, and after the value-adding they will be sold mainly to restaurants, hotels, and gourmet shops (i.e., shops selling hard-to-find ingredients and high-quality products) on neighbouring Trinidad. This project will combine training in post-harvest processing with sustainability objectives. In fact, fishermen who support it will be offered more than the market price of fish, provided that they voluntarily commit to sustainable fishing (e.g., not catching certain species during the spawning period, releasing undersized fish and lobsters with eggs). All of this will be paired with an outreach program informing on the fishing practices that are best avoided. Finally, the initiative is also a promising way to involve more women in the fisheries sector, since some of them will be the ones to receive the training in post-harvesting operations. In a context where fishing roles

are almost exclusively occupied by men, projects like this can lead to a more inclusive (as well as sustainable) Blue Economy. Sometimes, following the completion of programs aimed at capacity building in post-harvest processing skills, uncertainty remains as to whether the investments bring long-term benefits or not (Purcell et al., 2024). Therefore, when carrying out initiatives such as the one just explained, it is essential to monitor the adoption and spread of the innovations promoted through training, which can then provide important lessons to improve design and implementation of future projects (MacKeracher et al., 2019).

Looking at potential future projects, capacity building could also be implemented to improve the products that are already obtained as a result of post-harvesting processing, to teach these practices to others, and to introduce new delicacies (e.g., Albacore pâté) as will be done with the smoking. Initiatives like this have enormous potential, since the adoption of simple and inexpensive technologies can result in big impacts along the value chain, particularly by increasing the income of artisanal fishers (FAO, 2018). Investments in communal fish processing facilities could be facilitated by fisherfolk associations (FAO, 2012), and following the suggestion of Ifabiyi et al. (2023) training could be effectively conducted involving them. Alternatively, in order to maintain and further push the gender inclusiveness of the local Blue Economy, those projects could be undertaken and led by community women's groups. It has been demonstrated that such organisations can achieve great results with sufficient support and commitment among their members (e.g., Velarde et al., 2024). These authors provide a number of lessons learnt from this case study in the Galapagos that could be applied to increase the likelihood of success of similar initiatives in north-east Tobago.

3.2| Tourism sector

3.2.1| Overview

The tourist attractions within the North-East Tobago Man and the Biosphere Reserve are essentially nature-based and set in the context of an island ridge-to-reef scenery, ranging from tropical rainforest to marine marvels, combined with the experience of rural fishing village living. The main tourism businesses in north-east Tobago are guided tours, scuba diving, accommodation and catering. While dive sites are scattered all over the area, tours that fall fully within the Blue Economy are limited to coastline sightseeing, Little Tobago (and neighbouring Goat Island), and St. Giles Islet Complex. In addition to diving, both Little Tobago and St. Giles are renowned for birdwatching, particularly of seabirds, as they are Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas according to BirdLife International (2024). More detailed information on tourism activities that can be carried out as part of the Blue Economy is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Main Blue Economy tourist activities in north-east Tobago. Adapted from ERIC (2022b)

Focus	Activity	Location	Frequency	Main Target(s)
<i>Local Culture</i>	Fisherman's festival	Various villages	Annual	Local
	Traditional fishing village life	Every village	Permanent	International
<i>Sport</i>	Tobago International Game Fishing Tournament	Charlotteville	Annual	Local and international
<i>Nature</i>	Beach relaxation, bathing and sunbathing	Charlotteville, Speyside, Kings Bay, Castara, Englishman's Bay, Parlatuvier, Bloody Bay	Permanent	Local and international
	Sightseeing by boat	Along the entire coast	Permanent	Local and international
	Recreational fishing	Starting from Charlotteville, Speyside, Castara and Parlatuvier	Permanent	Local and international
	Snorkelling	Charlotteville, Speyside, Kings Bay, Castara, Englishman's Bay, Parlatuvier, Bloody Bay	Permanent	International
	Scuba diving	Speyside and Kings Bay areas, leeward coast	Permanent	International
	Turtle watching	Various beaches	Seasonal (from March to September)	International
	Bird watching	St. Giles Islet Complex and Little Tobago	Permanent	International
<i>Science</i>	Science tourism	Charlotteville	Permanent	International

The most common accommodation types are guesthouses, self-catering apartments and cottages, and villas; there are also a few (boutique) hotels. The villages where almost all of them are located are Charlotteville, Speyside, Castara, Parlatuvier and, to a lesser extent, the area of Parrot Hall and Englishman's Bay. Therefore, the main tourist areas of north-east Tobago coincide with those villages, with the only exception of Kings Bay, which is a popular beach. They are shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Tourist map of Tobago showing the main tourist areas in the northeastern region. Adapted from: <https://visittobago.gov.tt/sites/default/files/2023-07/2023-tobago-calendar-of-events-foldout.pdf>

Between the 1990s and the early 2000s, tourism was very successful in Tobago. According to many people, including key informants, this was the period when the sector reached its peak. Subsequently, tourism declined drastically. Competition with other Caribbean islands was the main reason identified by interviewees to explain the downturn, coupled with the fact that Tobago did not develop its tourism products adequately. This has been linked to the anti-tourism policy of the government in power during those years, with some respondents recalling that marketing decreased and funding programs were discontinued. Some key informants additionally reported that tourism was in rivalry with the oil and gas sector in terms of attention. However, the former could not compete with the massive revenues brought in by the latter, which has therefore always been considered as the priority and overshadowed tourism:

“Tourism and Hospitality was not given the consideration it deserved. [...] The strength of the oil and gas sector led to [the] belief that tourism wasn’t needed.” [Interviewee 99]

This is why, according to another key informant,

“It [the tourism sector] was not taken seriously, it was given to a Division or a Ministry just as a little hobby.” [Interviewee 96]

As a result of all of that, Tobago waned as a tourism destination and the sector did not recover for many years. It was not until the late 2010s that tourism finally started to revive and international flights to come back to the island. However, soon after, SARS-CoV-2 hit and the sector was flooded

again. As of early 2024, tourism is still recovering after the coronavirus pandemic, and the fact that Tobago is not yet back at pre-COVID-19 arrival figures is strongly felt by local stakeholders. In fact, 37 of the 45 tourism operators interviewed highlighted that at the time of this study there were not as many tourists as before the pandemic. When considering tour and dive operators, lifeguards, accommodation providers and key informants (with whom the topic was discussed) combined, it is remarkable that 50 out of 51 respondents used the word(s) “bad”, “not good” or “poor” to describe the state of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago, and/or said that it has not yet reached its potential.

The somewhat delayed recovery is partly due to the fact that Trinidad and Tobago only reopened to international tourists in July 2021 and there were still no international flights to Tobago by the end of 2021, while for comparison many other Caribbean countries reopened their borders in July and August 2020 (Budriea and Narinesingh, 2022; ERIC, 2022b), almost an entire year earlier.

Notwithstanding, figures are showing a positive trend and this is recognized by local stakeholders, who are noticing a growth in the sector and that international tourists are slowly starting to return. One thing was even mentioned as an improvement over the past on an absolute level. When the Government of Trinidad and Tobago restricted travel both into and out of the country during the COVID-19 pandemic, many Trinidadians discovered Tobago as a weekend and holiday destination. In addition to keeping it alive during the border closure period, a lot of them have maintained the habit of visiting Tobago. At the moment, Trinidad is the largest market for its sister island (as well as the closest), making domestic tourism vital. This is an asset that not many other Caribbean islands can boast and which provides Tobago with an influx of tourists for some months outside the main tourist season. In fact, while the high season for international tourism is roughly between November and April, July and August are still considered important because many Trinidadians go to Tobago to spend their holidays.

3.2.2| Perceived reasons for the low influx of tourists

According to stakeholders (51 in total), including key informants who were interviewed in relation to the tourism sector, two main factors are responsible for the small number of people visiting Tobago to date: scarcity of direct flights and poor marketing.

Starting with the former, more than a third of the study participants (18 out of 51) identified the low availability of direct flights to the island as a major obstacle to the development of international tourism. This relationship is a known problem in the literature (e.g., Kantawateera et al., 2015; Özgüt and Uludağ, 2022) and is determined for instance by the fact that the lack of direct flights can make travelling inconvenient and more time-consuming, thus dissuading visitors (Cró et al., 2022). Various studies have found that the availability of direct flights is determinant to attract international tourists (Fujii et al., 1992; Deluna and Jeon, 2014; Tveteras and Roll, 2014), hence it is deemed paramount for Tobago to establish non-stop flight routes to its main target countries (mostly in Europe and North

America). This would allow Tobago to compete more with some of its neighbouring islands such as Barbados and St. Lucia, which currently have more direct airlift options and are therefore more likely to influence the tourists' destination choice to their advantage. Some key informants revealed that this is an issue the THA is trying to address by upgrading the airport (it is being expanded at the time of writing this thesis) and by looking into new airlines that might be interested in reaching Tobago. Should this be successful, the accessibility of the destination will be improved and consequently the arrival figures will increase, as it is one of the most important factors influencing tourism flows into SIDS (Vítová et al., 2019).

An even more important reason to explain the low tourist flow according to interviewees is the weak marketing of the island. Fifty-seven percent of respondents (29 out of 51) were unsatisfied with the work the government is doing in terms of promotion, as they thought it is not sufficient or even not done properly. Some of them were more specific, adding that it is especially north-east Tobago which is not adequately advertised because too much attention is placed on the southwestern part of the island. This region is more developed for tourism, both in terms of accommodations and services, and it is where the airport is located. It is currently the most touristy part of Tobago and the most popular location for domestic tourism (local tourists visiting the Biosphere Reserve are mainly single-day visitors), being oriented towards entertainment and nightlife. Stakeholders criticised the over-concentration on these factors because the island has much more to offer. Thus, the most widespread hope among tourism operators was for better marketing of Tobago, perhaps with a stronger focus on the north-east.

Another major concern was raised in relation to the topic of marketing, namely the fact that the NETMABR is to date not fully capitalised on because it has not received enough recognition. This was confirmed by key informants, one of whom additionally disclosed that although the Biosphere Reserve is the feature that strongly distinguishes north-east Tobago from other small island destinations in the Caribbean, the UNESCO brand is not being pushed even at international travel and tourism trade shows. The interviewee admitted that the inadequate promotion of the NETMABR to the international public is a severe shortcoming, given the potential it has:

“There is a bit of disconnection between what could be done with the Reserve and what is actually being done.” [Interviewee 98]

The lack of brand awareness also extends to the local population. Countless informal conversations revealed that at the time of the study hardly anyone knew of its existence, including residents of the villages that are part of it. Not even all the people who work in the Division of Tourism, Culture, Antiquities and Transportation of the THA are aware of the NETMABR, including people working for the Promotions Unit. This is indeed a serious problem, since the mandate of the Promotions Unit is to disseminate information on the destination to visitors. Given that the Biosphere Reserve is arguably north-east Tobago's greatest asset and a perfect sales tool, improved marketing and brand

awareness are highly recommended, both on an international and on a local level. In fact, the UNESCO brand could be utilised and pushed by local stakeholders, who would thus contribute to the development of sustainable tourism in the region.

One third of study participants mentioned that awareness among residents should also be raised on how to benefit from tourism more generally. They identified the lack of training, from tour guiding to customer service, as the reason why tourist services are often not at the right level of professionalism. Since this can possibly hinder tourism growth, respondents expressed the priority need for the government to implement capacity building programs for people working in the sector or who intend to do so. This necessity has already been pointed out by Smith and Jordan (2021), following a study focusing specifically on the village of Castara. Moreover, according to some interviewees, this aspect could be coupled with education in schools aimed at teaching students the importance of the tourism sector and the opportunities it offers. The great importance of education and training to improve tourism worldwide, and in the Caribbean in particular, has been emphasized since the last century (e.g., Conlin, 1993). Given the vast potential that tourism has in north-east Tobago, there is a need for well-educated and trained professionals capable of delivering world-class services and quality management (Charles, 1997). Among the actions that the government can take to foster this and consequently develop the sector is the provision of capacity building programs, which should not only focus on customer service (or tour guiding), but also on higher level business skills (Lee et al., 2015; Cannonier and Burke, 2019). Along these lines, key training areas identified for Tobago include entrepreneurship, hospitality and tourism management, accounting, business planning, and computer literacy (Smith and Jordan, 2021). The authors further suggest that the THA could collaborate with the Tobago Hotel and Tourism Association (THTA), the island-wide tourism association, to design courses that meet the needs of local tourism business owners. Since findings from this study confirm the importance that stakeholders attribute to training and their willingness to receive it, shown by Smith and Jordan (2021) in Castara, and extend that to the whole of north-east Tobago, it is argued that the launching of a capacity building program should not be deferred any longer. Developing this in the short-term following the available recommendations is a real and big opportunity to enhance the tourism product of Tobago.

3.2.3| Cooperation between stakeholders and the model of Castara

The lack of unity among stakeholders is an issue that has also been raised by tourism operators, showing an analogy with the fishing sector. Respondents complained that people do not work together towards the common goal of improving tourism and Tobago as a destination. One way to do this is through the formation of local tourism associations, as it was done in Castara with the Castara Tourism Development Association (CTDA). This was the only functioning tourism association at the time of fieldwork and was reported as the key to the tourism success of the village, which has high occupancy rates year-round. Castara is currently the tourism hub in north-east

Tobago and, as many stakeholders acknowledged, it represents an exception in the otherwise anything but ideal industry of the region. At the heart of its fortune is precisely CTDA, a community-led group which represents tourism-related businesses and whose strength is the involvement of foreign property owners as well as local stakeholders (approximately 1/3 and 2/3, respectively), which allows for a collaboration between them. The Association also has a broader ambition, namely to represent the interests of all village residents, since it engages in regular consultation with the Castara Fisherfolk Association, Castara Village Council and faith-based organisations. One board member illustrated the importance of this in a very emblematic manner:

“In this way when we have meetings we don’t talk to people, we don’t talk to individuals. We talk to Castara.” [Interviewee 60]

Under the guidance of CTDA, Castara developed collectively a community-based tourism (CBT) product characterised by the pursuit of sustainability, promotion of small businesses and absence of large all-inclusive hotels and resorts, so as to maintain as much of the island’s natural beauty as possible. Given its success, one of the main recommendations for the tourism sector is that the other tourist villages (at the moment mainly Charlotteville, Speyside, and Parlatuvier) and those that might be interested in becoming such (e.g., Delaford) copy Castara’s model. As a first initiative, functional community groups could be created, if necessary with government support, which can then lead to a number of local benefits. For instance, they would have the power to mobilise funds from international agencies and open up training opportunities to build local expertise (Smith and Jordan, 2021). In addition to what has already been discussed above, training is very important also for a successful CBT (Gascón, 2013; Dodds et al., 2018). The aim of local tourism associations, in agreement with the achievements of CTDA, should be to foster collaboration between stakeholders and establish CBT, which however is not so easy to achieve. Despite the great potential of community-based tourism and agreement on some crucial conditions that determine its success or failure (e.g., Armstrong, 2012), many experiences have not been prosperous (Coria and Calfucura, 2012). Such conditions have also been put together in frameworks (e.g., Dangi and Jamal, 2016), but they can only be used as a broad guideline. The point is that there is no single set of criteria to be applied that guarantees that every CBT initiative will succeed, but rather general facilitating and inhibiting factors that have to be adapted to individual communities, considering their specific characteristics (Dodds et al., 2018). In any case, there is nothing better than a role model as close as Castara to drive (community-based) tourism development in north-east Tobago.

During interviews, some participants suggested that communities could receive financial assistance to establish CBT by attracting foreign investors to partner with local stakeholders. However, key informants explained that in the latter part of the 2000s a law that disincentivises this action has been introduced. Hence, it is recommended that if an effective tourism product is to be developed in north-east Tobago, an enabling environment for small and medium foreign investments should be restored.

Moreover, a group of respondents expressed hope for governmental support regarding the financial aspect of developing CBT. These expectations seem legitimate, as an analysis of 68 nature- and community-based tourism case studies in developing countries conducted by Zielinski et al. (2018) revealed that almost 80% of ventures started with external support. The authors suggest that, among other things, it is necessary precisely because capital is needed for tourism development (Zielinski et al., 2018). According to Dodds et al. (2018), the best way to assist CBT development is through micro-financing, and not grants: when there is a cost-sharing or loan system implying that communities provide an in-kind or monetary contribution, an increased sense of ownership and autonomy evolves. Following this further recommendation is considered of utmost importance in the context of north-east Tobago, characterized by an over-dependence on government interventions and a lack of entrepreneurship.

3.2.4| The importance of product development

Semi-structured interviews revealed that 22% of people (11 out of 51) believe that tourist sites are substandard. This was confirmed through personal observations, which led to noticing considerable deficiencies in the development and management of the local attractions in north-east Tobago. According to Allahar (2015), the situation is the same throughout the country, as he demonstrated that the great majority of sites both in Trinidad and in Tobago attract visitors because of their significance and distinctiveness, and certainly not because of their good condition. Hence, Allahar (2015) concludes that improvement is strongly needed if international standards are to be met. In the view of the participants in this study, mainly maintenance and on-site information for visitors are lacking, giving the impression that the sites are somewhat degraded and resulting in the failure to meet tourists' expectations created by the legal protection status. For instance, Little Tobago is a core zone of the NETMABR, but there is no tourist information available, the condition of the trails is not ideal, and while access should be controlled by the Department of Natural Resources and Forestry (ERIC, 2019), in practice anybody can access it at any time as the legislation is not enforced. Beyond this legislative issue, it should be considered that proper development often requires making sites more pleasant for tourists, e.g. by providing educational and explanatory signposts and walking paths, and having special consideration for aesthetics (Abuhay et al., 2019). Given the very small size of the islet, light interventions to upgrade the site would require relatively little effort and investment, and could do justice to an internationally renowned site. For example, all paths could be restored and enhanced, and one of the abandoned buildings could be refurbished and converted into a small museum. The realisation of such improvements could then warrant the introduction of a user fee, which in turn could be used to keep the site in good condition. The museum could inform about the rich history of Little Tobago, its flora and fauna (perhaps with a section dedicated to the significance of Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs)), and the surrounding marine ecosystem, which includes some of Tobago's most famous dive sites. Such a facility could

be the first 'compulsory' stop on the Little Tobago tour in order to collect user fees and data on arrivals, which would allow to obtain information on the number of tourists visiting the islet and to make inferences about how many people access the NETMABR (both figures are not currently available). The museum could also serve as a visitor center, providing information materials on north-east Tobago and more broadly a point of contact and interaction with tourists. This is essential because people need clear facts about attractions and services, as the impression they get of a destination depends not only on the sites per se, but also on the way basic necessary information is provided (Abuhay et al., 2019). Therefore, what is suggested here would certainly enhance visitors' overall experience and help fulfil their expectations.

The lack of standards is a problem that was reported to affect also the catering and accommodation sectors by almost 40% of study participants (20 out of 51).

Starting with the former, the main issue raised is that people do not cater with tourists' needs in mind. Some of the already very few restaurants are closed on Saturdays, during holidays (when there are more tourists, e.g., Christmas), and in the evenings. Street food stands and eateries are few and run out of food and close in the early afternoon at the latest, implying that for tourists it might be difficult to find somewhere to dine or that options are extremely limited (in some cases to a single place). Speaking of Speyside, one stakeholder commented:

"This village is a food desert." [Interviewee 84]

Therefore, interviewees (including key informants) expressed the need to develop a better catering sector that meets tourists' requirements. This would be very important because gastronomy is known to positively influence the way tourists experience a destination (Kivela and Crofts, 2006) and can favour their travel satisfaction (Babolian Hendijani, 2016; Robinson and Getz, 2016). Furthermore, Trinidad and Tobago's traditional cuisine has great potential to actively improve tourism, as according to Winston (2022), the country is unofficially recognised as the culinary capital of the Caribbean. Tobago's local cuisine shares most typical dishes with its sister island and should be promoted and valued in order for CBT to take full advantage of it. Gastronomy significantly contributes to create the image of a destination (Ab Karim et al., 2009) and can increase its attractiveness (e.g., Cracolici and Nijkamp, 2008; Leong et al., 2017). Thus, if valorised and marketed in the right way, Tobago's cuisine could provide the island with a meaningful competitive advantage over its Caribbean neighbours.

Turning to accommodations, the reported reason for inadequacy lies in the fact that many properties do not adhere to international standards. Since the hospitality sector is a true underpinning of tourism, this situation should be of particular concern. In fact, it is widely recognised that the progress of tourism development is constrained by the (under)development of the accommodation industry (Magombo et al., 2017). Upgrading its quality is extremely important to increase the competitiveness

of a destination (Salazar, 2008; Rogerson, 2013) and can therefore play a direct role in tourism development (Provotorina et al., 2022). Consistently, interviewees considered it imperative to upgrade the hospitality sector by improving the level of properties and establishing international standards. In addition to the previously discussed advantages, having functioning local tourism associations could facilitate this transition, for instance concerning the creation of a uniform and standardised accommodation product. The THTA has been dealing with the latter aspect on an island scale, as one of its purposes is precisely to ensure that Tobago's hospitality is at a certain quality level. However, many properties are not THTA members, and the industry is not well legislated. To date, anyone in Tobago can set up a guesthouse (or similar) without having to comply with any regulations and without having to declare it, which implies that unregistered accommodations are not inspected and do not pay taxes as the government is not officially aware of their existence. In order to change this situation and at the same time work towards its goal, the THTA has been implementing some key projects in cooperation with the THA. The first one is the Tourism Accommodation Relief Grant, which made governmental funding available for the upgrade of tourism accommodation facilities to assist owners in recovering from the coronavirus pandemic. The ingenuity of the project was that to access the grant, a property had to be registered with the THTA and working towards the Trinidad and Tobago Tourism Industry Certification (TTTIC). This is a national certification program that sets minimum requirements for tourism products and services, assuring that they – if certified – have achieved an acceptable level of quality (TTAL, 2024). The relief initiative was successful in bringing more properties in the THTA and improving the accommodation sector because many people wanted to access the grant. Quite similar is the Tourism Accommodation Upgrade Project, which provides a partial refund for properties' upgrade. In order to be eligible, an owner has to be part of a tourism association and working towards TTTIC. Finally, another way to tackle the problem of unregistered properties and their associated lack of standards is to track all accommodations that operate without registration and ask them to join the formal business community. This initiative has not yet been implemented to date, but conversations of THTA with the government (the only body with the authority to intervene) have started. While it will take time to fully resolve the issues affecting hospitality, they are being addressed through a promising multi-pronged approach. Continuing to work along these lines, popularising and pushing more the outlined strategies, will allow the creation of an improved and standardised accommodation sector, which will in turn benefit the overall tourism sector.

The potential for strengthening the hospitality sector goes even further, and this time the catering industry is concerned again. A first step forward could be taken as the Tobago Biosphere Management Alliance (TOBIMA) becomes operational. Since it will be the entity responsible for the implementation of the Man and the Biosphere Programme, TOBIMA could define the foundation that any accommodation and restaurant within the NETMABR should have to be sustainable and fit the UNESCO designation. In this way, in addition to being ideally TTTIC certified, tourism establishments

will also be 'Biosphere Reserve-approved' and therefore be in a better position to meet tourists' expectations. This could also be a very strong advertising tool. Another potential for the catering and accommodation sectors lies in having more Green Key properties in north-east Tobago (only one exists as of mid-2024). This certification represents a business commitment to environmental and sustainable performance, and is therefore ideal for a Biosphere Reserve context. Green Key would also have direct benefits for property owners, as for instance it can be an important motivational factor when tourists choose a hotel (Yurova, 2018). It has been shown that visitors' environmental awareness and concern can influence the hotel choice (Lee and Moscardo, 2005), whose green image can therefore be a powerful means of attracting more customers (Lee et al., 2010). Given these findings and that north-east Tobago is often chosen by people who are environmentally conscious (Moses-Wothke et al., 2021), it is argued that more Green Key establishments would have a positive effect on tourism, both in terms of increasing it and allowing it to advance sustainably and respecting the environment. Not least, this could also be a competitive advantage for the island over its Caribbean neighbours, which are still devoid of Green Key properties (FEE, 2024a).

What has been discussed so far shows the importance of product development to improve a destination. But there is more. The need for product development is not limited to famous tourist sites, accommodations and catering, but extends more generally to the villages of north-east Tobago. The author's personal observations in this respect were corroborated by interview results, as some stakeholders demonstrated to be aware of the situation. Twenty-two percent of respondents (11 out of 51) reflected on the fact that beyond the natural beauty, north-east Tobago does not provide enough reasons to justify a stay in the area longer than a few days or even just a day trip. Indeed, the absence of diversified tourism activities limits the overnight stay of visitors (Abuhay et al., 2019). With the exception of Castara, there is a lack of small commercial activities and recreational events that have the potential to attract and encourage visitors to go and stay longer in this part of the island. It thus seems crucial for north-east Tobago (and for small Caribbean islands in general) to complement its natural resources with other attractions and services (Allahar, 2015). For instance, following the model of Castara, promising opportunities would be to organise also in some other villages a weekly evening bonfire and 'dirt oven' baking day, an age-old tradition much appreciated by tourists who can consume locally made bread and pastries. These events should be scheduled in such a way that they do not overlap between villages, so that they can all attract tourists on specific days and/or nights, thereby avoiding internal competition. Furthermore, many more small businesses typically conceived for and loved by tourists that are currently missing could be established: from ice-cream parlours, coffee shops and fruit bars preparing juices and serving local treats (e.g., mango, sugar cane, coconut), to small periodical craft markets, traditional and beach clothes and gift shops. If a destination is to improve competitiveness, its products should develop to match evolving tourists' predilections (Dwyer and Kim, 2003). Hence the general idea of

implementing events and commercial activities that can make the destination more attractive and lively, while respecting sustainability and the Biosphere Reserve context.

Another strategy could be to enhance the beaches of the various villages. Some of them (i.e., Charlotteville, Speyside, Kings Bay, Castara and Bloody Bay) have facilities at the beachfront which, however, only have benches, generally a bar or restaurant, and toilets. Furthermore, both are not always functional, and the beaches are not always clean. Therefore, the beaches of the tourist villages in north-east Tobago have significant potential for improvement. First of all, since cleanliness and facilities are among the most (if not *the* most) important attributes that attract beachgoers (e.g., Marin et al., 2009; Saayman and Saayman, 2017), better infrastructure maintenance and regular clean-ups are a good way to start. Other opportunities to improve the beach facilities include providing wifi internet access and beach chairs and umbrellas. To capitalise more on them, the currently prescribed entrance fee should be collected regularly (at the moment this does not happen in most cases), and tourists could be charged for renting beach chairs and umbrellas, given that the entrance fee is extremely cheap (a few TTD). Then, visitor safety should be increased by clearly demarcating snorkelling areas to avoid accidents between fisherfolk and bathers, which have occasionally occurred in the past. This runs the risk of impacting the tourists' sense of security and comfort, which is another essential requirement for a sound tourism industry (Pawestri et al., 2022). Some beach facilities require other specific interventions, but the biggest problem common to all of them is the lack of treatment of the discharges that flow into the sea, which contributes to water pollution and is one of the main hindrances to achieving the Blue Flag status. At a time when there is great environmental concern, tourist destinations use certifications to try to increase their competitiveness (Capacci et al., 2015), and this was also the idea in Tobago. Blue Flag is an internationally recognised voluntary award for beaches, marinas, and tourism boats that meet and maintain strict environmental, educational, safety and accessibility criteria (FEE, 2024b). In north-east Tobago it was sought for two beaches, namely Kings Bay and Bloody Bay. The former is a Government property on a privately owned estate, so there are some legal matters to be solved before proceeding with the actions required to obtain the certification. The procedure is stalled in Bloody Bay too, as there is a lack of funds to upgrade the facility (fixing, creating access for the disabled and above all a sewage treatment system) and conduct a regular water quality testing, both of which are necessary to start working towards the Blue Flag status. Botero et al. (2024) report that the high cost associated with the latter is a major barrier to the development of the program in the entire country. Overcoming those challenges is very important for improving the tourism sector of north-east Tobago, as an analysis of the scholarly literature reveals considerable potential for the award. Although not much research was done on SIDS, it has been shown that the Blue Flag status of a beach can enhance visitors' overall experience satisfaction and be a signal of destination competitiveness (Dodds and Holmes, 2020). Moreover, various studies have demonstrated that the Blue Flag label can be effective at increasing international tourism and have a positive effect on the

economic development of the sector (Capacci et al., 2015; Merino and Prats, 2020; Castillo-Manzano et al., 2021). Blue Flag beaches possibly increase tourist demand in the area because they provide a trustworthy indication of environmental quality (Blackman et al., 2014). All of this clearly brings benefits to local tourism operators. In addition to the positive effect resulting from the increased inbound flows, contributing is also the fact that in some cases Blue Flag beaches can entice people to spend more (e.g., Saayman and Saayman, 2017). These findings are extremely relevant not only for local stakeholders, but also for the local government, responsible for pursuing the actions required to obtain the award and bearing its costs. In fact, if one of the goals of the THA is to develop the tourism sector in Tobago, the possibility raised in the literature that the costs associated with the certification are easily offset by its benefits could provide a significant motivation to begin or resume the procedures. In addition, the Blue Flag program can improve beach management (Creo and Fraboni, 2011) and has the capacity to trigger political support for it, making the certification an effective tool especially in countries without a solid coastal tourism strategy (Botero and Zielinski, 2020). Since the Blue Flag status promotes a balanced relationship between humans and the environment, it aligns perfectly with the Biosphere Reserve's objectives. In conclusion, Blue Flag is an outstanding product development initiative because it can allow to achieve a win-win situation: it holds potential for enhancing north-east Tobago as a tourist destination, and it is a valuable tool for safeguarding the environment.

3.2.5| Value assessment of the tourism sector

To estimate the economic value of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago, the annual income of tour and dive operators, as well as accommodation providers, was calculated. Added to this is the income from science tourism and yachts using the official moorings in Charlotteville. These have been installed in 2022 and are maintained by ERIC with the aim of reducing anchor damage. The money is used for ongoing servicing, ERIC conservation activities, and projects of the Charlotteville Police Youth Club (a community-based social enterprise) in support of the environment and vulnerable members of the community. The estimates that are given below represent gross revenues, since the costs of equipment, fuel, and maintenance of boats of tour and dive operators have not been taken into account, as well as the upkeep of moorings and operational costs of accommodation properties.

Starting with tour and dive operators, the number of monthly customers was multiplied by the cost of the activity. To make the calculation annual the resulting value was multiplied by 12:

$$I = n \cdot p \cdot 12$$

where:

- I is a tour or dive operator's gross income, expressed in TTD per year

- n is the number of clients that a tour or dive operator has in a month (since n can vary considerably throughout the year, interviewees were asked to provide an average between the high and low season)
- p is the price of the guided tour or dive in TTD (in the latter case, the average number of dives per person was used to calculate p)
- 12 is the number of months in a year

To conclude the computation, after the annual gross income has been calculated for all individual tour and dive operators, the values have to be added to obtain the total annual gross income of this group of professionals. This time there is no need to relate the sum to the total number of these stakeholders in the NETMABR as it was done in the case of fisherfolk. In fact, all relevant data for this calculation has been collected directly: every dive operator in north-east Tobago has been interviewed, and of the three tour guides who were not interviewed, only one regularly offers tours linked to the Blue Economy, and the respective data is available thanks to a conversation with a close collaborator. Thus, the assessment below is based wholly on information obtained during semi-structured interviews in response to specific questions aimed at assessing the economic value of the tour guiding and diving sectors (see Appendix, section 6.1.2 and considerations in 6.3).

The overall value of this first component of tourism in north-east Tobago is thus estimated at 6'247'030 TTD year⁻¹, equivalent to 920'812 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024.

For the focus on hospitality, much initial research was needed to create a list of accommodations within the Biosphere Reserve (see Appendix, section 6.4). In addition to their price per night, the second key figure for estimating the value of the sector is the occupancy rate (*(total number of rooms occupied / total number of rooms available) · 100*). The 2023 value of 45% (personal communication) was used in this computation. To date, properties in the NETMABR can accommodate around 600 guests in a total of 197 rental units. Based on an average occupation of 45%, there are approximately 89 overnight stays. Considering now that the mean cost of a rental unit (e.g., room, apartment, villa) is 132 USD night⁻¹, the gross income for the entire NETMABR area is 11'748 USD night⁻¹, yielding 4'288'020 USD year⁻¹ (equivalent to 29'091'043 TTD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024).

This calculation rests on two assumptions: every guest is a Blue Economy guest (the assumption under which the hospitality sector has been included in the analysis, see 2.3), and 45% is a plausible and acceptable figure. The latter is just a supposition because the value has been obtained from an initial and partial analysis, and is therefore not an official government figure. Moreover, it is a figure drawn from the entire island and only from members of the THTA, which are not that many in the north-eastern region. This means that there is no data on the occupancy rate specifically for the study site and that an important proportion of data is in fact not captured. However, in the absence of alternatives this value has been taken as adequate approximation, also because it is supported

by the information obtained during interviews. In fact, the average occupancy rate of the accommodations belonging to those respondents who were able to provide an accurate value (9 out of 17) is 42%. Going further, it has to be mentioned that there are uncertainties about the average night price of a rental unit and about the number of existing properties in north-east Tobago (and consequently the number of rental units). Starting with the latter, since many accommodations do not have a website and some do not advertise at all (e.g., in social networks or online marketplaces such as Airbnb), it is likely that a few were not traced and remained unknown to the researcher. Therefore, it is possible that the list of properties on which the above calculation is based is non-comprehensive. Concerning the mean cost of a rental unit (132 USD night⁻¹), it has to be considered as an approximation for several reasons. Firstly, the prices used to calculate it are not fixed, but are updated from time to time. Secondly, some of the tariffs were originally in GBP, TTD or EUR, and the exchange rate to USD fluctuates (the currency conversion is dated April 2024). Next, while many accommodations had a single price difference between high and low season, in some rental units the cost varied on an almost monthly basis, and others had the same price throughout the year. Wherever possible, the (average) high season price was used in the calculation. The rationale for this choice is that it was considered more informative than an average between the high and low season tariff, as the booking rate is much higher during high season. Clearly, the most expensive accommodations of the top-tier properties and the most expensive villas raise the regional average considerably (price range: 30 – 708 USD night⁻¹), but it is not certain that they have the same occupancy rate as cheaper options. However, once again, in the absence of disaggregated data this was the best possible computation.

Continuing with yachts using the ERIC moorings in Charlotteville, it must first be said that the price of their utilisation depends on vessel length and duration of stay. It was decided to employ an average price of 10 USD night⁻¹ per yacht for the computation. Data collected by ERIC in the first five months of 2024 provides an average of 3.7 yachts day⁻¹ using these paid moorings (personal communication). Assuming that this value is also representative of the remaining months of the year, it was multiplied by 10 USD night⁻¹ and by 365, yielding 13'505 USD year⁻¹ (gross) (equivalent to 91'621 TTD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024).

Such revenue could increase by almost three times if the usage of moorings was made compulsory, as ERIC data indicates that more than 10 yachts were anchored daily and 15 moorings are available in total. Since that is currently not the case, yachties prefer to anchor on their own in order not to pay the user fee. In order to capitalise more on the moorings, a solution is being worked on at the time of writing this thesis to make their use mandatory.

As for science tourism, the main income is brought in by the educational expeditions that some universities make to ERIC. These visits lead to a gross revenue of about 50'000 USD year⁻¹

(personal communication; equivalent to 339'213 TTD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024).

Adding up all the individual components, the value of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago is estimated at 35'768'907 TTD year⁻¹, equivalent to 5'272'337 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024.

As already pointed out, this remains an approximation. It is heavily affected by the data-deficient environment and certainly carries a series of inaccuracies (e.g., it is based on gross incomes), but in the absence of other data it was the only feasible approach to achieve the objectives of the dissertation. Moreover, as in the case of fisheries, the assessment does not perfectly reflect the value of the entire tourism sector in north-east Tobago because it does not take into account some sources of revenue. First of all, catering was not considered in the analysis for the reasons given in section 2.3. In order not to completely neglect its (most likely significant) contribution to the Blue Economy, the challenges associated with its investigation could have been partially overcome by trying to estimate the daily catering expenditure of tourists and multiplying this value by their number. However, this is impossible without figures on the number of people accessing the NETMABR. Secondly, some fishermen also offer minor tourist services. For instance, on Sundays and public holidays they take tourists from Charlotteville to Pirate's Bay (located two minutes away by boat). Due to its somewhat casual nature, this business has not been included. Finally, further income generated via supermarket spending, car rental and taxi services has not been taken into account either, as their analysis was not feasible given the time and resources available for this research.

3.2.6| Multifaceted potential to improve the tourism sector in north-east Tobago

In sections 3.2.2, 3.2.3 and 3.2.4 the major challenges to the development of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago identified by this study were presented. To summarise, they are: scarcity of direct flights, (perceived) poor marketing of the island, no brand awareness and inadequate promotion of the NETMABR, underdeveloped tourist sites, as well as lack of training, cooperation among stakeholders, standards in hospitality and catering, and of product development in general. These issues have been presented along with a discussion on possible solutions. Thus, a great potential for tourism lies in addressing these barriers to development, perhaps by following the recommendations provided here. But there is much more. There are certain tourism niches, activities and services that to date are completely untapped, and others that are only minimally capitalised on. Due to time constraints they cannot be analysed here. However, in order not to completely overlook this important aspect, an overview of further tourism opportunities in north-east Tobago is proposed in the Appendix (see section 6.5), to provide at least an idea of their vastness and suggest future improvements to the sector.

This study concludes that tourism in north-east Tobago has vast potential, mainly in the natural, cultural, and educational / scientific spheres. This is extremely relevant because tourism can be a core driver of economic development in SIDS (Puig-Cabrera and Foronda-Robles, 2019). It has the capacity to advance Tobago's economy, not only in the sense of bringing more revenue to the island, but also to partially reallocate the workforce. Currently, residents are highly dependent on state-sponsored unemployment relief programs and on governmental employment (Moses-Wothke et al., 2021). In 2022, the share of the labour force employed in the public sector stood at 55% (THA, 2023), an exceptionally high figure. If fully developed, tourism in the NETMABR could bring benefits to local communities, for instance by creating income and many additional jobs, and also to the THA by taking a good portion of the workload off the local government. Clearly this will take time and effort to materialise since the tourism sector is still very immature and lagging behind other Caribbean destinations. Looking on the bright side, this carries a considerable advantage: Tobago can learn from its neighbours' experiences. At the same time, the island can also look back to its past, when tourism was much more successful than today. Future research could investigate what conditions favoured it between the 1990s and early 2000s and what lessons can be learned from its heyday. By following these recommendations, development in Tobago can take place avoiding its past mistakes and following its own best practices (e.g., what to repeat and re-establish), as well as the more recent ones of other countries, thus enabling tourism to flourish in a sustainable way. In this respect, it is also crucial to give appropriate consideration to the concept of carrying capacity, which becomes particularly important when envisaging an increase in tourism to minimise adverse effects. This topic is examined in more detail in the following chapter (see section 3.3.3).

3.3| Management in the context of north-east Tobago

3.3.1| Background

Management is a critical, cross-cutting topic in fisheries and tourism, and is thus discussed on its own below.

Starting with fisheries, although 17 interviewees spoke about the overfishing and fish size reduction by local fisherfolk, and/or about the negative impacts exerted by the use of certain types of fishing gears (i.e., fish pots, beach seines and cast nets), most study participants were confident that residents are not overexploiting marine resources. Although it is true that the impact on fish stocks in north-east Tobago goes beyond that of local artisanal fishers, given the likely strong influence of fishing vessels from Venezuela, Barbados and Trinidad (see 3.1.4), the role of the former cannot be excluded either. The number of pirogues has increased over time, and in the absence (or non-enforcement) of restrictions fisherfolk have always fished as much as possible without ever setting

limits and worrying about preventing the catch of or releasing juvenile and premature individuals. Notwithstanding the limited capacity of local boats, it is conceivable that these practices, repeated habitually and over a long period of time, have put fish populations under severe pressure. Furthermore, it has been shown that FADs can have negative consequences on fish stocks, especially if fishing effort is not regulated (e.g., Taquet, 2013; Cabral et al., 2014).

Considering tourism, the number of visitors in north-east Tobago is currently low. This is why it is assumed that the negative effects of this sector are to date limited (Moses-Wothke et al., 2021). Even if no assessment has actually been conducted, it is very likely that no tourist site in the NETMABR has yet reached its carrying capacity or crossed the limit of acceptable change. In terms of environmental impacts, this paints a much better picture for the tourism sector than for the fisheries. While for the latter it is imperative to take action as soon as possible to improve the status quo, for the former it is more a matter of forward-looking management in view of a prospective and desired future increase in tourism (cf. 3.2).

3.3.2| Proposed interventions for the fisheries sector

With regard to fishing, it seems indispensable to put measures in place to control the level of resource extraction. Management can reduce fishing pressure and rebuild stocks, and is therefore essential to ensure sustainable catches (e.g., Hilborn and Ovando, 2014; Hilborn et al., 2020; Gebremedhin et al., 2021). In north-east Tobago it would help to prevent the collapse of the fisheries, which could happen if business as usual continues, given the results presented in the first part of section 3.1.2.

A first feasible management action that could be introduced is a fishery closure during the reproductive season of selected species. Spawning closures are widespread, both in terms of target species and location around the world (Russel et al., 2011; van Overzee and Rijnsdorp, 2015). The review conducted by van Overzee and Rijnsdorp (2015) suggests that, for example, they can be beneficial if they reduce the fishing mortality of large and old spawners and the risk of overexploitation of species forming large aggregations. The seasonal protection of spawning aggregations through fishing bans has proven to be successful in many cases (e.g., Nemeth, 2005; Whaylen, 2007; Luckhurst and Trott, 2009). Clearly, these measures require precise knowledge on timing and location of reproduction, which is why ad-hoc data collection in north-east Tobago is recommended before considering implementation. Research could initially focus on snappers (Lutjanidae) and groupers (Serranidae), but attention should also be paid to the Caribbean spiny lobster (*Panulirus argus*), for which fishing closures should be established during the egg-bearing period (Goñi and Latrouite, 2005; Sundelöf et al., 2015). Research could be conducted involving local NGOs, whose support could also be sought to help maintain the seasonal moratorium through public education, following a successful Bahamian experience (Sadovy de Mitcheson et al., 2013). Fishing prohibitions during spawning periods could be further effectively strengthened by combining

them with bans on the sale of managed species (Russel et al., 2011; Sadovy de Mitcheson et al., 2013). In fact, enforcement is crucial in this domain, as in its absence closures can be ineffective and the decline of fish populations continues (Eristhee et al. 2006; Gibson et al. 2007; Heyman and Kjerfve, 2008).

Other common management measures are gear and mesh size restrictions. Fishing gear restrictions have been proposed as a powerful tool to increase resilience of marine ecosystems and restore or balance the fisheries (McClanahan and Cinner, 2008; Cinner et al., 2009). The gears used in north-east Tobago that require consideration in that sense are mainly gill- and drift nets, fish pots and beach seines. The former are sometimes associated with the catch of non-target and endangered species, such as turtles, and if the mesh size is small, also of many juvenile fish (Osuka et al., 2021; FAO, 2024a). Traps are highly unselective (e.g., Hawkins et al., 2007), and beach seines disturb breeding activities, often lead to the capture of immature individuals, and strongly damage corals (Mangi and Roberts, 2006; FAO, 2024b). Restrictions on these non-selective and detrimental gears are therefore valid options for the recovery of fish biomass (Campbell et al., 2018). For instance, beach seine exclusions and a broader prohibition of the use of nets (including seine- and gillnets) have been successful in certain locations along the Kenyan coast and Indonesia, respectively (McClanahan, 2010; Campbell et al., 2012). If a total ban proves inappropriate, a less drastic possibility is to manage the use of certain gears spatially and/or temporally (Pomeroy, 2012; Edwin et al., 2020; Vieira et al., 2020). Another solution is to regulate the mesh size. Gill- and drift nets, pots, and beach seines are fishing gears that are perfectly suited for a mesh size intervention, which is a strategy to reduce juvenile and bycatch mortality as larger mesh sizes increase escape chances for smaller juvenile and non-target fish (MacLennan, 1992). Increasing the minimum mesh size is a management measure that has been proposed by numerous scholars (e.g., Broadhurst et al., 2007; Hawkins et al., 2007; Pope, 2009; Hicks and McClanahan, 2012; Akel and Philips, 2014). In the specific case of traps, in addition to eliminating or reducing the use of those with small mesh size (McClanahan and Mangi, 2004), it is also recommended to equip them with an escape panel. This mechanism significantly reduces mortality from ghost fishing (Rencehn et al., 2014), which is why legislation in Barbados imposes the use of traps with escape vents of approved size and design (Salas et al., 2011). A further way to improve their sustainability, and in particular to further reduce the risk of ghost fishing, is to use a biodegradable material for part of the trap (FAO, 2024c). This type of regulation is in force in the British Virgin Islands, and both the escape panels and the naturally-degrading materials are used in Antigua and Barbuda, where even the use of corrosion-resistant wire is prohibited (Lovell, 2023). Trinidad and Tobago could take these best practices of some of its Caribbean neighbours as an example and develop similar policies.

It has been found that artisanal fishers are generally more supportive of gear interventions (such as those discussed above) than other types of management (McClanahan et al., 2005; McClanahan and Abunge, 2018), but it still has to be considered that such regulations have economic implications

for fisherfolk. In Tobago, for instance, they may need to invest in new nets and traps that comply with the regulated mesh size, which can be a considerable burden since interviewees reported the high costs of fishing gear and many fishermen operate with limited financial resources. Moreover, since Tobagonian fishers catch many smaller juvenile fish, larger mesh sizes can decrease their catches in the short term, thereby impacting their income (Mahon and Hunte, 2001; Tschernij et al., 2004). Although the long-term benefits can offset the initial losses and investments (Sary et al., 1997; Heikinheimo et al., 2006), these can be significant obstacles for many fishermen before such benefits materialise. In this context, government support is therefore crucial. Subsidies could be provided for the transition to the new fishing gear, similar to those the THA has already introduced for the purchase of fishing vessels and engines. Alternatively, the government could seek the support of international funding agencies to distribute nets and traps with appropriate mesh sizes directly to fisherfolk (Kim et al., 2014). The situation could be simpler with regard to equipping fish pots with escape gaps and biodegradable panels, since they are relatively inexpensive (Bilkovic et al., 2012; Mbaru and McClanahan, 2013). Furthermore, there is no evidence that the fishing performance of traps with these modifications is impaired (Bilkovic et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2014). It is possible that fisherfolk's catches will be reduced in the short term as smaller juveniles can escape, but studies from the Caribbean claim that traps equipped with appropriately-sized escape vents do not reduce fisher's revenues, while making this type of fishing more sustainable (Munro et al., 2003; Johnson, 2010; Gomes et al., 2014). Other considerations for evaluating the feasibility of management measures concerning the installation of naturally-degrading and escape panels for fish pots are their maintenance and frequency of repair and replacement. No information was found on this in the specific case of traps, which is why it would be important to investigate such aspects before planning implementation.

An additional practicable intervention for fisheries management is the introduction of size limit regulations. These are very common in Latin America and the Caribbean (Salas et al., 2007) and are generally based on a minimum legal size, defined as the smallest size at which a species can be legally retained if caught (Hill, 1992 as cited by Busilacchi et al., 2012). Size-based management has been recommended in many cases (e.g., Freire and García-Allut, 2000; Rosales et al., 2017; Ben-Hasan et al., 2021; Prince et al., 2021), as it helps to avoid the landing of undersized and immature individuals and therefore avoid growth and recruitment overfishing (e.g., Alonso-Fernández et al., 2021). Models indicate that if appropriate size restrictions are rigorously enforced, fish biomass and catches increase substantially (Ben-Hasan et al., 2021). A first minimum landing size strategy is to use the length at maturity as a reference, in order to allow fish to spawn at least once (Myers and Mertz, 1998). The alternative is based on the fact that ideally, length at first capture should be beyond length at maturity (Froese, 2004), in order to catch fish at an optimum size for population growth (Froese et al., 2008). In any case, it is of paramount importance that management actions are aligned with the available biological knowledge of target species, which is not always the

case (Alonso-Fernández et al., 2021). Many of the most avant-garde countries in terms of fisheries management started with minimum size regulations (Prince et al., 2021), which is why their implementation is recommended in north-east Tobago. Once again, such measures have to be carefully planned, as they can lead to costs for fisherfolk. First of all, minimum size limits can initially reduce catches (Bohnsack, 2000) and consequently fishers' earnings, especially if many smaller juvenile fish are usually harvested, as is the case in north-east Tobago. This is a considerable hindrance, as one interviewee pointed out:

“This [size-based management] would face strong opposition. Many fellows rely on catching small fish to pay back gas so they would never throw ‘em back. But at the same time fish is not as abundant as it used to be, so it’s time to think about management.”
[Interviewee 10]

In addition, size regulations can result in an increase in fishing effort (Harley et al., 2000; Newman and Hoff, 2000), which in turn can raise operational costs such as fuel (it may be necessary to travel longer to catch fish that meet the regulations), which this study found to be already high in the NETMABR (see 3.1.5 and 6.3). For these reasons, as with gear and mesh size restrictions, it may be necessary to mitigate the negative impacts on fisherfolk until fish populations recover. Some kind of compensation for short-term income losses could be considered, but other strategies should be devised in conjunction with the fishing communities.

Another measure to be introduced could be aimed at FADs governance. The possibility of bringing them closer to shore has been widely discussed above, but there is more. There are concerns that FADs can lead to the overexploitation of pelagic species that aggregate around them (e.g., Karama and Matsushita, 2019). Without fishing effort regulations, FADs can thus lead to the decline of these populations (Taquet, 2013; Cabral et al., 2014). It is therefore suggested to conduct research with the purpose of exploring the situation in north-east Tobago and, should it prove necessary, establish a management system for FADs.

These are just some of the potential ways to manage the artisanal fisheries in the NETMABR. Investigating their feasibility in the local context is crucial, as will be careful implementation and ensuring that fisherfolk's livelihoods are safeguarded during the potential transition. The management actions presented in this section have been proposed because they were all first suggested by study participants. During interviews, 10 fishermen mentioned the need for one or more of these interventions to address the alarming catch decrease and allow fish populations to recover. All ten have also identified bad fishing practices (e.g., overfishing) as causes of the catch decline (see 3.1.2), and most of them (8 out of 10) had been fishing for 30 to 50 years. It is therefore possible that these respondents recognised the importance of management through experience, as some of them claimed to have done in recognising certain fishing practices as detrimental. However, two of these interviewees were somewhat sceptical about the viability of the management measures, pointing precisely to the aforementioned economic problems they could pose for fishers, many of

whom already have financial difficulties. These accounts, together with information obtained from key informants, suggest that (without proper planning and support) most fisherfolk could resist management. This seems to confirm the findings of Flower (2011), who reported that most of his respondents in north-east Tobago were against any management of their fishing. Such attitude can be explained considering the cultural heritage of independence and freedom associated with the ocean. In post-slavery times, the exploitation of marine resources was one of the few activities that freed people could engage in away from formerly slave-owning estate owners, and this sense of liberty has been strongly valued and deeply ingrained in locals ever since (ERIC, 2021a). However, there is a fundamental difference between the present study and that of Flower: whereas the examination of perceptions towards management was one of the objectives of his research, here, no specific question was ever asked in that regard. Thus, the interviewees who mentioned the establishment of regulations did so on their own initiative and as a hope for the improvement of the fisheries in north-east Tobago. Given these results and the possible exacerbation of the decline in catches, it cannot be ruled out that attitudes towards management have changed over the past 12-13 years. Investigating this aspect through future research is deemed crucial because a positive outcome could potentially remove one of the obstacles to the governance of the sector. What the present work has found bodes well, as it is now known that there is already a group of people who believe in the importance of sustainable management practices. By allowing fish populations to recover, these would help secure the numerous livelihoods dependent on marine resources. Furthermore, with healthier stocks and a more profitable and sustainable artisanal fisheries, it is possible that young people may return to the profession and that this will no longer be a secondary occupation. In fact, in addition to what was noted above about young people not getting into the industry, it must be said that almost all fisherfolk currently have a main job other than fishing. This was the case for 87% of interviewed fishermen (40 out of 46), the vast majority of whom worked for the THA. While fishing is now considered an uncertain livelihood, these jobs provide them with a constant income and a pension, hence offering security. However, the strong reliance on professions within the THA might turn out to be a risk in the long run, for instance if there were to be redundancies due to state cutbacks (Flower, 2011). In conclusion, a further benefit of improved artisanal fisheries in north-east Tobago is the likely reduction of a potentially risky dependence on public sector employment.

3.3.3| Proposed interventions for the tourism sector

The situation regarding tourism governance can be seen as relatively simpler, given that the number of people travelling to the NETMABR is rather limited. Reefs (as well as forests) have not reached their carrying capacity, and waste production and pressure on commodities (e.g., fish, fruits and vegetables) are still low, as it has been estimated that the average number of visitors at a given time is less than 3% of the total population of the study site (Moses-Wothke et al., 2021). Therefore,

management is not needed to urgently alter the status quo as in the case of the fisheries sector. Nevertheless, given the enormous potential of tourism in north-east Tobago and the concrete possibility and outlook that it will increase in the near future, it is necessary to start developing strategies already now. This is the only way to keep the destination pristine and grow tourism in a sustainable manner. Moreover, minimising right from the start the threat that tourism poses to marine ecosystems is vital to its profitability (Failler et al., 2015).

During semi-structured interviews, tourism stakeholders referred less frequently than fisherfolk to the need for management and mentioned fewer measures. Some (5 out of 51) wished for the establishment of a protected area in Speyside to preserve its reefs and associated species. The focus on this part of Tobago can be explained considering that in Speyside there are some of the island's most famous dive sites, and that among tourism stakeholders it was almost exclusively the tour and dive operators who showed environmental awareness and sensitivity, and half of these interviewees (8 out of 16) were located in Speyside itself. The topic of an MPA in north-east Tobago will be addressed later in the chapter; for now, the most important overall management tool in the context of tourism in the Biosphere Reserve is presented.

As soon as operational, TOBIMA should be in charge of a study to assess the carrying capacity for Little Tobago and the most popular or sensitive dive and snorkel sites, so as to be ready to limit the number of tourists when it becomes necessary (ERIC, 2021a; ERIC, 2021b). The concept of carrying capacity is extremely important in planning the development of a destination and managing tourism (Jovicic and Dragin, 2008), as it is generally defined as the "number of visitors an area can sustain without degrading natural resources and visitor experiences" (Prato, 2001, p. 2). Although different methods for its assessment exist (see for example Santos and Brilha, 2023 for a review), calculating the carrying capacity is very complex due to its dynamic nature and because it is not exclusively a function of the number of tourists, but is influenced by several other parameters such as visitors' activities, behaviour, and distribution (Simon et al., 2004; Salerno et al., 2013). According to Salerno et al. (2013), the difficulty in determining suitable limits on tourism growth has led some scholars to shift the focus from the question "how many is too many?" to "what are the desirable, appropriate or acceptable conditions for [...] [a certain] tourism destination?" (Lindberg et al., 1997, p. 3; McCool and Lime, 2001, p. 14). From this perspective, what underlies carrying capacity is the need to define a limit to tourism activities that is in line with the targets of local management (Coccosis and Mexa, 2017). So, in any case, the concept is considerably relevant for estimating upper thresholds and for setting an exploitation optimum accordingly (Leka et al., 2022). In north-east Tobago, the management of visitor flows in such informed manner will allow to pursue an environmentally sustainable tourism development and can thus contribute to the branding of the Biosphere Reserve as an eco-tourism destination.

Considering the niche markets in the area, one deserves special attention from a management point of view: recreational spearfishing. In Tobago, spearfishing with scuba gear is permitted and not

regulated at all. It is practiced mainly by Trinidadians, but also by some international tourists and locals. The adverse effects of spearfishing on reef fishes have been extensively described (e.g., Sadovy et al., 2003; Coll et al., 2004; Young et al., 2014). It can have considerable impacts on population dynamics and structure, especially of those species that belong to higher trophic levels and/or that are particularly vulnerable because long-lived, slow-growing and with low reproductive potential (Jouvenel and Pollard, 2001; Lloret et al., 2008). Moreover, it has been demonstrated that spearfishing can shift the composition of reef fishes from large carnivore and omnivore species to herbivores and smaller omnivores (Godoy et al., 2010). This is exactly what happened in Tobago, where the activity has led to a decrease in mesopredators (mainly groupers and snappers) at specific reefs. Here, however, it has also caused a decrease in parrotfish (locally sold as ‘rock fish’), resulting in an even greater negative impact on the ecosystem (ERIC, 2021a). All of this creates discontent among local tour operators, who strongly rely on reef health for their business. To address the problems caused by scuba spearfishing, many authors advocate a strong restriction or, even better, a ban on the use of diving gear while spearfishing (Nevill, 2005; Cinner et al., 2009; Godoy et al., 2010; Lindfield et al., 2014), a position also taken by some study participants. Noteworthy, the complete ban of scuba spearfishing combined with rigorous enforcement has been presented by the FAO as the “single most important spearfishing management measure” (Gillet and Moy, 2006, p. 74). Given that the coral reef ecosystem is the cornerstone of the Blue Economy tourism in north-east Tobago, the recommendations of this thesis are aligned with those just outlined. Banning the use of diving gear while spearfishing should be given serious consideration and hopefully implemented. If this proved unfeasible, it would at least be necessary to regulate the niche market at issue. So, as a viable alternative it has been proposed to ban spearfishing at 65% of the reefs in the NETMABR and to introduce a certification and licensing scheme (ERIC, 2021a). The former should not apply to the hunting of the invasive lionfish (*Pterois volitans*), so as to redirect spearfishing effort towards this ecologically detrimental marine species (see also Appendix, section 6.5, for a lionfish-related tourism opportunity). Further interventions could concern a closed season for some species and size and bag limits. If effectively enforced, such measures would make spearfishing much more sustainable and allow operators to capitalise on it, since certifications and licenses will be offered to tourists for a fee. Hence, this management option also holds potential to increase the revenue of the tourism sector.

3.3.4| The recipe for a successful management

The importance of applying efficiently the proposed interventions has been repeatedly emphasised in the previous sections, as weak enforcement has been shown to undermine the benefits even of appropriate management strategies (Ben-Hasan and Daliri, 2023). Enforcement is thus key to an effective natural resource management (Ostrom, 1990). Its outcomes also depend heavily on people’s compliance with the rules, which is indeed essential for marine conservation (Keane et al.,

2008; Arias et al., 2015; Cinner et al., 2016). Rohe et al. (2017) claim that understanding the drivers of (non-) compliance in a certain context is essential to inform management. Of the various factors that have been identified in the literature as influencing compliance, it is argued that two in particular are extremely relevant in the setting of north-east Tobago. The first one is the perceived legitimacy of regulations (Sutinen and Kuperan, 1999; Jentoft, 2000; Keane et al., 2008; Jagers et al., 2012), as resource users are more inclined to comply with the rules if they see these as legitimate (De Vos and Van Tatenhove, 2011). The second factor is the efficacy of sanctions, which influences the decision to obey the rules or not (Jackson et al., 2012). Strong deterrents are also important because people partly base this latter choice on the (perceived) compliance of others (Pomeroy et al., 2015; Rohe et al., 2017). A system of graduated sanctions, where penalties increase with repeat offences and the severity of offences (Bellanger et al., 2019), should be implemented in the NETMABR. This approach provides a compelling reason to comply (Sutinen et al., 2006), and to benefit fully from it, the sanctions have to be strictly executed and made widely known among the public, so as to raise the perception of the risk posed by breaking the rules. Then, to address the first driver of non-compliance it is imperative to ensure that local communities perceive the management measures as legitimate. Several possibilities exist to try to achieve this; some of them are proposed and discussed below.

A first key to success could be to grow management over time, as for countries seeking to develop management it has been recommended to start with simple interventions, and only afterwards gradually introduce new ones (Prince and Hordyk, 2018). This was also suggested by key informants and explains why restrictions such as permanent closures and catch limits for artisanal fisherfolk have not been proposed in the present dissertation: being very restraining they are extremely likely to encounter strong resistance at this stage. The expansion of management through time should be coupled with the progressive building up of the trust of local communities. Trust has been recognised as a prerequisite for legitimacy, capable of boosting voluntary rules' acceptance and compliance (Grafton 2005; Stern, 2008; Turner et al., 2016; Silva et al., 2021). Matera (2016) found trust in local government in particular to be the variable that most affected adherence to marine conservation programs. However, interviews and informal conversations conducted during fieldwork for this study revealed that the level of faith in public institutions is extremely low in north-east Tobago. So, initially and at least until that placed in the THA rises, trust in management has to be built in other ways. In the case of fisheries, for example, a feasible strategy implies giving fisherfolk time to get used to the new situation – following the introduction of a management system, the ocean will no longer be completely free for the first time in Tobago – and fish populations the opportunity to recover a little. In this way, people can conceivably notice the progress the first simple limitations will have led to before even starting a discussion about implementing additional, more restrictive regulations. Detectable increases in catch abundance and/or size could positively influence their attitudes towards the validity of the interventions. If, instead, the restoration of fish biomass and effects on

catches were to be imperceptible to fishers, it would be crucial to show them the results of scientific investigations, as a perceived lack of ecological effectiveness has been linked with non-compliance (Owusu et al., 2023). Clearly, to do that it will be necessary to conduct thorough research prior to the establishment of the first management practices, in order to produce a baseline that can then be compared with the findings of future studies, and then to communicate this simply and effectively. This leads to the second key tool likely to increase the perceived legitimacy of management and therefore the likelihood of its success: education and outreach.

In addition to divulging over time the positive outcomes that conservation interventions will have led to in order to foster trust in them, outreach activities will be crucial prior to the adoption of any governance action. In fact, if Tobagonians fully understood the motivations behind management (and the risks associated with its absence) they would probably be more apt to accept and comply with it. Raising public awareness and conducting education activities pertaining to the environment has been advocated by many scholars, both with regard to fisheries (Akankali et al., 2011; Nunoo et al., 2015; de Lara and Corral, 2017; Mudzakir et al., 2024) and tourism (Fotiou et al., 2002; Carr et al., 2016; Walker, 2017 as cited in Walker et al., 2021). In the specific case of Tobago, it is argued that the more residents realise that their income depends directly or indirectly on thriving natural ecosystems, the more likely they are to preserve these (Moses-Wothke et al., 2021). Informing locals first of all with the aim of increasing environmental awareness and their understanding of sustainability is thus deemed central, as some interviewees also stressed. At this point, instructing people on what management is and why it is necessary (e.g., current fisheries harvest trends are not sustainable, tourist sites have to be protected in view of an increase in tourism) should be easier and at the same time more effective. Given the importance of education in supporting management (Filous et al., 2021; Truchet et al., 2022), meticulous attention will have to be paid to how it is arranged: each outreach effort should follow the advices of local experts, be intelligible, locally meaningful, and carefully planned with the target audience in mind. For example, in the case of fisherfolk, it will be crucial to emphasise that management is not an end in itself because they will directly benefit from the recovery of fish stocks, and therefore any negative impact of the introduction of restrictions will likely be temporary and largely outweighed by the medium- and long-term benefits. In the case of tour and dive operators, there will be a need to raise awareness about the fact that maintaining healthy ecosystems is critical to tourism in Tobago. For this reason, any possible limitation on the number of visitors at certain sites is introduced to prevent their degradation and consequently to ensure sustainable tourism in the long run, ultimately benefitting precisely those stakeholders.

The last and perhaps most important tool discussed here that can help ensure that residents will perceive rules as legitimate, is co-management. This has spread and has been widely adopted around the world in the past decades (e.g., FAO, 2016a), arising from the recognition that local communities should have some power over decisions affecting the resources on which their

livelihoods are based (WCED, 1987; Noble, 2000). Co-management promotes the joint management of natural resources by their users and the respective local and/or national governments, who therefore share responsibility for it (Sen and Nielsen, 1996; Berkes, 2009). If effectively implemented, it allows all stakeholders to actively and equally participate in decision-making, enhancing legitimacy of regulatory systems, and thus compliance (Jentoft, 1998; Jentoft, 2000; Pomeroy, 2001; Evans, 2011; Van Tatenhove, 2013; Owusu et al., 2023). At the same time, state guidance and support remain essential, for instance because communities do not always have the capacity to impose sanctions on transgressors (Gelcich et al., 2009; Ferse et al., 2010). In the case of fisheries, co-management has been shown to be successful in achieving both social and ecological goals, as it has positive effects on fishers' income, abundance of target species, and in general on the sustainability of small-scale fisheries (Evans, 2011; Gutiérrez et al., 2011; Cinner et al., 2012; d'Armengol et al., 2018). Moreover, this model of governance makes fisherfolk less likely to accept non-compliance from others (Jagers et al., 2012). Finally, a general advantage of co-management is that it can be more economical than centralised regimes: as there is greater adherence to the rules, monitoring and enforcement costs (i.e., the implementation costs that will have to be borne enduringly) are lower (Pomeroy, 2001; Kuperan et al., 2008).

A co-management system in Tobago would require reforming completely the way natural resources are currently administered. The political structure of the island still partly reflects that of its colonial ruler, where everything was (and pretty much is) orchestrated from the very top of the government, and therefore has historically neglected the value and rights of civil society inclusion (Moses-Wothke et al., 2021). A top-down approach, where the government decides and acts unilaterally, has been proven repeatedly to be inadequate, especially in the case of (small-scale) fisheries. In such centralised regimes, exclusion of fishers and lack of consultation jeopardise the legitimacy of management measures and consequently often lead to deep dissatisfaction and non-compliance (OECD, 1997 as cited by Cochrane, 2000; Reis and D'Incao, 2000; Begossi, 2010; Arceo et al., 2013; Rohe et al., 2017). In fact, in the words of Ostrom et al. (1999, p. 4), if regulations are dictated without consulting local stakeholders, they "may engage in a game of 'cops and robbers' with outside authorities". In Tobago, fisherfolk are either not or inadequately consulted, and their resentment was evident during semi-structured interviews and informal conversations. Exactly the same is true for tourism operators. Smith and Jordan (2021) have shown that most of their study participants in Castara were unhappy because of the lack of community consultation, and that the top-down management has negative effects even on the relationship between CSOs and the THA. The problems caused by the hierarchical model of governance are therefore already evident, and would only be exacerbated by the introduction of restrictions imposed from the outside. In Tobago there is a need to shed the legacy of colonial centralisation and initiate a transition from the current system to co-management with transparent and equitable consultation and participation of local stakeholders. Following the recommendation of Rohe et al. (2017), both should occur regularly to

renegotiate arrangements if appropriate. Furthermore, the combination with learning by doing would enable the implementation of an adaptive co-management that can respond rapidly to social and environmental changes (e.g., Berkes, 2009; McCay et al., 2014). This is the ideal solution to aim for in the NETMABR.

With TOBIMA, the platform for such a participatory management approach has already been devised. On one hand it is envisaged to implement the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere Programme in Tobago as well as specific management activities, and on the other it has been designed as a multi-sectoral organisation. It will involve representatives of the government, civil society (e.g., environmental NGOs), and private sector (e.g., fisheries and tourism stakeholders), and will facilitate communication between these. Therefore, TOBIMA provides an excellent enabling environment for the (adaptive) co-management recommended here.

3.3.5| The North-East Tobago Marine Protected Area

The management interventions recommended earlier in the chapter, once examined, discussed and defined together and in agreement with local stakeholders, could be introduced in the context of the North-East Tobago MPA (see Fig. 2). All attractions for the Blue Economy tourism fall within the proposed MPA, which would encompass all the reefs of north-east Tobago (hence, all the important snorkelling, diving and spearfishing sites), Little Tobago and St. Giles Islet Complex (both are IBAs). Yet, not all artisanal fishing activities take place within what would be the boundaries of the North-East Tobago MPA. It is planned to extend from the shore up to 6 nautical miles (6.9 miles) offshore, which delimits the marine space administered by the THA (ERIC, 2019), while study results revealed that only 35% of interviewees definitely fish within this range. This implies that the suggested measures to manage the fisheries (see 3.3.2) should also be implemented beyond the borders of the MPA to address the challenges the sector is facing and to aim for sustainability. In turn, this means that the establishment of the North-East Tobago MPA, at least initially (following the principle of growing management and trust over time), would have no impact on fisherfolk other than that of the overall management practices, and that if appropriately included and consulted they might not oppose. Investigating the possibility of an MPA in Speyside, Flower (2011) found a majority of positive opinions and that only a very few people were really against it, as many fisherfolk saw the potential benefits for their business as well as for the local tourism. Exploring current attitudes is a goal for future research.

North-east Tobago is an ideal location for an MPA because of its ecological value and the absence of activities that could compromise conservation objectives (ERIC, 2019). It is only used for artisanal fishing and recreation; there are no commercial ports, significant shipping routes, hydrocarbon extracting operations or major economic interests in general within its planned boundaries. Despite these optimal prerequisites for long-term conservation and the fact that the management plan for the North-East Tobago MPA has already been developed, the project has been in deadlock since 2019.

Therefore, the resumption of the process that can lead to its implementation should be given high priority. The main recommendation here is that some time after (ideally a few years) the introduction of the MPA, so as to begin to show stakeholders the positive ecological effects and thus increase their trust, management could be expanded by establishing stricter measures within it, such as permanent fishing closures in the most popular (for snorkelers and divers) and sensitive reefs. Under this condition (presence of no-take zones), it has been demonstrated that MPAs can increase fish abundance, size and biomass (García-Charton et al., 2004; Russ et al., 2004; Alcalá et al., 2005; Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008; La Mesa et al., 2011; Rolim et al., 2019; see also the reviews of García-Charton et al., 2008 and Fenberg et al., 2012). These outcomes directly benefit tourism, because in Tobago it is strongly connected to the health of marine ecosystems and visitors would be allowed access to the MPA (subject to carrying capacity), and indirectly also adjacent fisheries. This occurs mainly through two processes: net movement of adults and juveniles beyond reserve boundaries (i.e., spillover effect) and export of propagules – pelagic eggs and larvae – from recovered spawning stocks (i.e., recruitment effect) (Rowley, 1994; Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008; La Mesa et al., 2011; Di Franco et al., 2012; Hackradt et al., 2014; da Silva et al., 2015). Given the opportunity to bring benefits to both tourism and fisheries, the North-East Tobago MPA holds great potential to improve the livelihoods of local communities and sustainable and regenerative Blue Economy in north-east Tobago.

Furthermore, fees for the tourists accessing the MPA should be set in order to make it self-sustaining (at least to some extent). Examples of successful systems can be found all over the world, from Bonaire and the Galápagos to the Philippines, Malaysia and Palau, just to name a few (Lindberg, 2001 as cited by Tongson and Dygico, 2004; Tongson and Dygico, 2004). It is strongly recommended to allocate tourist entrance fees to increase the budget security of the North-East Tobago MPA and therefore to earmark the money for a use within it, as it has been shown that these funds can effectively contribute to financing both management and conservation (Tongson and Dygico, 2004; Terk et al., 2010; Thur, 2010; Kirkbride-Smith et al., 2016; Brown et al., 2023). Transparency in fee collection and use is crucial because tourists are more likely to increase their willingness to pay if they know how their money influences conservation (Leung et al., 2018). In north-east Tobago, to fulfil both these conditions, visitor fees could be paid to TOBIMA, which could also be responsible for the dissemination of the way they are used and (later on) the conservation outcomes they have supported. Lastly, fees can help to prevent negative environmental impacts from excessive numbers of tourists (Alban et al., 2006). This is not yet necessary in the Biosphere Reserve because of the current low number of visitors, but it is part of the forward-looking management vision that has already been recommended to be adopted in the light of an expected and planned tourism intensification.

Every strategy discussed above to increase compliance with natural resource management will have to be meticulously applied to the North-East Tobago MPA. This is paramount because in many cases

the failure of ecological performance has been attributed primarily to non-compliance (e.g., as reviewed by Iacarella et al., 2021). With this in mind, strong deterrents (i.e., graduated sanctions), growing management and trust over time, education and outreach, as well as co-management are of utmost importance. In the latter regard, involvement and consultation of stakeholders should start already during the planning phase, as early and inclusive co-design has been identified as key to the successful establishment of MPAs (Pelletier, 2020). It implies sharing goals and expectations through timely communication (Perea-Munoz et al., 2022), and allows the integration of local needs into management plans (Sena et al., 2023). In addition, in north-east Tobago, co-design could be an effective approach to address the issues of trust and sanctions, and thus more generally the topic of compliance. Such a participatory approach can then develop into an efficient (adaptive) co-management with appropriate stakeholder engagement fostered by TOBIMA once the North-East Tobago MPA has been officially implemented.

To conclude, Trinidad and Tobago is a member of the Global Ocean Alliance, an international initiative aiming to conserve and manage at least 30 percent of the world's ocean by 2030 (UK Government, 2024). By establishing the North-East Tobago MPA, the country would come closer to this pledge.

3.4| Total value of the current Blue Economy in the NETMABR

3.4.1| Value assessment of the shipbuilding and repair sector

Before the total value of the Blue Economy can be calculated, the contribution of shipbuilding and repair has to be considered, as it is the third and last existing Blue Economy sector in north-east Tobago. To estimate its economic value, the annual net income of boat builders was calculated. To do so, the average number of boats they build in a year was multiplied by the corresponding selling price. Since the result would provide the gross income, the cost of the material (e.g., fiberglass resin) was subtracted from it:

$$I = n \cdot p - n \cdot m$$

where:

- I is a boat builder's net income, expressed in TTD per year
- n is the average number of boats that a boat builder builds in a year
- p is the average boat selling price in TTD
- m is the average cost of the material in TTD

To conclude the computation, after the annual net income has been calculated for each boat builder, the values have to be added together to obtain the total annual net income of this group of professionals. As in the case of tourism, there is no need to relate the sum to the total number of these stakeholders in the NETMABR (which had to be done for the fisheries sector). In fact, all relevant data for this calculation has been collected directly, as every boat builder in north-east Tobago has been interviewed. Thus, the assessment below is entirely based on information obtained during semi-structured interviews in response to questions aimed precisely at assessing the economic value of the shipbuilding and repair sector (see Appendix, section 6.1.5 and considerations in 6.3). Its value is estimated at 665'000 TTD year⁻¹, equivalent to 98'021 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024. Yet again, a computation made in this way carries some inaccuracies; *p*, *m* and *n* are assumed to be representative of actual values, but since the price of a boat and the materials used vary according to its size, *p* and *m* are only approximate averages, as is *n*, which is also self-reported and not based on written records. Finally, the assessment does not perfectly reflect the value of the entire shipbuilding and repair sector in north-east Tobago because it does not take into account boat repairing for the reasons given in section 2.3.

3.4.2| Overall value of the Blue Economy

Adding up the worth of all sectors of the Blue Economy, its total current value in north-east Tobago is estimated between 41'685'727 TTD year⁻¹ and 48'688'153 TTD year⁻¹, equivalent to the range 6'144'477 USD year⁻¹ – 7'176'635 USD year⁻¹ for a currency conversion dated April 2024. In the case of fisheries, the figures obtained in the third scenario were used (see 3.1.5). The major contribution is made by tourism, followed by fisheries and finally shipbuilding, which accounts for a very small fraction of the total.

Due to the fact that north-east Tobago is a data-deficient environment, the assessment had to rely almost exclusively on data collected by the researcher. Thus, it is an approximation based on a series of assumptions and is inherently subject to a range of possible errors, as explained in detail in the respective sections (see 3.1.5, 3.2.5, and 3.4.1). There, it is also highlighted that none of the estimates fully captures the value of the Blue Economy sector they refer to, as a number of businesses (most notably third-party fish sales, catering, and boat repair) could not be included considering the time and resources available for this research. Moreover, while the estimates of the fisheries and shipbuilding sectors provide net amounts, that of tourism yields a gross amount; and ideally they should not be added together. Lastly, the rough order of magnitude estimate was used only in the case of fisheries. The rationale is that the value of this sector is believed to be associated with more sources of uncertainty than the others, for which using such a wide range (-25% to 75%) was considered excessive as it would have most likely returned figures too distant from the real ones.

Nevertheless, considering that the present study had to start virtually from scratch, the result achieved is deemed appropriate. The assessment was conducted by investigating all the established Blue Economy sectors in north-east Tobago and many relevant stakeholders were interviewed to accomplish this. Due to this study, the NETMABR is associated with a value that corresponds to the Blue Economy activities that take place within it and that can be taken into account by policy makers and TOBIMA for future discussions and developments.

3.5| Further potential Blue Economy sectors

The value of the Blue Economy in the Biosphere Reserve has the potential to increase enormously in the future. This can materialise in two ways: by focussing on improving the existing industries and by developing new sectors. The two strategies are by no means mutually exclusive, so it is strongly recommended to pursue both simultaneously. The first one has already been extensively discussed in and throughout the previous chapters. It forms the bulk of the dissertation because of its feasibility in and relevance to the local setting, as it concentrates on the established economic activities on which the livelihoods of local communities heavily depend. However, in addition to artisanal fisheries, tourism, and shipbuilding and repair, other sectors are part of the Blue Economy (see Table 1). Three receive great attention worldwide and could be meaningful in the context of north-east Tobago: aquaculture, marine bioprospecting and biotechnology, and marine-based renewable energy. Some of the specific challenges related to the development of these sectors are touched upon below, but since SIDS generally lack technical, technological and financial capacities, regional and global partnerships have been identified as an important tool to enhance them (Bakshi, 2019). In this regard, a promising strategy for Trinidad and Tobago is the collaboration with other Caribbean countries, for example within the Caribbean Community (CARICOM). This is an intergovernmental organisation comprising 15 member states (including Trinidad and Tobago), whose objectives encompass the promotion of economies and collaboration between nations (CARICOM, 2024). This can reduce the overall cost of research and increase the chance of obtaining grants and/or loans from international agencies and banks.

Aquaculture, marine bioprospecting and biotechnology, and marine-based renewable energy all have great potential from an environmental, economic and social point of view, and thus to contribute to the development of a sustainable Blue Economy. Their potential and applicability to the NETMABR varies, but placing attention on and exploring those industries can provide large returns. For the time being, no monetary value can be calculated without speculation, and a detailed analysis is not possible here due to the vastness of each topic and their implications. However, a brief overview is offered below to acknowledge and inform about the existence of those opportunities and to pave the way for future studies.

3.5.1| Aquaculture

Aquaculture has a relatively short and not very successful history in Trinidad and Tobago (UNESCO-IOC and IMA, 2021). According to this report, the system put in place by the central government to facilitate the establishment of the industry in the country failed in 2015, as did trials on shrimp and oyster production in Trinidad. Until recently, a pilot oyster aquaculture project of the ERIC was the only marine aquaculture activity in north-east Tobago, but it also failed and the idea has been abandoned. Aquaculture is therefore currently underdeveloped in the twin-island state and actually non-existent in north-east Tobago, which is why the sector cannot even be considered emerging here. The main factors inhibiting aquaculture development in the NETMABR are probably the absence of proper infrastructures and transportation systems, and the arduous access to technology and materials, which would always have to come from south-west Tobago or more likely even Trinidad. In addition, north-east Tobago does not have the workforce with the technical skills needed for aquaculture, which is why also additional labour force would have to come from outside, at least initially and until locals are sufficiently trained. For all these reasons, it is probable that other places in the country would be chosen as better locations should the central government opt to try supporting the establishment of the aquaculture industry again. Additional problems for local (marine) aquaculture development include larceny risks (ERIC, 2022a) and physical constraints (e.g., low tidal range, while tidal currents are very important to flush ponds and cages). Although those outlined so far are considerable challenges, two aquaculture opportunities are still presented below, with the sole purpose of illustrating them to inform decision making. After all, aquaculture creates employment and can provide a solution to rebuild depleted wild fish stocks by reducing pressure on capture fisheries (Sarker et al., 2018; Alharthi and Hanif, 2020; Manikarachchi, 2022). One possibility that could be considered is offshore aquaculture. It refers to marine production systems located at sites characterised by full exposure to open-ocean elements (e.g., wind, waves, storms and currents), rather than by a specific distance from shore (O'Shea et al., 2019). Many sites are relatively shallow and close to shore (less than 3.5 miles), as the minimum distance from the coast for aquaculture to be considered 'offshore' is generally understood to be around 1.2 miles (Bostock et al., 2010; Froehlich et al., 2017). Offshore aquaculture can help mitigate some of the adverse impacts typical of nearshore and land-based farms. For instance, moving production systems further offshore eliminates the problems related to space and visual impacts, and can significantly reduce disease risks (Bostock et al., 2010). Moreover, modern technologies and proper siting have minimised the effects of individual fish farms on water quality and benthic communities, thus making the operations sustainable (Price et al., 2015; Boyd et al., 2020). In support of this, Welch et al. (2019) have shown that an offshore aquaculture facility that has the right size and location and is efficiently operated has a negligible impact on the environment. A significant exception is the escape of farmed fish, as these events continue to occur (e.g., Kanstad-Hanssen et al., 2023; Singh, 2024). Yet, the likelihood of fish escapes has been reduced by improved

engineering and the implementation of appropriate regulations (Bravo et al., 2023), and the understanding of their genetic consequences has progressed to the extent that models can be run to identify (and potentially manage) the risks (Gunnarsson, 2023).

Another option, this time on land, is lobster aquaculture. In 2017, a pilot project was launched in the British Virgin Islands by the organisation Caribbean Sustainable Fisheries (CSF, 2024). The value of farmed lobsters (i.e., the Caribbean spiny lobster, *Panulirus argus*) is high thanks to the constant excellent quality and continuity of supply of fresh products (UNDP, 2023). According to this report, the pilot facility has received approval for expansion (the size will still be modest for an aquaculture commercial operation), and once upgraded for full-scale production it is anticipated to generate approximately 4 million USD worth of lobsters per year. Moreover, it will create employment and opportunities for capacity building in emerging areas of aquaculture technology. Caribbean Sustainable Fisheries guarantees that the farm is designed to have low environmental footprint and avoid damage to the ecosystems, which would make it more sustainable than other types of aquaculture (CSF, 2024). If this initiative proves successful, it could be an option to consider duplicating in the NETMABR, as it fits both the Biosphere Reserve context (because of its sustainability and fairly small spatial scale) and local culture, basically reviving a tradition. In fact, while the Caribbean spiny lobster was once extremely abundant in north-east Tobago and was exported from Charlotteville mainly to Barbados, it is now much rarer and very expensive.

Both aquaculture opportunities are hindered by the challenges discussed above, but researching ways to overcome these and find feasible solutions remains a possibility. To facilitate this, partnerships with international organisations, universities (e.g., the University of Trinidad and Tobago and University of the West Indies), and companies (as in the case of lobster aquaculture) should be sought, and skills development programs encouraged (Bethel et al., 2021; UNECA, 2023). Finally, it will be necessary to carefully evaluate all potential environmental impacts that the selected form of aquaculture may have, so as to curb them and achieve a sustainable industry (World Bank, 2016; Howard, 2018) that preserves the vulnerable ecosystems of north-east Tobago.

3.5.2| Marine bioprospecting and biotechnology

In the marine environment, organisms are exposed to the most diverse, and sometimes extreme, physical and chemical environmental conditions, which have led to the evolution of a myriad of unique genes, molecules and compounds that can be discovered through marine bioprospecting and find application through marine biotechnology (Pathak, 2020; Bethel et al., 2021). The potential for discovering new products with biotechnological applications is high in north-east Tobago's waters, given the rich marine biodiversity and the significant genetic repository it represents. Therefore, marine bioprospecting and biotechnology has the scope to play a central role in the Blue Economy of the study area (and the country as a whole). It has to be admitted that this is an economically uncertain venture: tens of thousands of biological compounds (e.g., peptides,

terpenes, and alkaloids) have to be analysed to find a promising one, and only one in fifty leads can result in a marketable product after about 15 years (Hunt and Vincent, 2006 as cited by Cisneros-Montemayor et al., 2019; March et al., 2023). Almost prohibitive barriers in this sector are the therefore high investment costs, protracted processes, and the lacking guarantee that a product will reach the market (Piker, 2016 as cited by Phang et al., 2023). At the same time, however, it has been claimed that discovering a compound in coral reefs that might lead to a new drug can be a few hundred times more likely than doing so on land (Bruckner, 2002). An immeasurable number of new and potentially profitable medical and industrial products could be derived from marine organisms: from pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals and antibiotics, to cosmeceuticals, antifreeze and antifouling paints (FAO, 2016b; Kim, 2019). Just to give an example from the Caribbean region, the compound isolated from the soft coral *Antillologorgia elisabethae* found in the Bahamas has led to the successful development of a cosmetic product worth 3 – 4 million USD annually (Bifani et al., 2019). Modern technology makes it possible to synthesise compounds in a laboratory, which means that there is no need to overharvest wild organisms (Hunt and Vincent, 2006 as cited by Cisneros-Montemayor et al., 2019). At the same time, this resulted in a significant drawback: private companies could patent and produce compounds without having to share the potential benefits with the countries where these compounds were found, and which alone were (and still are) unable to venture into the sector, especially in the case of SIDS (UNCTAD, 2014; Cisneros-Montemayor et al., 2019). To address these issues, the Nagoya Protocol was adopted in 2010 by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity, with the aim of ensuring a just and equitable distribution of the benefits derived from the use of genetic resources (CBD, 2015). However, Trinidad and Tobago remains a non-signatory to the Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) principles of the Nagoya Protocol (CBD, 2024). Data from 2018 reveals that a single corporation owned 47% of all marine gene patents and that 98% of all patent sequences had been registered by companies in just 10 countries, which can be explained considering that only a few large firms can afford to invest in such long-term and risky research (Blasiak et al., 2018; Cisneros-Montemayor et al., 2019). Therefore, should Tobago (or likewise Trinidad and Tobago) decide to start investigating this Blue Economy opportunity, signing and ratifying the Nagoya Protocol, along with stipulating carefully conceived agreements with private corporations, will be of paramount importance to avoid exclusion from possible economic returns. Ideally, the covenants can even lead to greater benefits beyond the ‘merely’ financial ones. Still taking the Bahamas as an example, in relation to the soft coral *A. elisabethae* there is an ABS agreement in place between three parties (i.e., the government, local communities and a foreign firm) that provides for fisherfolk training and financial income for the government through licensing (Meyer et al., 2014). To go even further, it is recommended to encourage partnerships and collaborations involving, for instance, technology transfer and student and professional exchanges (Farrier and Tucker, 2001). These types of agreements have the potential to bring much greater long-term benefits to Trinidad and Tobago than direct payments alone.

3.5.3| Marine-based renewable energy

To underpin a sustainable Blue Economy, renewable energy production is a priority. It contributes to meeting the demand for energy while reducing consumption of fossil fuels, and therefore air pollution and greenhouse gases emissions, which is vital to mitigate climate change (e.g., Pachauri et al., 2014; Ebarvia, 2016). In this context, marine-based renewable energy assumes great importance and indeed has been recognised to have enormous potential (e.g., OECD, 2016).

The first and probably biggest impediment to the development of this Blue Economy sector is the fact that Trinidad and Tobago is a hydrocarbon-based economy. So, for example, the argument that the development of renewable energy would help SIDS to become self-sufficient in energy production (Bakshi, 2019) is in no way attractive to Trinidad and Tobago. Unfortunately, during fieldwork for this study, the author did not meet nor hear of any potential interviewees who could shed light on the status or prospects for ocean-based renewables in Tobago. What is certain is that the oil and gas companies will continue with their operations, as the fields still have long lifespans and consequently will not be abandoned anytime soon to switch to renewables (UNESCO-IOC and IMA, 2021). For this reason, even if as part of CARICOM Trinidad and Tobago has committed to a renewable energy future (Phang et al., 2023), it is likely that a substantial development of this industry will only happen in the long term. Additional obstacles related to the development of marine-based renewable energy in north-east Tobago coincide with those mentioned above for aquaculture: logistical challenges, absence of qualified workforce, and difficult access to technology and materials. Thus, once again, other locations would be probably chosen for implementation.

At the same time, it is also true that the Blue Economy industry at issue would fit perfectly the UNESCO designation, since it reduces dependence on fossil fuels thereby mitigating climate change and is a sustainable sector par excellence. Not coincidentally, marine-based renewable energy is recognised as a model for a Blue Economy transition because it generates short- and long-term jobs and energy, while aiming to minimise environmental impacts (Patil et al., 2016). Moreover, SIDS have geographical advantages for ocean-based renewables (Manikarachchi, 2022) that may compensate for their limited land area. The main sources that can be exploited are wave, oceanic current, tidal and offshore wind power, thermal gradients (through ocean thermal energy conversion, OTEC), and biomass (Borthwick, 2016; Bakshi, 2019). The costs of the associated technologies have decreased enormously, which is why it has been suggested that they could be a valid solution for many Caribbean SIDS (Patil et al., 2016). Clearly, research is needed to investigate each opportunity. At this stage, it will be essential to put physical parameters (e.g., wind and current speed and consistency) in relation with the latest and best available technologies. For instance, a previous assessment of the microtidal range of the region (Kjerfve, 1981) suggests that tidal energy extraction is not economically viable, and indeed it was until recently, but nowadays there are technologies designed to operate at less energetic flows that could change the situation (Encarnacion et al., 2019).

Similarly, floating wind turbines instead of those fixed at the bottom could be the key to improving offshore wind harnessing (Bashetty and Ozcelik, 2021).

In conclusion, it is recommended that Tobago (and Trinidad and Tobago as a whole) seriously consider the possibility of marine-based renewable energies and conduct feasibility studies, given their huge potential and that dependence on hydrocarbons is unreasonable, unsustainable, as well as unfeasible when thinking in the long term.

4| Conclusion

In a Blue Economy, the ocean is seen as the frontier for economic development. This has to be undertaken in an inclusive and sustainable way, in order to benefit local communities as a whole while at the same time maintaining obligations towards a healthy environment. The Blue Economy is a great opportunity for SIDS like Trinidad and Tobago, within which the study site is located. Despite the fact that the Blue Economy is now a globally leading concept, as shown by the abundance of literature on it, estimates of its value are still extremely rare, and an analytical framework to evaluate it is actually missing (Phang et al., 2023). In addition to an economic assessment, the NETMABR also lacks a detailed description of the Blue Economy that already takes place within it and the potential it has. It is exactly these knowledge gaps that the thesis aimed to close. Consequently, three research questions guided it: what is the state of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR? (RQ1), what is the present value of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR? (RQ2), and what is the potential of a sustainable Blue Economy in the NETMABR? (RQ3).

To answer RQ1, the current Blue Economy of north-east Tobago has been described as best as possible. Inevitably, from this point of view, the focus was exclusively on fishing and tourism because they are by far the two main sectors. Simultaneously, this work sought to assess the existing Blue Economy in the study area. As a result of the investigation, the value of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR (RQ2) is presently estimated between 6'144'477 USD year⁻¹ – 7'176'635 USD year⁻¹. The vast majority of this revenue comes from tourism, while shipbuilding and repair accounts for the smallest share. The estimate is strongly conditioned by the pervasive data deficiency that characterises north-east Tobago regarding all components of the Blue Economy. To make matters worse, there was no cooperation in sharing even what little data was available. For this reason, the study did not have access to the number of visitor arrivals and to the record of fishers' landings that could have substantiated the perceived decline in fish catches. Clearly, all of this influenced, and even shaped, the investigation to answer the second research question, from the way it had to be conducted to the results it led to. To begin with, the assessment had to be based almost solely on primary data collected through specifically conceived interview questions. Then, in the absence of entirely reliable figures, the author had to make quite a few decisions on how to calculate the value of the Blue Economy (e.g., regarding the values to be used in the formulas and the reporting time period). Although such choices are believed to have been made in the best possible way, they cannot be fully accurate. Furthermore, it has to be said that the estimate does not exactly represent the value of the existing Blue Economy in the NETMABR, as various income streams, the analysis of which was not feasible given the time and resources available, were not taken into account. Lastly, the assessment did not include ecosystem services like coastal protection and carbon sequestration, which should be included in future research. Therefore, the value of the Blue Economy provided by this study must be understood as a very conservative approximation based on a number of

assumptions. Nevertheless, a calculation with a level of detail like the one presented in this dissertation had never been done for north-east Tobago, and even in the scientific literature there are very few such attempts. Thus, the main contribution of the present work is not limited to having described the Blue Economy of the study site to the best extent possible so as to provide a useful baseline for comprehending the local current situation. In fact, it has also placed an overall figure on the Blue Economy of the Biosphere Reserve for the first time. This research also adds to the literature on the Blue Economy and strategies to assess it in data-deficient scenarios in rural SIDS contexts. The last overarching objective of the thesis was to determine the potential of the Blue Economy in the NETMABR (RQ3). It has been found that there is significant potential for already established sectors, as well as for developing new ones. Regarding the first aspect, numerous solutions have been proposed to address the challenges that emerged during fieldwork, and more generally to improve the local artisanal fisheries and tourism (on the latter, see also 6.5). All the presented opportunities respect the Biosphere Reserve context and residents, and the focus of the investigation at this stage has been on those that have a connection to the local setting, for example because they are based on something that is already in place, or on possibilities suggested by local communities. Concerning the second aspect, the attention has been placed on sectors of global relevance and that are appropriate for the context of north-east Tobago: aquaculture, marine bioprospecting and biotechnology, and marine-based renewable energy. The difficulties associated with their development were briefly discussed, along with an overview of the potential they nonetheless have. Every opportunity that has been analysed, whether related to existing sectors or those yet to be established, aims to develop the Blue Economy of the NETMABR in a sustainable and inclusive manner. Therefore, they can (and should) be used to plan areas for intervention and future development. This, together with the targeted recommendations that have been offered for stakeholders, practitioners and policy makers to take, represents the other main contribution of the dissertation.

Finally, suggestions have been made in the area of management, which was explored for artisanal fisheries and tourism. Study results revealed that while in the case of fisheries it is essential to take action to address the present situation of (perceived) drastic decline in catches, tourism management is more on a preventive basis to keep the destination unspoilt and develop the sector in a sustainable way. Indeed, although the number of visitors is currently low in north-east Tobago, the importance of the industry makes it imperative to govern its growth. Interventions in terms of closures during the reproductive season of selected fish species, gear-and mesh size restrictions, size limit regulations and FADs governance were recommended for the fisheries; management related to visitor numbers and recreational spearfishing was recommended for tourism. Additionally, factors likely to increase compliance with these possible future management measures have been identified: strict sanctions, growing management and trust over time, education and outreach, and co-management. In this last respect, the urgency of shifting from the current top-down approach to one based on ongoing

consultation and involvement of local communities (and ideally also on learning by doing) was emphasised. The enabling environment for this can be TOBIMA, the multi-sectoral organisation that sets out to implement the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere Programme in Tobago and to promote and facilitate collaboration among stakeholders.

The thesis also discussed the possibility of the establishment of the North-East Tobago MPA, which has been planned as a Buffer Zone of the NETMABR but has not yet been implemented. North-east Tobago has been described as an ideal site for an MPA, and it is argued that this would provide the perfect environment for the introduction of some of the proposed management actions, thereby positively impacting both tourism and fisheries and, by consequence, local communities.

The Blue Economy has the capacity to strengthen Tobago's economy by creating employment and reallocating a good part of the workforce. In this way, not so many people would be dependent on public sector employment anymore, which would support the local government as well. At present, however, north-east Tobago's marine and coastal environment is not realising its capabilities in terms of economic and social benefits. The underdevelopment of the Blue Economy, mainly due to the fact that it has never been considered a priority nationwide, implies that its progression can be achieved by shadowing the positive experiences of other SIDS, especially in the Caribbean. At the same time, by developing a sustainable, regenerative, and inclusive Blue Economy, perhaps by putting into practice the opportunities that have been identified and proposed in this thesis, the NETMABR could in turn share its lessons learned, thus becoming a regional role model and fulfilling the mandate of the Man and the Biosphere programme.

The study concludes that the potential for the Blue Economy in north-east Tobago is considerable and is further heightened by the UNESCO designation, which is suitable for its development and for attracting research and international investments. Action is needed, and this can only happen if Tobago realises the critical role the marine and coastal environment can play in its development, with the NETMABR having both the possibility and scope to execute the concept of the Blue Economy.

5| References

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6| Appendix

6.1| Interview guidelines

The following lists present questions that were part of the guidelines used as a reference during semi-structured interviews with fisherfolk (6.1.1), tour and dive operators (6.1.2), accommodation providers (6.1.3), lifeguards (6.1.4), and boat builders (6.1.5). The questions are thematically grouped, indicated by italic headings.

6.1.1| Interview questions for fisherfolk

Occupation as a fisher:

How many days do you go fishing per week?

How much time do you spend fishing on a typical day?

Do you own a boat or do you borrow one from someone else?

What kind of engine does the boat have (stroke and horsepower)?

[If the interviewee owns a boat] Do you lend your boat to other people?

Do you go fishing alone or are there other people fishing with you on the same boat?

What kind of fishing techniques do you employ?

[If the answer includes nets / pots] How frequently do you check nets and/or pots?

Is the fishing gear yours or do you borrow it from others?

[If the interviewee owns it] Do you lend it to other fishers?

Do you use any kind of technology on your boat?

How far from the coast do you fish?

Do you use FADs?

[If so] Do you also set them?

Are there specific times of the year in which you catch more, or others where you catch less?

Does the sale of the fish vary depending on the time of the year?

Does the fish price vary over time?

Do you always sell all your catch on the very same day you went fishing?

Are you part of a Fisherfolk Association / Cooperative?

Do you have another job?

Livelihood constraints, challenges and opportunities:

On a scale from 1 to 10, how happy are you regarding the fishing facility here in [village name]?
Do you think it needs improvement?

How long have you been fishing?
Has your catch changed since you started?
In your opinion, is fish (still) abundant?

[If appropriate based on previous answers] Why do you think the catch (and its size) has decreased?

Are there any difficulties or issues you are experiencing in fishing?

What are your hopes for the future of the fisheries in Tobago?

Assessing the economic value of the fisheries sector in the NETMABR:

How much do you spend on fuel per fishing trip?

How much do you spend on ice per fishing trip?

Did you go fishing today?
[If so] How many pounds of fish did you catch?

How many pounds of fish do you usually catch per fishing trip?

Currently, what is your catch on a very good day?
How often does that happen?

Currently, what is your catch on a very bad day?
How often does that happen?

6.1.2| Interview questions for tour and dive operators

Occupation as a tour / dive operator:

What kind of services / activities do you offer?

[If applicable] Are you a certified tour guide?

Do you advertise?

Are you part of a Tourism Association?

Livelihood constraints, challenges and opportunities:

What do you think is the current state of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago?

Besides during the Covid period, have there been any changes in the number of tourists in the last 10 years?

And in the last 20-30?

Are there any difficulties or issues you are experiencing in your tourism business?

What are your hopes for the future of tourism in north-east Tobago?

Assessing the economic value of the tourism sector in the NETMABR:

How many people do you take on a tour / diving on average in a month?

How much do you charge for the service you offer?

6.1.3| Interview questions for accommodation providers

Occupation as an accommodation provider:

In your opinion, what is the proportion of guests that undertake marine activities as part of their stay or as their only focus?

Do you advertise?

Are you part of a Tourism Association?

Livelihood constraints, challenges and opportunities:

What do you think is the current state of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago?

Besides during the Covid period, have there been any changes in the number of tourists in the last 10 years?

And in the last 20-30?

Are there any difficulties or issues you are experiencing in your tourism business?

What are your hopes for the future of tourism in north-east Tobago?

Assessing the economic value of the tourism sector in the NETMABR:

What is the annual occupancy rate of your accommodation?

6.1.4| Interview questions for lifeguards

How many people come to this beach on average (weekdays, weekends / holidays, high season and low season)?

On a scale from 1 to 10, how happy are you regarding the beach facility here in [village name]?

Do you think it needs improvement?

Do you think that something needs to be implemented on this beach?

What do you think is the current state of the tourism sector in north-east Tobago?

Besides during the Covid period, have there been any changes in the number of tourists in the last 10 years?

And in the last 20-30?

Are there any difficulties or issues you notice in the tourism business?

What are your hopes for the future of tourism in north-east Tobago?

6.1.5] Interview questions for boat builders

Occupation as a boat builder:

What is the size of the pirogues that you build?

How long does it take to build a boat?

Do you have another job?

Livelihood constraints, challenges and opportunities:

Are there any difficulties or issues you are experiencing in your business?

What are your hopes for the future of the boat building sector in north-east Tobago?

Assessing the economic value of the boat building sector in the NETMABR:

How many boats do you typically build in a year?

How much does it cost to have a boat built?

6.2| Codification results

Supplementary Table 1. Overview of the codes used for data analysis and their main subdivisions

Code	First-level subcode
Reasons for declining catches and related interventions	Oil and gas companies
	Foreign fishing vessels
	FADs
	Overfishing and other bad fishing practices
	Climate change
Improving the fisheries sector	Government financial assistance
	Training and education
	Management
	Bureaucracy
	Cooperation within fishing communities
Reasons for the low influx of tourists	Marketing
	Airlift
Improving the tourism sector	Government financial assistance
	Foreign investments
	Training and education
	Management
	Collaboration among stakeholders
	Product development
<i>Sargassum</i>	
Need for further government support and general criticism	Fish sales
	Safety
	Missing infrastructure
	Lack of consultation
	Lack of support

A few themes have not been covered in chapter 3 due to prioritisation reasons.

6.3| Fisheries data

Supplementary Table 2. Figures used to estimate the value of the fisheries sector

Interviewee number	Fishing days per week	Approximate fuel (left) and ice (right) expenditure per fishing trip (TTD)		Usual catch (pounds)
1	6	1200	150	/
2	1	400	30	50 - 60
3	2	500	60	30 - 40
4	3	300	30	20
5	5	900	60	50
6	5	750	60	30 - 40
7	5	800	60	50 - 60
8	5	600	100	50
9	6	600	40	60
10	5	1000	50	60 - 70
11	5	1000	80	50 - 60
12	5	300	30	30
13	3	300	35	10 - 15
14	5	500	30	30
15	5	550	30	20
16	1	300	40	20
17	1	250	60	50
18	3	500	25	15
19	2	400	0	0 - 7
20	2	400	0	40 - 50
21	6	400	20	15
22	4	1000	80	30
23	4	250	60	70
24	1	300	50	100
25	6	2300	300	100 - 200
26	2	800	40	30
27	6	800	40	40
28	3	1500	200	100 - 150
29	2	1000	60	80
30	4	500	50	30
31	6	400	30	30
32	5	1300	60	60
33	5	1500	300	100 - 150
34	6	800	80	40 - 50
35	6	1000	100	100
36	6	2000	500	200 - 300
37	4	1000	200	50
38	5	400	30	20 - 30
39	6	2000	500	200-300
40	5	/	/	/
41	3	500	0	30
42	6	300	30	20 - 30
43	2	500	60	80
44	6	900	30	15
45	5	250	30	20
46	6	1200	60	100

The symbol “/” indicates missing data due to the interruption of the interview during the final part. An ice expenditure of 0 means that study participants reported to produce ice on their own.

Similar tables exist also for the tourism and shipbuilding sectors, but they are not disclosed here for ethical reasons. Given the very small number of tour and dive operators and boat builders in north-east Tobago, the figures could lead to the identification of interviewees, who were instead guaranteed confidentiality. Interested people may contact the author.

6.4| Accommodations

Supplementary Table 3. Accommodation properties in north-east Tobago

	Property name	Location
1	RefleXion Views	Belle Garden
2	Auchenbago Rustic Luxury	Bloody Bay
3	Erasmus Cove	Bloody Bay
4	Alibaba's Sea Breeze	Castara
5	Baywatch Apartments	Castara
6	Blue Mango Cottages	Castara
7	Boatview Apartments	Castara
8	Carpe Diem Villa	Castara
9	Castara Bliss	Castara
10	Castara Cottage	Castara
11	Castara Inn	Castara
12	Castara Retreats	Castara
13	Castara Villas	Castara
14	Coffee House Apartments	Castara
15	Cottage Mango	Castara
16	C&K Apartments	Castara
17	Golden Apple Cottage	Castara
18	Guava Shores	Castara
19	La Casa de Castara	Castara
20	Lilibets	Castara
21	Mango Bottom Cottage	Castara
22	Mot Mot	Castara
23	Naturalist Beach Resort	Castara
24	Oceanview Castara Roundhouse	Castara
25	Seascape	Castara
26	The Beach House	Castara
27	The Little House on the Hill	Castara
28	The Littler House on the Hill	Castara
29	Bella Vista Cottage	Charlotteville
30	Belle Aire Inn	Charlotteville
31	Campbellton Beach House	Charlotteville
32	Chachalaca Villa	Charlotteville
33	Cholson Chalets	Charlotteville
34	Dr. P Guesthouse	Charlotteville
35	Greencorner Villa Guesthouse	Charlotteville
36	Man-O-War Bay Cottages	Charlotteville
37	Nicoville	Charlotteville
38	Rosa's House	Charlotteville
39	Rustic 5 Bedroom Vacation Home	Charlotteville
40	The Big Fish	Charlotteville
41	The Charlottevilla	Charlotteville
42	Oceanview Mountain Top Birdwatchers Paradise	Charlotteville

43	Tony's Offgrid Cabin Getaway	Charlottesville
44	Top River Pearl	Charlottesville
45	Property without a name	Charlottesville
46	Crab Inn Guesthouse	Delaford
47	Oceanview Cottage	Delaford
48	Bayview Cottage	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
49	Parrot Estate Villa	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
50	Silk Cotton Cottages	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
51	Tanager Ridge Villa	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
52	The Wood House	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
53	Victory Villa	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
54	Villa Escalante	Englishman's Bay / Parrot Hall
55	Bay Cottage	Parlatuvier
56	Beach Side Apartments	Parlatuvier
57	Conscious Cabin	Parlatuvier
58	Dynasty	Parlatuvier
59	Essex Cottage	Parlatuvier
60	Sea Shell Apartment House	Parlatuvier
61	Sugar Shack Cabin	Parlatuvier
62	Tamarind House Villa	Parlatuvier
63	Birdwatchers Cottages	Speyside
64	Blue Waters Inn	Speyside
65	Grandview Guesthouse	Speyside
66	Manta Suites	Speyside
67	Nature View	Speyside
68	Tencent Guesthouse	Speyside
69	Topranking Guesthouse	Speyside

6.5| Further potential of the tourism sector

Supplementary Table 4. Overview of further promising tourism opportunities in north-east Tobago

Subsector or opportunity	Description
<i>Diving</i>	<p>Diving is recognised as the most important niche market in Tobago. Dive sites are scattered all over the NETMABR, and some of them (e.g., around Little Tobago and St. Giles Islet Complex) are internationally renowned. At present, diving is focused exclusively on the observation of marine biodiversity, at some locations in a very special context of hard coral – sponge co-dominated reefs due to the influence of the Orinoco plume, and on recreational spearfishing (spearfishing on scuba is permitted). The diversification of this lucrative niche is very promising for north-east Tobago.</p> <p>A first opportunity is conservation and ‘research’ diving: from underwater clean-ups and activities in the coral nurseries, to Reef Check dives. These options are currently offered by the ERIC in Charlotteville, but there is scope to both enhance them in this village (e.g., by advertising them more, setting regular weekly or monthly days and actively inviting customers to take part in them) and extend the operations to other NETMABR areas.</p> <p>A second opportunity is archaeological diving. Tobago changed hands many times throughout its history, and so there are many different artifacts buried in the bays. Lastly, a great potential exists for spearfishing the invasive lionfish (<i>Pterois volitans</i>). Dive operators are well aware of the threat they pose to local ecosystems, and are therefore very active in removing them. The benefits are clear to see: the most frequently visited sites are definitely freer of lionfish. This invasive species is still very abundant, but the effectiveness of that practice to at least partially control localised sub-populations should not be overlooked. Coming to its potential for tourism, the PADI Invasive Lionfish Tracker Distinctive Specialty is starting to be highly requested by visitors, and those who are already certified are taking part in the spearfishing of that species more and more frequently. This possibility should be popularised and encouraged more, as hunting exclusively for lionfish is a sustainable practice with a positive environmental impact and adds to the revenues of the diving sector</p>
<i>Recreational fishing</i>	<p>Recreational fishing exists in north-east Tobago, but to a very small extent. Trips are offered from Charlotteville, Speyside, Castara and Parlatuvier, generally by the same people who organise sightseeing tours, but they are not advertised and the number of customers is currently very low.</p> <p>Recreational fishing holds great potential in the NETMABR. The most important aspect would be to valorise it through the inclusion of the cultural dimension. Locals could share their rich cultural heritage, e.g. by telling visitors anecdotes about Tobago’s waters and the history of fishing on the island, how the profession has changed over time, but also by explaining the traditional fishing gear and methods, fished species and so on. In addition, fisherfolk could organise lunch or dinner on board or on shore, and promote sustainable recreational fishing (e.g., catching only certain species and sizes) and associated data collection. Some properties could then specialise in accommodating recreational fishers, for example by offering direct boat access through contacts with local fisherfolk, in a perfect community-based tourism. The idea is to have game fishing businesses that offer all that, advertise effectively, and are trained in safety practices. In this way, recreational fishing can become a significant niche market and allow to preserve and strengthen local livelihoods and culture</p>

Supplementary Table 4 (continued)

Subsector or opportunity	Description
<i>Turtle watching</i>	<p>The coastal area of north-east Tobago is the habitat of five species of sea turtles, including regionally important rookeries for the critically endangered hawksbill and leatherback sea turtles. The main Association that used to deal with them in the NETMABR is no longer operational. Among other things, they used to organise observations with tourists during the laying of eggs and hatching. Therefore, at the moment this potentially highly profitable business is not capitalised on at all. Restarting this activity, clearly in a sustainable way (e.g., accompanied by beach clean-ups) and with full respect of turtles (e.g., no disturbing lights, very limited amount of people), is a very big opportunity. First of all, this would certainly increase the revenue of the tourism sector and may help develop it, as the possibility of turtle watching could be one of the highlights of tourists' visit. In this last regard, if properly advertised, it could increase the attractiveness of the destination. Secondly, but not less important, turtle watching could contribute to the protection of the species. The main threat to sea turtles in Tobago is a local tradition of consumption: they are an expensive delicacy that is consumed during birthdays and harvest festivals. Although there are very severe penalties (liability upon conviction is a fine up to 100'000 TTD and imprisonment for up to two years), the law is not strongly enforced and there are not enough controls, which is why poaching continues (according to some stakeholders at extremely high rates). From this point of view, sustainable and highly profitable turtle watching activities with tourists could raise awareness among locals about the importance of these creatures, even for the local economy, and increase their level of protection through more frequent monitoring</p>
<i>Dolphin watching</i>	<p>While seeing whales around north-east Tobago is seasonal and quite rare, fisherfolk report to see dolphins almost every day and throughout the year. So, during informal conversations emerged that this kind of business could be feasible. Frequently encountered species are the common bottlenose dolphin (<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>) and the melon-headed whale (<i>Peponocephala electra</i>, still belonging to the family Delphinidae). As in the case of turtle watching, this activity must be carried out with total respect of the animals (e.g., regulations on the approach distance, no potentially disturbing behaviours). It could be combined with coastline sightseeing to improve customer satisfaction and with environmental education for a complete ecotourism experience</p>
<i>Alternative tours</i>	<p>Currently, tours that fall within the Blue Economy are limited to coastline sightseeing and Little Tobago. The options are therefore very limited and rather standard. Potential indeed exists to develop new activities based on Tobago's valuable ecosystems. To begin with, wetland, mangrove and river ecological tours are considerable opportunities. Wetland tours could take place in Bloody Bay and Kings Bay, mangrove tours in Louis D'Or and Kings Bay, and river tours for instance along the Bloody Bay River. Tour guides would have a lot to explain about the ecology of these ecosystems and their abundant biodiversity. In the case of river trekking, for example, tours could start from a river mouth and end at a spring or waterfall, and be focused on the gradual change of the flora and fauna and on their conservation.</p> <p>Another option is coastal hikes, a very beautiful one of which could be realised between Speyside and Charlotteville. Trail development is necessary, but the potential undoubtedly exists.</p> <p>Lastly, St. Giles is not as popular as it should be. Even if it is not possible to walk on the islets, the complex is a wildlife sanctuary, an Important Bird and Biodiversity Area (it is believed to host one of the largest breeding populations of <i>Fregata magnificens</i> in the Caribbean), and the surrounding reefs are very beautiful. However, tour guides generally do not advertise St. Giles, which instead holds great potential</p>

Supplementary Table 4 (continued)

Subsector or opportunity	Description
<i>Light boating</i>	Great potential exists also for unmotorised boating activities in Castara, Englishman’s Bay, Kings Bay and Charlotteville, as these areas are very sheltered. The opportunities include sailing dinghies and sailing schools for kids, kayaking, canoeing, and paddleboarding. The objects are all quite cheap and require very low maintenance, and could be rented out either for independent use or for use during short organised excursions (e.g., to Pirate’s Bay and beaches not accessible by land such as Lovers’ Bay)
<i>Advertising</i>	Study results revealed that only 36% of accommodation providers and tour and dive operators interviewed have a website, and that only 48% and 39% use Facebook and Instagram, respectively, which in some cases were last updated many years ago. The most common way to advertise is by word of mouth (27 out of 33 people), which clearly makes it extremely difficult for many properties and tour operators to become known to large numbers of international tourists. Due to the difficulty in finding information online about services for tourists, it cannot be excluded that many potential visitors choose other destinations. Therefore, advertising with websites and social networks is strongly recommended to improve tourism in north-east Tobago
<i>Science tourism</i>	The NETMABR is already visited by scientists and student groups from both national and international institutions. Research and environmental education activities have mainly increased since 2014 with the establishment of the first permanent research facility by the ERIC in Charlotteville, which is now a national science-tourism hotspot. Continuing on this path has potential for north-east Tobago, especially in terms of promoting research with direct application and/or that could lead to benefits for local communities
<i>Culture tourism</i>	“Local culture, people and heritage” is one of the cornerstones of TTAL, as tourists see involvement in the local culture as something that enhances their experience, or even as the main reason for visiting. In fact, in north-east Tobago visitors have the opportunity to experience a traditional fishing village life and take part in unique events. The cultural dimension of tourism has immense potential for the Blue Economy in the NETMABR for two main reasons. First of all, the local cultural heritage is ocean-oriented, meaning that they are strongly intertwined. Valuing more this connection has the capacity to really improve tourism in the Biosphere Reserve. Secondly, Tobago hosts many cultural events that already attract people (see Table 3, but there are many more that do not fall directly within the Blue Economy), who however often stay only for the duration of the celebration. The key here is to try to seize the opportunity and entice tourists to stay longer by combining their primary reason for visiting with activities such as diving, snorkelling and visiting the islets. All of that also supports the preservation and enhancement of local cultural traditions
<i>Yachts</i>	In addition to making the use of the moorings in Charlotteville mandatory, they could be installed in Castara in order to prevent anchor damage and capitalise more on yachts here as well (Man-o-War and Castara Bay are the only sheltered areas where yachts can stay for long periods of time in north-east Tobago). Moreover, the services for yachties (e.g., pet therapy, braiding) advertised on the website of the buoys of Man-o-War Bay (https://www.tobago-moorings.com/services) are not actually offered, or at least not regularly. Committing to providing such services could improve yachties’ experience and ensure a constant source of income for some community members